

Doctoral Dissertation

博士論文

Detailed Chemical Abundances of Cepheids Based on Near-Infrared Spectra

(近赤外線高分散分光観測にもとづく
セファイド変光星の詳細な化学組成解析)

A Dissertation Submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

December 2021

令和3年12月博士（理学）申請

Department of Astronomy, Graduate School of Science,

The University of Tokyo

東京大学大学院理学系研究科

天文学専攻

SAEZ ELGUETA, Scarlet Margarita

サエズ エルゲタ, スカーレット マルガリタ

“It is hard for fish to be aware of water. It is hard for us to notice something that’s an ingrained pattern shaping our habitual thought.”

Anne Chapman

Abstract

Detailed Chemical Abundances of Cepheids Based on Near-Infrared Spectra

by SAEZ ELGUETA, Scarlet Margarita

Classical Cepheids (hereinafter, simply Cepheids) are pulsating stars evolved from intermediate-mass stars with 4 to 11 solar masses. The importance of Cepheids is not limited to their unique value as distance indicators, but they are also good tracers of chemical abundances in their hosting galaxies as we can observe a considerable number of absorption lines in their spectra, allowing the abundance determination of different kinds of elements. Observing Cepheids in the infrared poses a clear advantage over the optical observations as the interstellar extinction is significantly lower in the infrared bands, and objects heavily affected by the extinction are thus within the scope of infrared spectroscopic techniques. Yet, the implementation of such techniques requiring basic information such as a list of infrared absorption lines has not been as evolved as optical spectroscopy. Hence, exploring the IR regime is necessary to uplift the employed methods and to make their results comparable to those in optical studies for objects as complex as obscured stars or objects at different regions within our Galaxy. Establishing the chemical abundance analysis for such objects would pave the way for investigating the chemical structure of the Galactic disk, from the center to its outskirts, thereby extending the frontier of Galactic archaeology.

In this thesis, we report a high-resolution spectroscopic analysis of Cepheids in our Galaxy observed in the near-infrared YJ bands ($0.96\text{--}1.35\ \mu\text{m}$) using the WINERED spectrograph ($R = \lambda / \Delta\lambda = 28000$). We aim to establish a method to derive accurate and precise stellar parameters, T_{eff} and $\log g$, as well as chemical abundances of several elements based on YJ -band spectra.

Our sample consists of well-known Cepheids in the solar neighborhood observed during the first runs of WINERED in Japan while mounted on the Araki Telescope (1.3m aperture) at Kyoto Sangyo University in 2013–2016, as well as Cepheids at large distances in the Galactic disk, detected by the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment (OGLE) and later observed with WINERED on the ESO New Technology Telescope (NTT, 3.58m aperture) in 2017 at La Silla observatory, Chile.

Our sample of Cepheids is divided into three groups: Calibrators, Validators, and Disk Targets. The Calibrator sample consists of 8 Cepheids that have been widely studied (mainly in optical) and for which a good set of time-series spectra with WINERED are available. This sample is first used to find and calibrate the relations that enable us to estimate the effective temperature and surface gravity. On the other hand, the Validator sample consists of 5 Cepheids with a limited number of spectra or little information available in the literature. This sample is used to test and validate the relations obtained with the Calibrators. Finally, we applied the calibrated and validated relations to the 9 Cepheids of the Disk Target sample. The summary of the observation log can be found in Table 2.3. The step of establishing the abundance analysis takes a similar path; we use the Calibrators and Validators to identify useful absorption lines and calibrate their oscillator strengths, and then apply our findings for measuring the abundances of the Disk Targets. In contrast to the Calibrator and Validator samples mostly with a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) higher than 200, we have the WINERED spectra only with low S/N ranging from ~ 40 to over 100 for the Disk Targets. An important question during the following analysis is how good YJ -band spectra are required to measure the abundances well. Roughly speaking, we need $S/N=100$ or higher depending on the effective temperature, as we see below.

FIGURE 1: Spectroscopic estimates of T_{eff} and $\log g$ plotted against the pulsation phase for δ Cep.

For the step of determining the stellar parameters, we employed the line-depth ratio (LDR) method. The method requires selecting pairs of absorption lines whose excitation potentials differ from each other and whose ratios of depth are tightly correlated with the effective temperature and surface gravity.

This method has been widely used in the optical regime. Some recent works have been done in the infrared regime, but the LDR relations therein cover a limited range of the stellar parameters. We need to extend the parameter range to cover the distribution of Cepheids, i.e., $4500 < T_{\text{eff}} < 6500\text{K}$ and $1.0 < \log g < 2.5$. Selecting line pairs that are useful for this parameter range, we have found 12 pairs of two Fe I lines showing tight LDR- T_{eff} relations, while 5 Fe I- Fe II pairs and 5 Ca I- Ca II pairs follow tight LDR- T_{eff} - $\log g$ relations. By applying these new 22 empirical relations established with the Calibrators to the Validators, we found that our LDR relations enable an estimate as precise as 90 K in T_{eff} and 0.2 dex in $\log g$. However, the LDR relations we found require S/N around 100 or higher. Moreover, absorption lines tend to be very weak in Cepheids with higher T_{eff} , and it is hard to give precise estimates of stellar parameters. To overcome this difficulty, we found that we can use the T_{eff} - $\log g$ - $\log P$ relation of classical Cepheids. The literature T_{eff} and $\log g$ show

the correlation expected from the instability strip, and we discovered that including the $\log P$ term (logarithm of the pulsation period) reduces the scatter down to 0.108 dex. This scatter is as small as the error in $\log g$ estimated with the LDR relations in best cases and also comparable with best spectroscopic estimates with other methods (Meszaros 2013, *AJ*, 146, 133). Thus, we can use the LDR-based T_{eff} and the $\log g$ based on this $T_{\text{eff}}\text{--}\log g\text{--}\log P$ relation with a precision of 0.12 dex (see Figure 1)).

Once the T_{eff} and $\log g$ get estimated, we can go on to the measurements of chemical abundances. For this purpose, we first need to establish a list of lines that are present in the *YJ*-band spectra of Cepheids and useful for the abundance analysis. We used the Vienna Atomic Line Database (VALD) and the list of Melendez & Barbuy (1999, *ApJS*, 124, 527) as the starting point, and we identified dozens of absorption lines of several species including Dy, Si, P, Fe, and Y. However, the information of lines in the infrared regime tends to be inaccurate. It is necessary to confirm or calibrate the oscillator strengths ($\log gf$) before precise abundance measurements become possible. Therefore, we calibrated the $\log gf$ using the spectra of Calibrator Cepheids whose stellar parameters and abundances have been well known based on optical spectra. Finally, we calibrated the $\log gf$ of 102 absorption lines (16 Si I, 9 P I, 2 S I, 9 Ca I, 1 Ca II, 46 Fe I, 12 Fe II, 1 Zn I, 5 Y II, and 1 Dy II lines).

Another crucial ingredient needed in the abundance analysis is microturbulence (ζ). This parameter controls the effect of line saturation and has a direct impact on the abundances inferred from strong, saturated lines. Like in previous works on Cepheids' abundances, we use 1D hydrostatic atmosphere models and employ a fixed ζ for each spectrum due to the lack of established models with depth-dependent microturbulence. Considering the number of lines, we are forced to use Fe I lines to estimate ζ , again, as done by most previous works with optical spectra. We confirmed that Fe I lines (42 from VALD and 37 from MB99) can be used for this purpose, and then we successfully determined ζ of Validators and Disk Targets (except a few with very low S/N) in a manner consistent with the Calibrators whose ζ varying with pulsation phase were known. However, we found that the same ζ fails to give

reasonable abundances for very strong lines. We consider that this is because the microturbulence is different in the upper layers of the atmosphere where the strong lines are formed. Avoiding such deep lines has been commonly done in previous works, and we determined that the depth limit appears at 0.2 in depth (with the spectral resolution of 28000). Therefore, we decided to exclude lines deeper than 0.2 from our analysis, including the $\log gf$ calibration.

Thus, we have established the procedures of using the YJ -band spectra of Cepheids to derive the stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, and ξ) and the chemical abundances of 10 species from Si to Dy, including Fe as the most fundamental metal. We also provide the list of absorption lines with the $\log gf$ calibrated. The calibration was done by using 51 spectra of 8 Calibrator Cepheids. The test of our procedures on 17 spectra of 5 Validators shows that the abundances can be well measured with precision around 0.06 dex, although a couple of species (especially Ca II, Zn I, and Dy II) have too few lines to allow a robust estimation in many spectra. The analysis on 9 spectra of 9 Disk Targets (no time-series spectra for this group) gives a good demonstration of how high S/N is required to use our procedures and how promising the YJ bands would be to explore the chemical abundances of Cepheids spread over a large part of the Galactic disk. Among the 9 Disk Targets, we failed to estimate the LDR-based T_{eff} of 2 objects with no LDR pairs measured properly. Their spectra are of low S/N, 40–65, and T_{eff} of these short-period ($P < 5$ days) Cepheids are expected to be high. In addition, for 2 other short-period Cepheids, we could use only a couple of LDR pairs also because of the limited S/N and the high T_{eff} (inferred from the short periods). For the other 5 objects, we obtained $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ and the abundances of a few other elements, although the abundances of some elements could not be measured. Even though the uncertainties in stellar parameters and abundances for the Disk Targets are not negligible, the results follow the trends seen in previous works, e.g., the abundance gradient showing the decreasing trend of abundance with increasing distance from the Galactic center (Figure 2).

This work demonstrated for the first time that the detailed chemical abundances

FIGURE 2: The abundance gradient of a few elements obtained with the YJ -band spectra compared to the results with optical spectra from Luck (2018)

of Cepheids can be derived with near-infrared spectra as precisely as optical spectra. Our results look promising for considering future observations of new Cepheids with near-infrared spectrographs such as WINERED, which will soon be operating on the 6.5m Magellan Telescope at Las Campanas Observatory (LCO), Chile. The failure of our procedures with short-period Cepheids observed with lower S/N suggests that it is recommended to observe relatively long-period Cepheids, which are also bright, with sufficient S/N about 100 or higher in future projects to investigate Cepheids across the Galactic disk.

Contents

Abstract	v
Acknowledgements	xiii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 The Milky Way	1
1.1.1 Chemodynamical evolution of the Milky Way	1
1.1.2 The components of the Milky Way	2
1.2 Pulsating stars: Cepheids	6
1.2.1 Discovery of Cepheids	6
1.2.2 Why does a Cepheid pulsate?	8
1.2.3 Cepheids as tracers in the Milky Way	11
1.3 Infrared Spectroscopy	13
1.4 Aims	16
1.5 The Structure of this Thesis	19
2 Targets and Observations	21
2.1 Targets	21
2.2 Observations	25
2.2.1 WINERED	25
2.2.2 Observations of Calibrator and Validator Cepheids with the Araki Telescope	27
2.2.3 Observations of Disk Target Cepheids with the NTT	27
2.3 Stellar Parameters from Literatures	32
2.3.1 Light curves	32
2.3.2 Phase-by-phase Stellar Parameters from Literatures	34
2.4 Chemical Abundances from Literatures	36

3	Data Reduction	39
3.1	Data Reduction	39
3.1.1	Sky subtraction	40
3.1.2	Wavelength calibration	40
3.2	Signal-to-Noise Ratio	43
3.3	Telluric Correction	45
3.4	Continuum Normalization	46
3.5	Correction of Wavelength Shift	48
4	Effective Temperature and Surface Gravity	49
4.1	Introduction	49
4.1.1	Approaches for estimating effective temperature	50
4.1.2	Approaches for estimating surface gravity	52
4.1.3	The LDR method	53
4.1.4	The goal of this chapter	53
4.2	Line Identification and Selection	53
4.2.1	Hands on: measuring the line depth	54
4.3	LDR Relations Established With the Calibrators' Spectra	55
4.4	Application of the LDR Relations	61
4.5	Trend of Temperature and Surface Gravity	62
5	Abundance Analysis: Methodology	67
5.1	Introduction	67
5.1.1	Oscillator strength: log gf values	68
5.1.2	Microturbulence	70
5.2	Tools for Measuring Abundances with Individual Lines	71
5.2.1	Stellar models	71
5.2.2	Line lists	71
5.2.3	Spectral synthesis codes: MOOG	72
5.2.4	MPFIT	73
5.3	Methods	76
5.3.1	Abundances as a function of microturbulence	76
5.3.2	Calibrating the oscillator strengths	78

5.3.3	Determining microturbulence	79
5.3.4	Determining the abundance with the microturbulence given	81
6	Abundance Analysis: Iron	83
6.1	Calibration of the Oscillator Strengths	83
6.2	Derivation of Microturbulence and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$	87
7	Abundance Analysis: Other Species	91
7.1	Introduction	91
7.2	Line Identification	92
7.3	Calibration of the Oscillator Strengths	92
7.3.1	Failed calibration including strong lines	93
7.3.2	Calibration without including strong lines	95
7.4	Derivation of abundances of various species	97
8	Discussion	105
8.1	Discussions on Stellar Parameters	105
8.1.1	Limitations due to S/N and effective temperature	105
8.1.2	The choice of literature (reference) data	107
8.1.3	The derivation of the Microturbulence	108
8.2	Discussions on Individual Elements	110
8.2.1	Ionized Iron — Fe II	110
8.2.2	Neutral Phosphorus — P I	112
8.2.3	Neutral Sulphur — S I	113
8.2.4	Alpha-elements - Si I and Ca I	115
8.2.5	Heavier elements - Zn I, Y II and Dy II	115
8.3	Abundance Gradients	116
8.4	Summary	118
A	Spectral Atlas	119
B	Light Curves	131
B.1	Calibrators	131
B.1.1	δ Cephei	131

B.1.2	η Aquilae	132
B.1.3	FF Aquilae	132
B.1.4	RT Aurigae	133
B.1.5	SU Cassiopeiae	133
B.1.6	SZ Tauri	134
B.1.7	X Cygni	134
B.1.8	ζ Geminorum	135
B.2	Validators	136
B.2.1	DL Cassiopeia	136
B.2.2	Polaris	137
B.2.3	S Sagittae	137
B.2.4	T Vultur	138
B.2.5	V367 Scuti	138
C	LDR relations	139
D	Derived Effective Temperatur eand Surface Gravity	163
E	Calibrated log gf for Fe I and species lines.	167
E.1	For Fe I	167
E.2	For species	169
F	Abundances	171
F.1	Abundances for Fe I	171
F.2	Abundances for Species	174

List of Figures

1	Spectroscopic estimates of T_{eff} and $\log g$ plotted against the pulsation phase for δ Cep.	vii
2	The abundance gradient of a few elements obtained with the YJ-band spectra compared to the results with optical spectra from Luck (2018) .	x
1.1	Schematic diagram of the Milky Way structure	2
1.2	Milky Way seen by COBE/DIRBE	4
1.3	Period–luminosity relation discovered by Leavitt	6
1.4	Artist’s impression of distance ladder	7
1.5	Instability strip on the HRD	10
1.6	Metallicity Gradient for MW Cepheids obtained by Luck (2018), P-L distances are derived in Madore, Freedman, and Moak (2017).	11
1.7	Distribution of Classical Cepheids in the Milky Way and the Magellanic Clouds. (Skowron et al., 2019)	13
1.8	Far-infrared Milky Way seen by COBE	15
1.9	Classical Cepheids in the MW. Blue circles representing Cepheids . . .	16
2.1	Distribution of the Cepheids studied in this thesis. Light blue star for Calibrators, Green star for Validators, and Pink star for Disk Cepheids. Light gray points represent the sample analyzed by Luck (2018).	22
2.2	WINERED at the Nasmyth platform of NTT	26
2.3	WINERED at the Nasmyth platform of NTT	26
2.4	NTT in the La Silla observatory	28
2.5	Light curve of X Cyg	33
2.6	Curves of effective temperature and surface gravity of X Cyg	35
2.7	The $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ – $[\text{X}/\text{Fe}]$ diagrams for literature abundances	37
3.1	Telluric absorption (orders: 43, 44, 45, 46)	41

3.2	Telluric absorption (orders: 47, 52, 56, 57)	42
3.3	S/N values for the Calibrators sample.	43
3.4	S/N values for the Validator sample.	44
3.5	S/N values for the Disk Targets sample.	44
3.6	Before and after the telluric correction and normalization	47
3.7	YII line aligned over the pulsation cycle of δ Cep	48
4.1	Illustration of the LDR method from Gray (2005).	51
4.2	Performance of the T_{LDR} estimation.	59
4.3	Same as Figure 4.2 but for $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ instead of T_{LDR}	60
4.4	Estimated T_{LDR} and $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ and their errors	61
4.5	Distribution of Cepheids' ($T_{\text{eff}}, \log g$)	63
4.6	$T_{\text{eff}}-\log P-\log g$ trend of Cepheids	64
5.1	Microturbulence and Macroturbulence difference scheme in terms of their free path. Figure from Cantiello, M. (2008).	70
5.2	The grid of ($T_{\text{eff}}, \log g$) ATLAS9 and MARCS models from Mészáros et al., 2012	71
5.3	The quartiles of FWHM (left), RV (middle), and the normalization fac- tor (right) as functions of ξ are indicated by solid curves	75
5.4	Fe I abundances as a function of microturbulence. The case of η Aql observed on 2016 March 21.	77
5.5	The slope a as a function of ξ (in the top panel) and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ as a func- tion of the X index	80
6.1	The offset in $\log gf$ inferred from individual spectra. Horizontal lines indicate the mean (solid) and the standard deviation (dotted), for which we neglected the measurements for the absorption deeper than 0.2 (vertical dotted line). This is for Fe I 9800.3075 with the original $\log gf$ taken from VALD.	84
6.2	The offsets between the original and new $\log gf$ values in our calibra- tion.	85

6.3	Comparison of $\log gf$ before and after the calibration for the lines in both VALD and MB99.	86
6.4	(Upper) The number of Fe I lines used for deriving ξ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. (Lower) The standard deviations of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from individual lines. . . .	87
6.5	Deviations of our estimates of ξ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from the literature values. For Calibrators.	88
6.6	Same as Figure 6.5, but for Validators.	88
6.7	ξ plotted against $\log P$ (upper) and T_{LDR} (lower). The orange lines indicate the approximate trends given in Equation 6.2 and 6.2	90
7.1	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for Si I lines from VALD.	94
7.2	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for Si I lines from MB99.	94
7.3	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for P I lines from VALD.	94
7.4	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for P I lines from MB99.	94
7.5	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for S I lines from VALD.	94
7.6	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for S I lines from MB99.	94
7.7	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for Ca I lines from VALD.	95
7.8	$\Delta \log gf_i$ for Ca I lines from MB99.	95
7.9	The offsets between the original and new $\log gf$ values in our calibration	96
7.10	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Si I.	99
7.11	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for P I.	99
7.12	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for S I.	100
7.13	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Ca I.	100
7.14	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Ca II.	101
7.15	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Fe II.	101

7.16	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Zn I.	102
7.17	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Y II.	102
7.18	The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Dy II.	103
7.19	[Fe/H]–[X/H] for six species (Si I, P I, S I, Ca I, Zn I, and Y II). Light blue circles represent the Calibrators. Green triangles, the Validators, and pink downward triangles represent the Disk Cepheids.	104
8.1	Temperature and surface gravity variation for 30 Cepheids in Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh (2005).	107
8.2	Comparison of the dependency of ζ on the atmosphere layer represented by the Rosseland optical depth τ_{Ross} from the studies of Kolenberg et al. (2010) and Fossati et al. (2014)	109
8.3	The different atmosphere heights (τ) for each line under study.	110
8.4	Fe I abundances for our sample of Cepheids compared to those from Luck (2018)	116
8.5	Our abundance estimates of elements other than Fe I for our sample of Cepheids compared to the results in Luck (2018).	117
A.1	Order 57 ($9760 < \lambda_{air} < 9920\text{\AA}$)	120
A.2	Order 56 ($9920 < \lambda_{air} < 10100\text{\AA}$)	121
A.3	Order 55 ($10100 < \lambda_{air} < 10280\text{\AA}$)	122
A.4	Order 54 ($10280 < \lambda_{air} < 10480\text{\AA}$)	123
A.5	Order 53 ($10480 < \lambda_{air} < 10680\text{\AA}$)	124
A.6	Order 52 ($10680 < \lambda_{air} < 10890\text{\AA}$)	125
A.7	Order 47 ($11800 < \lambda_{air} < 12050\text{\AA}$)	126
A.8	Order 46 ($12050 < \lambda_{air} < 12320\text{\AA}$)	127
A.9	Order 45 ($12320 < \lambda_{air} < 12600\text{\AA}$)	128
A.10	Order 44 ($12600 < \lambda_{air} < 12900\text{\AA}$)	129
A.11	Order 43 ($12900 < \lambda_{air} < 13190\text{\AA}$)	130

B.1	Light Curve of δ Cephei in V band and Visual band.	131
B.2	Light Curve of η Aquilae in V band and Visual band.	132
B.3	Light Curve of FF Aquilae in V band and Visual band.	132
B.4	Light Curve of RT Aurigae in V band and Visual band.	133
B.5	Light Curve of SU Cassiopeia in V band and Visual band.	133
B.6	Light Curve of SZ Tauri in V band and Visual band.	134
B.7	Light Curve of X Cygni in V band and Visual band.	134
B.8	Light Curve of ζ Geminorum in V band and Visual band.	135
B.9	Light Curve of DL Cassiopeia in V band and Visual band.	136
B.10	Light Curve of Polaris in V band and Visual band.	137
B.11	Light Curve of S Sagittae in V band and Visual band.	137
B.12	Light Curve of T Vultur in V band and Visual band.	138
B.13	Light Curve of V367 Scuti in V band and Visual band.	138
C.1	Line Pair 1: Fe I 10155.162 Å/Fe I 10353.804 Å	140
C.2	Line Pair 2: Fe I 10167.468 Å/Fe I 10347.965 Å	141
C.3	Line Pair 3: Fe I 10195.105 Å/Fe I 10216.313 Å	142
C.4	Line Pair 4: Fe I 10218.408 Å/Fe I 10227.994 Å	143
C.5	Line Pair 5: Fe I 10340.885 Å/Fe I 10532.234 Å	144
C.6	Line Pair 6: Fe I 10395.794 Å/Fe I 9861.7337 Å	145
C.7	Line Pair 7: Fe I 10423.743 Å/Fe I 10863.518 Å	146
C.8	Line Pair 8: Fe I 10577.139 Å/Fe I 10849.465 Å	147
C.9	Line Pair 9: Fe I 10616.721 Å/Fe I 9868.1857 Å	148
C.10	Line Pair 10: Fe I 10783.050 Å/Fe I 9889.0351 Å	149
C.11	Line Pair 11: Fe I 10818.274 Å/Fe I 9811.5041 Å	150
C.12	Line Pair 12: Fe I 12556.996 Å/Fe I 12648.741 Å	151
C.13	Line Pair 13: Fe I 9868.1857 Å/Fe II 9997.5980 Å	152
C.14	Line Pair 14: Fe I 10347.965 Å/Fe II 10173.515 Å	153
C.15	Line Pair 15: Fe I 10353.804 Å/Fe II 10366.167 Å	154
C.16	Line Pair 16: Fe I 10611.686 Å/Fe II 10501.500 Å	155
C.17	Line Pair 17: Fe I 10818.274 Å/Fe II 10862.652 Å	156
C.18	Line Pair 18: Ca I 10838.970 Å/Ca II 9854.7588 Å	157

C.19 Line Pair 19: Ca I 10343.819 Å / Ca II 9890.6280 Å	158
C.20 Line Pair 20: Ca I 10846.792 Å / Ca II 9931.3741 Å	159
C.21 Line Pair 21: Ca I 12105.841 Å / Ca II 11838.997 Å	160
C.22 Line Pair 22: Ca I 13033.554 Å / Ca II 11949.744 Å	161

List of Tables

1.1	The solar abundance adopted from Asplund et al. (2009)	20
2.1	Observed Cepheids and categories.	23
2.2	The previous data set used in this thesis	24
2.3	Observation Log	29
4.1	LDR relations	57
7.1	Deviations of abundances from the literature values, Luck (2018) and Usenko et al. (2005)	98
8.1	Numbers of lines with calibrated $\log gf$	118
E.1	Calibration of $\log gf$ of Fe I lines	167
E.2	Calibration of $\log gf$ of lines other than Fe I	169
F.1	Derived microturbulence and Fe I abundance	171
F.2	Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 1)	174
F.3	Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 2)	176
F.4	Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 3)	178

List of Abbreviations

ESO	European Southern Observatory
HRD	Hertzprung Russell Diagram
LC	Light Curve
LDR	Line Depth Ratio
NTT	New Technology Telescope
SNR	Signal (to) Noise Ratio
WARP	WINERED Automatic Reduction Pipeline
WINERED	Warm INfrared Echelle (spectrograph to) Realize Extreme Dispersion

To Camila, my twin and my half...

Chapter 1

Introduction

The target of study in this thesis is Cepheids, which are useful tracers for investigating the structure and evolution of the Milky Way,¹ in particular, its disk. Here, we introduce the background and motivations of studying the Milky Way disk in Section 1.1 and, then, basic features and previous studies on Cepheids in Section 1.2. We will explain, in Section 1.3, why infrared spectroscopy is important for the research of Cepheids and how it has been so far immature to the present years. Finally, we describe the goals of this study in Section 1.4.

1.1 The Milky Way

1.1.1 Chemodynamical evolution of the Milky Way

Eggen, Lynden-Bell, and Sandage (1962) pioneered the idea of the possibilities that chemodynamical analysis (abundances and stellar dynamics) offered to study the Galactic archaeology, anticipating its applications to constrain stellar nucleosynthesis models as well as setting the timescales of the formation of the different galactic structures such as the bulge, disk (thin and thick), and halo. Studies of the chemical evolution of galaxies seeks to provide hints on the synthesis of chemical elements and how their abundances evolved and will evolve as a function of position and time (Matteucci, 2021).

The field of Galactic archaeology, highlighting the importance of chemical evolution has gained accelerated growth, firstly, because of the advent of large-scale

¹The galaxy hosting us in the Solar system is called the Milky Way as well as the Galaxy (with the capital G).

spectroscopic surveys capable to map our Galaxy, e.g., APOGEE, GAIA, GAIA-ESO, GALAH, 4MOST, LAMOST (LEGUE), RAVE, and SEGUE (among others). A comprehensive review of such surveys is found in Jofré, Heiter, and Soubiran (2019). These surveys have led to estimates of chemical abundances in millions of stars. In modern studies of the chemodynamical evolution of the Milky Way (and galaxies), such observational data are combined with the progress of stellar nucleosynthesis calculations and many other “ingredients” such as the initial mass function (IMF), the star formation rate (SFR) and gas kinematics, each of which are still subjects of research for themselves. Chemodynamical models, depending on these ingredients, predict key observables such as chemical compositions of stars and gas, and are tested in comparison with observational data.

1.1.2 The components of the Milky Way

Our Galaxy is divided into various substructures: the disk which is a composition of thin and thick disks, the bulge, and the halo which can be subdivided into the stellar halo and the dark matter halo (Figure 1.1).

FIGURE 1.1: Schematic diagram of the Milky Way illustrating its components (not scaled). (Image Credit: Swinburne University of Technology, Image link: <https://astronomy.swin.edu.au/cosmos/t/thick+disk>).

The bulge, sometimes called simply “bar”, as it has been proved that a dominant

fraction of it is composed of a triaxial bar structure (López-Corredoira, Cabrera-Lavers, and Gerhard, 2005; Rattenbury et al., 2007; Saito et al., 2012). It is a commonly seen feature, especially outstanding when a galaxy is observed “edge-on”, around two-thirds of spiral galaxies display this characteristic bar-shaped structure in the center. Because of the oldness of the stellar population and the reduced impact of interstellar extinction, the bulges are often clearer in the near infrared. The origin of the Galactic bulge is thought to be a natural consequence of the instability of the disk, following the dynamics of a roughly flat rotating disk of stars (e.g., Barbuy, Chiappini, and Gerhard, 2018). The bulge homes old and α -enhanced stars that, according to Meléndez et al. (2008), may have chemical abundances similar to those of stars located in the disk.

Also, in the center of the Galaxy, we can find the core part of the Galactic halo, with a spherical shape stretching over ~ 300 kpc, far beyond the bulge and the disk. The stellar component of the halo, often referred to as stellar halo which is still difficult to distinguish from the whole big structure, though some components hosted within it can clearly be identified, those are the globular clusters containing collections of stars for which we can find some of the oldest relics in our Galaxy. The stars found in this region tend to have metallicities less than -1.0 . Its kinematics differs from the other components, having a mean rotation close to zero. According to Searle and Zinn (1978), the origin of the stellar halo is attributed mainly to the debris of small accreted galaxies yet, following the work of Eggen, Lynden-Bell, and Sandage (1962), it is also believed that a fraction (an inner component) of the halo was formed dissipatively during the galaxy formation process. An example of such phenomena that we can witness until today is how Sgr dwarf is “disrupting” our Galaxy.

The thin disk (often just called “the disk”) hosts the majority of the stars and represents a big fraction of the stellar light of the entire Milky Way, which also contains gas and dust. The Sun itself is hosted by the thin disk at about 8.5 kpc from the Galactic center. Its name comes from the fact that it is a roughly circular structure extending for at least 15 kpc from the Galactic center, whose radius is nearly 100

times larger than its height, ~ 300 pc (Bland-Hawthorn and Gerhard, 2016), as it can be appreciated in Figure 1.2.

FIGURE 1.2: Milky Way taken by the DIRBE instrument on board the Cosmic Background Explorer (COBE) satellite (Image Link: https://map.gsfc.nasa.gov/universe/rel_milkyway.html).

On the other hand, the thick disk (discovered by Yoshii, 1982; Gilmore and Reid, 1983) contains approximately 10% of the Galaxy's stellar mass, having a vertical velocity dispersion of about 40 km s^{-1} and a scale height² of about 1000 pc . The thick and thin disks have clear differences, not only given by their shape but also their kinematics and more. They host two distinct stellar populations, i.e., the thick disk contains stars older than ~ 10 Gyr with typically low metallicities ($-1.0 \leq [Fe/H] \leq -0.5$) in contrast to mostly young, metal-rich stars located in the thin disk. According to Ivezić et al. (2008), no abundance gradient is found in the thick disk, which has been later corroborated by other works such as Tautvaišienė et al. (2021) and Delgado Mena et al. (2017) showing that the slope seems to flatten at certain distances between 4.5 and 9.5 kpc. This is, however, still a matter of debate as other studies, such as the one of Boeche et al. (2013) using RAVE data, suggest that another reason for encountering such flat gradient could be the superposition of thin–thick disk stars, resulting in a mixed population displaying flatter or positive gradients. In contrast, a well-defined abundance gradient, $\sim 0.07 \text{ dex kpc}^{-1}$, is found in the thin disk traced with Cepheids (Luck, Kovtyukh, and Andrievsky, 2006; Luck and Lambert,

²For a spiral galaxy, the height above the disk at which the density of an observable (e.g. HI gas) declines by e .

2011).

As of now, we have seen that stars at different loci present distinct chemical and kinematic behaviors. The state-of-the-art Galactic archaeology is unveiling the secrets of our own galaxy. In this study, we aim to contribute to the understanding of the chemical evolution of the thin disk by establishing the method of detailed chemical analysis on Cepheids observed in the near-infrared regime.

1.2 Pulsating stars: Cepheids

1.2.1 Discovery of Cepheids

Even though timescales in nature cannot be compared, for example, our life span versus the one of an insect, or the one of a star (millions of years), one can still witness natural phenomena occurring up in the sky and by the naked eye. Centuries ago, astronomers were able to acknowledge the presence of certain objects whose appearance was variable. This led to the confirmation of this new category of stars, called *Cepheids*, of which the first discovered was δ Cep in the constellation of *Cepheus* by John Goodricke in 1784 (see Goodricke, 1786, for details).

Moving forward more than a hundred years to the beginning of the 20th century, Miss Henrietta Leavitt belonged to the infamously named “the Computers” Pickering’s team at the Harvard College observatory. One of her main tasks was to analyze photographic plates of the sky. When she was analyzing plates coming from observations performed in the Southern hemisphere, specifically the plate with “data” from the Small Magellanic Cloud, she noticed that the brightness of a certain group of stars changed in time and that such a change seemed to be *periodic*.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIGURE 1.3: Period–luminosity relation found by Ms. Henrietta Leavitt. Note that the second panel, Fig. 2 in Leavitt and Pickering (1912), represents the same as Fig. 1 but in logarithmic scale.

Thanks to her moment of realization, from her findings on how a star changed its luminosity over time (according to the pulsation period), she was able to derive the *period-luminosity relation* for Cepheids, which we now know as the Leavitt's Law establishing the foundations of cosmology by constructing what we currently know as the *extragalactic distance scale* for which Cepheids play a fundamental role, making them the primary standard candles of this ladder composed of various steps from nearby to farthest objects.

FIGURE 1.4: Distance Ladder (Image credit: NASA, ESA, A. Feild (STScI), and A. Riess (STScI/JHU), Image Link: <https://esahubble.org/images/heic1611a/>)

1.2.2 Why does a Cepheid pulsate?

Even though the application of Cepheids for the distance scale had been established, we had to wait for a time scale of a human lifetime after the Leavitt's discovery before we could truly understand the pulsation of Cepheids. Back at the beginning of the 20th century, many "peculiar" objects were already observed, such as stars that nowadays we know as Cepheids, Mira Variables, and RR Lyrae stars. Astronomers could tell there was a pulsation phenomenon on such objects but the reason of the empirical evidence showing that there was an obvious variability in their light curves could not yet be told. The "true reason" behind the pulsation was a matter of debate for several years, including renowned scientists of the epoch such as Belopolsky (1895) who noticed that the radial velocity of a Cepheid star changed in time along with the brightness variation and therefore the reason for pulsation "had to be" that Cepheids were actually spectroscopic binaries which *seemed to be* a convincing argument, to some extent, neglecting the fact that indeed *the light curve of a Cepheid star does not look like the light curve of a binary system.*

The dispute continued for several years until Shapley (1914) by making use of the new discovery of giants and dwarfs star, said that Cepheids were that big that their radii could not keep the consistency of them belonging to a binary system. Shapley could not come up with a physical explanation on the pulsation and limited himself to say " *...the only thing they have in common with ordinary spectroscopic binaries is the definitely periodic oscillation of the spectral lines ...*" but reinforced one of the fundamental ideas on these kind of objects, *radial pulsation* which was proposed by Arthur Ritter in 1879 and kept waiting to gain mathematical assessment provided by Sir Arthur Eddington. Several decades had to pass until Baker and Kippenhahn (1962), Cox and Whitney (1963) and Zhevakin (1963) to introduce the concept of non-adiabatic opacity modulations of ionizing gas in different regions of the star.

In an attempt to answer this question, it is better to consider the whole Cepheid's "life path", i.e., the evolution of the star, is mainly dictated by its mass which plays a fundamental role on a star's life. Cepheids are evolved from stars with 4–11 M_{\odot} and belong to the regime of intermediate-mass stars (Ekström et al., 2012).

Nowadays, we know that the process that drives the pulsation in Cepheids and also in other variables, such as RR Lyrae objects, is the *kappa* (κ) *mechanism* (Baker and Kippenhahn, 1962), named this way because of the symbol given for the opacity at any depth of the stellar atmosphere. For a Cepheid to keep this process running, two requirements need to be met. Firstly, it has to have enough mass at the right position, i.e., enough material to be ionized when the star is about to leave its adiabatic stage to enter into a non-adiabatic regime (Cox, 1985). In fact, several attempts were made to estimate the fraction of Helium needed to meet the first requirement, Kukarkin (1975) proposed that the fraction of initial Helium should be around 10–15 % half of which to be ionized. The second requirement is concerned with temperature within the star; the partial Helium ionization zone appears in the 35000–55000 K range. In stars like a Cepheid, this temperature is found at stellar depths closer to the surface but not too close to the surface where the gas density is too low to drive the pulsation.

The two aforesaid requirements that drive the pulsation in a star can only be met at a specific range of effective temperature (T_{eff}), whose locus on the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram (HRD) is defined as the *Instability Strip* or, more accurately, *Classical Instability Strip* (Figure 1.5).

FIGURE 1.5: Classical Instability Strip and variable stars on the HRD (Image credits "An Introduction to Distance Measurement in Astronomy" (Grijs, 2013))

1.2.3 Cepheids as tracers in the Milky Way

Cepheids' main use is not only limited to distance estimates. They are also good tracers of chemical abundances in their hosting galaxies, and it has been proved how useful they are for studying the metallicity gradient of the Galactic disk. Among many papers published over decades (e.g., Andrievsky et al., 2002a; Andrievsky et al., 2002b; Andrievsky et al., 2002c; Luck, 2018), a series of papers to study chemical abundances of Cepheids in the Galactic disk came out from the DIONYSOS (The Disk Optical Near-infrared Young Stellar Object Spectroscopy) project, of which Genovali et al. (2014) revealed that over a broad range of Galactocentric distances ($R_G \sim 5\text{--}19\text{ kpc}$) the metallicity gradient remained linear, and the residual around the gradient is correlated to spatial overdensities of Cepheids across the thin disk. Such a study on the metallicity gradient can be compared with other tracers, such as OB stars and open clusters, although Cepheids show the tightest trend. The work of Genovali et al. (2014) was later followed by Genovali et al. (2015) who used α -elements to find that the abundance ratios, $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$, are constant across the disk.

FIGURE 1.6: Metallicity Gradient for MW Cepheids obtained by Luck (2018), P-L distances are derived in Madore, Freedman, and Moak (2017).

This constancy suggests that the nucleosynthesis process that contributed to chemical enrichment in different parts of the disk is common. Another piece available for understanding the chemical evolution of the disk was later added by da Silva et al. (2016) whose work focused on neutron capture elements (Y, La, Ce, Nd, Eu) in 73 classical Cepheids revealing well-defined radial gradients in these elements.

Given the need of having more Cepheids in different regions across the Galactic disk far beyond the solar neighborhood, Matsunaga et al. (2011) started the seek of new Cepheids in the near-infrared using data from the Infrared Survey Facility (IRSF) resulting in 4 new Cepheids found in the bulge, 13 beyond the Galactic center (Matsunaga et al., 2016). Subsequently, Tanioka et al. (2017) added three new Cepheids on the northern side and Inno et al. (2019) reported 5 new Cepheids on the southern side of the inner disk. In parallel, in the Southern hemisphere, ESO's Vista Survey of the Vía Láctea (VVV) found 24 Cepheids located beyond the Galactic center (Dékány et al., 2015a; Dékány et al., 2015b).

Recent large-scale surveys have further expanded the sample of Galactic Cepheids. A breakthrough came out with the studies by Chen et al. (2019) and Skowron et al. (2019) providing a three-dimensional map, based on the positions and distances of 2431 classical Cepheid stars that were discovered by the OGLE project, allowing to constrain the warped shape of the disk. In the "veiled" regions, given the extremely high extinction, a census of classical and type II Cepheids was done using ESO VVV by Dékány et al. (2019), revealing up to 640 classical Cepheids and more than 500 type II Cepheids that allowed to reveal a steep extinction curve toward the bulge. Classical Cepheids were used to trace vertical and radial age gradients of the thin disk population.

FIGURE 1.7: Distribution of Classical Cepheids in the Milky Way and the Magellanic Clouds. (Skowron et al., 2019)

As we have seen, the advantages offered by Cepheids are clearly not limited to distance determinations, their use in Galactic archaeology is of major importance, hence the need of searching more targets of interest at different loci becomes obvious. It is important to note that the advent of new infrared observations will provide deeper insights into this field. In order to perform a chemical analysis on the newly available sample of Cepheids, follow-up observations of near-infrared spectroscopy are needed. This Ph.D. project responds to such need, aiming to set the directions for stellar parameter derivations and chemical analysis of (time-series) near-infrared spectroscopy of Cepheids in the solar neighborhood and the disk. In the next section, we will proceed to explain in detail the advantages and the current status of using infrared data.

1.3 Infrared Spectroscopy

It has been almost two centuries since the very first step into infrared wavelengths was made by William Herschel, followed by a century to just start using only thermocouple detectors, today having high-end technology allowing us to observe a wide variety of objects, from cool stars to obscured Cepheids. The focus of this work is on analyzing time-series, near-infrared spectra of classical Cepheids with our high-end spectrograph, **WINERED**, which will be detailed in Section 2.2. The

infrared bands that WINERED covers are the *Y* (0.96–1.11 μm) and *J* (1.14–1.35 μm) bands. These windows of the atmospheric transmission have some advantages over surrounding wavelengths ranges, the optical bands on the shorter and the *H*, *K* and further infrared bands on the longer wavelengths.

An advantage of the infrared observations, especially for classical Cepheids, is that the interstellar extinction is low compared to optical ranges. According to the classical extinction law by Cardelli, Clayton, and Mathis (1989) with $R_v = 3.3$. It is, therefore, easier to get near-infrared spectra than optical spectra for stars with large interstellar extinction. However, the methodology and basic information such as the list of absorption lines are not established for the infrared spectroscopy in contrast to the optical spectroscopy for which there is a long history. For example, Andreasen et al. (2016) presented there are huge errors in the oscillator strengths, $\log gf$, of iron lines in the infrared range.

The *H* (1.50–1.80 μm) and *K* (2.00–2.34 μm) bands are commonly used atmospheric windows not only for photometric observations such as the 2MASS all-sky survey but also for spectroscopic observations. For example, the APOGEE has made a gigantic step forward in advancing infrared spectroscopy with fiber-fed multi-object spectrographs observing hundreds of thousands of objects in a part of the *H* band (Majewski et al., 2017). Moving along the infrared regions of the spectrum, when we depart from the near-infrared to the mid-infrared (*L*, *M*, *N*, and *Q* bands), more easily observed are cooler objects such as protoplanetary disks, comets, asteroids, planets, warm interstellar dust, and so on. In the far-infrared regimes (*Z* band–submillimetric), even cooler objects get revealed, such as the emission from cold interstellar dust and cold molecular clouds (Figure 1.8).

FIGURE 1.8: Composite of three far-infrared wavelength images of our Galaxy, taken with COBE satellite (Image credit: Michael Hauser (STScI), COBE/DIRBE Science Team and NASA. Image Link: <https://sci.esa.int/web/home/-/29478-traces-of-the-disc-surrounding-our-solar-system-are-visible-in-this-image-taken-by-cobe>)

In spite of some pioneering works on infrared spectroscopy, partly mentioned so far, the YJ -band spectra with high resolution have not been used for studying Cepheids. Thus, our work is the first, for example, to make an extensive search for different chemical elements (species) in the YJ -band spectra of Cepheids. We explore our unique spectra looking for elements studied in Genovali et al. (2014), Genovali et al. (2015), da Silva et al. (2016), Kondo et al. (2019), Matsunaga et al. (2020), and Fukue et al. (2021), accounting for Fe I, Fe II, α - enhanced elements, neutron capture elements. In addition, following up the works of Caffau et al. (2005), Caffau et al. (2007), Caffau et al. (2011), and Caffau et al. (2016), we can identify and confirm significantly more P I and S I lines. For S I, for example, there has been a confusion about its true identification and hyper-fine structure of the S I singlet at $\lambda_{\text{air}} = 10635.97$ (Ryde et al., 2019). Chapter 7 elaborates on this topic in detail. We provide an atlas of lines for different species identified and confirmed in our targets in the YJ bands which can be found in full extension in the appendix.

1.4 Aims

This work aims to establish the procedure to determine stellar parameters (in particular, T_{eff} and $\log g$) and chemical abundances of several elements based on near-infrared YJ -band spectra of classical Cepheids. The use of infrared spectra to measure the abundances of Cepheids has been just started to be explored by Inno et al. (2019) and Minniti et al. (2020). The spectra they used are, however, limited in the spectral resolution, $R = \lambda/\Delta\lambda \sim 3000$ in the former paper and ~ 8000 in the latter. In contrast, we use the spectra obtained with WINERED, giving $R \sim 28000$, which allows us to measure individual lines with high precision. We determine stellar parameters and chemical abundances of various elements by combining measurements of individual lines rather than by matching observed spectra with synthetic ones as done by the above studies.

FIGURE 1.9: Classical Cepheids in the MW. Blue circles representing Cepheids

Photometric data may give precise estimates of stellar parameters in some cases, especially for stars in the solar neighborhood. However, classical Cepheids are located in the Galactic plane and the interstellar extinction gets large, $A_V > 1$, at relatively short distances, $\gtrsim 1$ kpc. This prevents the estimates with photometric data

for which the degeneracy between the reddening and color-based temperature becomes the problem. The Cepheids at larger distances, $\gtrsim 4$ kpc, are affected by large extinction, and the advantage of infrared spectroscopy gets prominent. Therefore, the method of determining T_{eff} with infrared spectra is crucial for studying new classical Cepheids being discovered by large surveys (Chen et al., 2019; Skowron et al., 2019; Dékány et al., 2019).

In order to develop the spectroscopic path for estimating T_{eff} and $\log g$, we will analyze a sample of 22 Galactic Cepheids which has been divided into three categories: **Calibrators**, **Validators**, and **Disk Targets**. The **Calibrator** sample consists of Cepheids that have been widely studied (mainly in optical) and for which a good set of time-series spectra with WINERED are available. We use their spectra to find and calibrate the relations needed for deriving fundamental stellar parameters (T_{eff} and $\log g$). Subsequently, the **Validator** sample consists of Cepheids with a limited number of observations or limited information available in literatures that are to be used to test and validate the relations obtained with the Calibrators sample. Once the relations aimed to obtain T_{eff} and $\log g$ were calibrated and tested appropriately, they can be applied in the analysis of **Disk Target** Cepheids, detected by OGLE IV program, for which there is no literature available regarding their stellar parameters nor prior spectroscopic data.

After derivation of T_{eff} and $\log g$, we move forward to measure chemical abundances. First, we need to identify absorption lines present in the YJ -band spectra of Cepheids. There are published lists of absorption lines, e.g., Vienna Atomic Line Database (VALD, Ryabchikova et al., 2015), including those in the YJ bands. Moreover, there are a few papers in which absorption lines observed in WINERED YJ -band spectra were investigated (e.g., Kondo et al., 2019; Fukue et al., 2021). Nevertheless, it is necessary to establish a list of lines that are present and useful in the abundance analysis for Cepheids. Not only identify absorption lines, but we also calibrate the oscillator strengths of the lines using the spectra of Calibrator Cepheids. This is important because the list of infrared lines is not well established as mentioned above. In addition to the most fundamental elements, Fe, we perform the

measurements of Si, P, S, Ca, Zn, and Y. There are other species that show absorption lines in *YJ*-band spectra of Cepheids. The spectral atlas in Appendix A shows both the lines we use in the final analysis and some prominent lines which are not used.

Once the oscillator strengths are calibrated, we can use them to measure the abundances of Cepheids. Using the spectra of Validators and Disk Targets, we validate our calibration and try the application of our line list and procedures. The main purpose of the thesis is to demonstrate that one can measure the abundances of Cepheids with *YJ*-band spectra with reasonable precision, let's say ~ 0.1 dex when a sufficient number of lines are measured in a sufficiently high-quality spectrum. An important limitation of our analysis is that, like in most of the previous studies on Cepheids and other pulsating stars, we use standard models for a static atmosphere, which is different from the atmosphere of pulsating stars. This means, that we have to take the quasi-static approximation, with which it is assumed that the structure of the pulsating atmosphere at a given time can be approximated by the hydrostatic atmosphere model. Most previous studies measuring the abundance of Cepheids made this approximation, and this approach has been supported by Vasilyev et al. (2018), who found that hydrostatic 1D atmosphere models give the abundances consistent with those obtained with hydrodynamic 2D time-dependent models. Moreover, it is useful to explore the new *YJ*-band windows with the classical approach same as previous studies based on optical spectroscopy, thereby allowing us to give measurements directly comparable with the previous results. For the purpose of our analysis, we will assume a 1D atmosphere model and an LTE regime, even though we are aware that some lines are not sensitive to LTE departures (to Non-LTE regime), such as Fe II (Kovtyukh and Andrievsky, 1999).

1.5 The Structure of this Thesis

This thesis is organized as follows: In Chapter 1 a description of the context involving this research is given. In Chapter 2 the observed data with WINERED and the processes performed during the reduction are exposed. Chapter 3 provides a detailed view of the preparation and analysis of the observed sample. Derivation of the effective temperature and surface gravity is discussed in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, we describe some basic theories of the abundance analysis and the methods we use in this work. Then, Chapter 6 shows the steps taken to derive the microturbulence and iron abundances of our targets, and Chapter 7 presents the analysis for species other than Fe I. Finally, a discussion on our results and future approaches are discussed in Chapter 8.

Following the standard of astronomical spectroscopy, we use the roman character to indicate the ionization state of each species: I for neutral species and II for singly ionized species. Doubly or more ionized species do not appear in this thesis. For example, Fe I and Fe II indicate neutral and singly-ionized iron, respectively. Also, to indicate the iron abundance, we use the following notation:

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \log \left(\frac{N_{\text{Fe}}}{N_{\text{H}}} \right)_{\text{star}} - \log \left(\frac{N_{\text{Fe}}}{N_{\text{H}}} \right)_{\odot} \quad (1.1)$$

which is the logarithm³ of the iron abundance with respect to the solar abundance (Table 1.1). This quantity is commonly referred to as “metallicity” and it is measured in a dimensionless quantity called “dex” (contraction of decimal exponent; Allen 1951). Where it is more appropriate, we clarify the ionization stage of the species clear like $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ and $[\text{Fe II}/\text{H}]$. We also consider $[\text{X}/\text{H}]$ where X is other species such as Si and Ca. Furthermore, the ratio of various species X to iron) given by

$$[\text{X}/\text{Fe}] = [\text{X}/\text{H}] - [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \quad (1.2)$$

is useful to discuss contributions from different sources of chemical enrichment. Indeed, different stellar populations tend to show different chemical patterns on the

³The log notation indicates the logarithm to base 10 throughout the thesis.

[X/Fe]–[Fe/H] diagrams; e.g., thin and thick disks show different [Mg/Fe] at a given [Fe/H] (Matteucci, 2021).

Another commonly-used indicator of abundance is $\log \epsilon$, used also in Table 1.1, which gives the abundance on the logarithmic scale, with respect to Hydrogen with $\log \epsilon_{\text{H}} = 12$,

$$\log \epsilon_{\text{X}} = \log \left(\frac{N_{\text{X}}}{N_{\text{H}}} \right) + 12. \quad (1.3)$$

TABLE 1.1: The solar abundance adopted from Asplund et al. (2009)

Z	Element	$\log \epsilon$
14	Si	7.51
15	P	5.41
16	S	7.12
20	Ca	6.34
26	Fe	7.50
30	Zn	4.56
39	Y	2.21
66	Dy	1.10

Chapter 2

Targets and Observations

2.1 Targets

As mentioned in Chapter 1, our sample of target Cepheids is divided into three groups: (1) Calibrators, (2) Validators, and (3) Disk Targets. The observed targets are summarized in Table 2.1. In total, we observed 22 Cepheids (together with telluric standards). Thirteen of the target Cepheids (Calibrators and Validators) are located in the solar neighborhood, while the other nine Cepheids are located in the galactic disk. As we describe in Section 2.2, the former sample was observed with WINERED in 2013–2016 during its operation at the Araki telescope in the Koyama observatory of the Kyoto Sangyo University (Japan), while the latter group was observed in February 2017, with WINERED at the New Technology Telescope (NTT) in the La Silla observatory, ESO (Chile).

The Calibrators and Validators are well-known Cepheids with various observations reported in the literature. We make use of their stellar parameters as a function of phase and their abundances obtained mainly by Luck, Andrievsky, and collaborators (Table 2.2). They used optical high-quality spectra with high spectral resolution at dozens of phases. We can establish the relations between LDRs and T_{eff} based on the temperatures they obtained (Chapter 4) and calibrate the oscillator strengths of absorption lines present in the WINERED spectra assuming the abundances reported (Chapters 6 and 7).

The Disk Targets were first discovered by the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment (OGLE) (Skowron et al., 2019). Their J -band magnitudes range from 10.5 to 13 mag (except OCEP 0788, $J \sim 9$ mag), which are much fainter than the Calibrators (2–5 mag in J) and Validators (4–8 mag in J , except Polaris with $J \sim 0.8$ mag). They are located at larger distances in the southern Galactic plane, and good testbeds for the WINERED ability to observe and measure chemical abundances of classical Cepheids at large distances.

FIGURE 2.1: Distribution of the Cepheids studied in this thesis. Light blue star for Calibrators, Green star for Validators, and Pink star for Disk Cepheids. Light gray points represent the sample analyzed by Luck (2018).

TABLE 2.1: Observed Cepheids and categories.

Target	RA, Dec (J2000.0)		P (days)	T_{old}	T_{new}	N_{obs}
Calibrators						
δ Cep	22 : 29 : 10.27	+58 : 24 : 54.7	5.3663	2450102.860	2450102.860	7
η Aql	19 : 52 : 28.37	+01 : 00 : 20.4	7.1766	2450100.861	2450101.076	7
FF Aql	18 : 58 : 14.75	+17 : 21 : 39.3	4.4709	2450102.387	2450102.879	5
RT Aur	06 : 28 : 34.09	+30 : 29 : 34.9	3.7281	2442361.155	2442361.789	9
SU Cas	02 : 51 : 58.75	+68 : 53 : 18.6	1.9493	2450100.156	2450100.156	5
SZ Tau	04 : 37 : 14.78	+18 : 32 : 34.9	3.1487	2450101.605	2450101.605	5
X Cyg	20 : 43 : 24.19	+35 : 35 : 16.1	16.3863	2450106.014	2450106.178	9
ζ Gem	07 : 04 : 06.5	+20 : 34 : 13.1	10.1507	2450108.930	2450108.016	10
Validators						
Polaris	02 : 31 : 49.09	+89 : 15 : 50.8	3.9619	2457685.737	2457685.856	10
DL Cas	00 : 29 : 58.59	+60 : 12 : 43.1	8.0006	2437043.910	2437043.750	3
S Sge	19 : 56 : 01.26	+16 : 38 : 05.2	8.3821	2450675.768	2450675.433	3
T Vul	20 : 51 : 28.24	+28 : 15 : 01.8	4.4355	2450101.410	2450101.454	2
V367 Sct	18 : 33 : 35.24	-10 : 25 : 38.1	6.2931	2437430.660	2437429.968	1
Disk targets						
OCEP 0930	13 : 34 : 29.54	-62 : 33 : 21.7	23.6075	—	2457000.697	1
OCEP 0917	13 : 27 : 16.60	-62 : 47 : 40.6	6.6767	—	2457002.252	1
OCEP 0848	12 : 55 : 47.17	-64 : 41 : 29.9	4.2290	—	2457002.451	1
OCEP 0788	12 : 27 : 57.35	-61 : 37 : 37.4	28.2666	—	2457014.244	1
OCEP 0689	11 : 39 : 54.13	-61 : 52 : 52.3	10.2650	—	2457000.731	1
OCEP 0460	10 : 13 : 39.01	-59 : 15 : 20.5	13.6754	—	2457011.661	1
OCEP 0336	09 : 13 : 07.92	-50 : 14 : 56.4	3.2122	—	2457000.132	1
OCEP 0267	08 : 42 : 01.28	-44 : 05 : 30.9	3.7879	—	2457003.440	1
OCEP 0272	08 : 44 : 34.62	-46 : 05 : 04.3	1.9676	—	2457000.271	1

TABLE 2.2: The previous data set used in this thesis

Target	Photometry		Stellar Parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, ξ)	Abundances
	old	recent		
Calibrators				
δ Cep	K98	AAVSO	A05	L18
η Aql	K98	AAVSO	L04	L18
FF Aql	K98	AAVSO	L08	L18
RT Aur	K98	AAVSO	A05	L18
SU Cas	K98	AAVSO	L08	L18
SZ Tau	K98	AAVSO	L08	L18
X Cyg	K98	AAVSO	K05	L18
ζ Gem	K98	AAVSO	L08	L18
Validators				
Polaris	F93	AAVSO	U17	U05
DL Cas	B95	AAVSO	U15	L18
S sge	K98	AAVSO	L04	L18
T Vul	K98	AAVSO	A05	L18
V367 Sct	—	AAVSO	—	L18

References — (A05) Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh, 2005, (B95) Berdnikov and Vozyakova, 1995, (F93) Fernie, Kamper, and Seager, 1993, (K98) Kiss, 1998, (K05) Kovtyukh et al., 2005, (L04) Luck and Andrievsky, 2004, (L08) Luck et al., 2008, (L18) Luck, 2018, (U05) Usenko et al., 2005, (U15) Usenko, 2015, (U17) Usenko et al., 2017.

AAVSO — We collected recent photometric data of every target from the database made publicly available by the American Association of Variable Star Observers (AAVSO).

2.2 Observations

2.2.1 WINERED

Warm INfrared Echelle spectrograph to Realize Extreme Dispersion and sensitivity (**WINERED**) is a near-infrared spectrograph that covers the 0.91–1.35 μm range achieving high resolution with its three observational modes:

- WIDE mode: 0.91–1.35 [μm], $R \simeq 28000$
- HIRES-Y mode: 0.96–1.11 [μm], $R \simeq 70000$
- HIRES-J mode: 1.13–1.35 [μm], $R \simeq 70000$

During its beginnings, WINERED was operated with the Araki telescope at the Koyama observatory in the Kyoto Sangyo University, then early in 2017 the operation of WINERED started with the New Technology Telescope (NTT) at the La Silla observatory, Chile. It will be soon operated with the Magellan Telescope at Las Campanas Observatory, Chile. A detailed summary of the observations performed in Japan and in Chile can be found in Table 2.3.

Amongst its important features, the high quantum efficiency and high throughputs of WINERED stand out, with more than 50 % for WIDE and over 40 % for the HIRES modes, which allows us to collect high signal-to-noise ratio spectra comparable to optical spectra used in previous studies on Cepheids. For this work, we will be using spectra obtained with the WIDE mode, covering the echelle orders 42nd to 61st. The instrument contains three slits of 2, 2.8, and 4 pixels in width (and 60.5 pixels in length), of which we used the narrowest one corresponding to $R \simeq 28000$.

FIGURE 2.2: WINERED spectrograph at the Nasmyth platform of NTT (Image credit: Scarlet S. Elgueta)

FIGURE 2.3: WINERED spectrograph at the Nasmyth platform of NTT (Image credit: Scarlet S. Elgueta)

2.2.2 Observations of Calibrator and Validator Cepheids with the Araki Telescope

The first cycle of the observations with WINERED aimed to study Cepheids was performed in Kyoto, Japan, at The Araki Telescope, an optical and near-infrared telescope with an aperture of 1.3 m at The Koyama Telescope. Multi-epoch observations were done for the Calibrator Cepheids and Validator Cepheids, enabling us to test how time variations of Cepheids affect our measurement of stellar parameters and abundances. Each calibrator was observed at least five times at different phases allowing us to have a decent phase coverage so that we could appreciate phase-to-phase parameter variations. On the other hand, for the validator sample of Cepheids it was not possible to collect enough phases (some of them having only one phase) or, distinctly for the case of Polaris we have collected ten phases but its literature stellar parameters exhibit a lack of information for the surface gravity, thus, the whole sample is used to validate our further results.

2.2.3 Observations of Disk Target Cepheids with the NTT

The second cycle of the WINERED observations in the framework of the OSIRIS project was conducted at ESO New Technology Telescope (NTT) in La Silla observatory, with a 3.58-m diameter. The targets were first detected by the OGLE project and published in the work of Skowron et al. (2019).

Single-epoch observations of Disk Targets were conducted at NTT in 2017. The performance of WINERED at NTT is described in Ikeda et al., 2018. Having only one phase for every target only allowed us to apply the relations that were calibrated and validated in the other two samples. The results on this sample can be found in Chapter 4.

FIGURE 2.4: NTT in the La Silla observatory, February 2017, Chile
(Image credit: Scarlet S. Elgueta)

TABLE 2.3: Observation Log

Target	Date and Time (UT)	JD	Phase	Exposures	Nodding	Accepted
δ Cep	2013-12-02 11:12	2456628.967	0.119	$188^s \times 3$	ABB	OK
	2013-12-05 10:24	2456631.934	0.672	$188^s \times 2$	AB	OK
	2013-12-25 10:07	2456651.922	0.396	$138^s \times 4$	OSO	NO
	2015-08-06 13:09	2457241.048	0.178	$20^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2015-08-08 13:49	2457243.076	0.556	$20^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2015-08-15 18:34	2457250.274	0.897	$30^s \times 2$	AB	OK
	2015-10-23 12:51	2457319.036	0.711	$30^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
η Aql	2014-09-16 13:00	2456917.042	0.743	$188^s \times 2$	AB	OK
	2014-09-17 10:23	2456917.933	0.867	$18^s \times 4$	ABBA	NO
	2015-08-06 12:33	2457241.023	0.887	$30^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2015-08-08 13:59	2457243.083	0.174	$30^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2016-03-21 19:58	2457469.332	0.700	$100^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-26 19:46	2457474.324	0.395	$30^s \times 6$	OSO	OK
	2016-05-14 18:36	2457523.275	0.216	$50^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
FF Aql	2015-08-06 14:48	2457241.117	0.594	$120^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
	2015-08-07 15:23	2457242.141	0.823	$60^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-17 19:13	2457465.301	0.737	$150^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-21 18:41	2457469.279	0.627	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-04-19 17:49	2457498.243	0.105	$300^s \times 2$	AB	OK
RT Aur	2014-01-23 16:20	2456681.181	0.920	$228^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2015-10-28 18:53	2457324.287	0.422	$150^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2016-02-16 14:41	2457435.112	0.149	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-02-28 12:20	2457447.014	0.341	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-07 12:47	2457455.033	0.492	$150^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-15 11:12	2457462.967	0.620	$300^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-17 11:03	2457464.961	0.155	$200^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2016-03-21 13:13	2457469.051	0.252	$200^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-23 12:05	2457471.004	0.776	$300^s \times 2$	AB	OK
SU Cas	2013-12-25 10:07	2456651.922	0.054	$588^s \times 4$	ABBA	NO
	2015-08-15 18:50	2457250.285	0.014	$120^s \times 2$	AB	OK
	2016-03-12 09:36	2457459.900	0.546	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-15 10:40	2457462.945	0.108	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-17 11:24	2457464.975	0.150	$300^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK

TABLE 2.3: Observation Log (continued)

Target	Date and Time (UT)	JD	Phase	Exposures	Nodding	Accepted
SZ Tau	2014-01-24 13:00	2456682.042	0.870	288 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2016-02-18 12:12	2457437.009	0.639	300 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2016-03-17 09:57	2457464.915	0.502	300 ^s × 2	AB	OK
	2016-03-21 09:59	2457468.916	0.772	300 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
	2016-03-25 11:00	2457472.959	0.056	300 ^s × 4	ABBA	NO
X Cyg	2014-08-30 13:16	2456900.053	0.606	188 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2014-09-15 13:03	2456916.044	0.582	108 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2014-09-18 11:12	2456918.967	0.760	108 ^s × 2	AB	OK
	2014-10-15 11:13	2456945.968	0.408	138 ^s × 2	AB	OK
	2015-07-25 13:35	2457229.066	0.685	300 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2015-10-26 10:49	2457321.951	0.353	300 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
	2016-03-17 19:58	2457465.332	0.103	200 ^s × 4	OSO	OK
	2016-05-04 19:06	2457513.296	0.030	300 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
2016-05-18 17:16	2457527.220	0.880	300 ^s × 5	OSO	OK	
ζ Gem	2013-02-22 11:38	2456345.985	0.534	188 ^s × 7	OSO	OK
	2013-02-23 14:35	2456347.108	0.645	108 ^s × 8	OSO	OK
	2013-02-27 12:01	2456351.001	0.028	108 ^s × 9	OSO	OK
	2013-03-03 14:38	2456355.110	0.433	88 ^s × 9	OSO	NO
	2013-11-29 15:08	2456626.131	0.133	108 ^s × 4	ABBA	OK
	2016-02-17 13:35	2457436.066	0.923	100 ^s × 4	OSO	OK
	2016-03-07 12:37	2457455.026	0.791	60 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
	2016-03-23 11:13	2457470.968	0.362	180 ^s × 4	OSO	NO
	2016-05-01 10:16	2457509.928	0.200	30 ^s × 4	OSO	OK
	2017-12-05 08:12	2458092.842	0.626	30 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
Polaris	2016-03-15 14:39	2457463.111	0.779	30 ^s × 2	OSO	NO
	2016-03-16 19:03	2457464.294	0.077	10 ^s × 4	OSO	OK
	2016-03-17 11:47	2457464.991	0.253	10 ^s × 8	OSO	OK
	2016-03-21 18:24	2457469.267	0.332	20 ^s × 4	OSO	OK
	2016-03-26 16:16	2457474.178	0.572	15 ^s × 8	OSO	OK
	2016-04-19 14:05	2457498.087	0.607	10 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
	2016-04-20 10:19	2457498.930	0.819	5 ^s × 2	OSO	OK
	2016-04-24 16:35	2457503.191	0.895	30 ^s × 3	OSO	OK
	2016-05-04 12:00	2457513.000	0.371	10 ^s × 2	OSO	NO

TABLE 2.3: Observation Log (continued)

Target	Date and Time (UT)	JD	Phase	Exposures	Nodding	Accepted
	2016-05-12 14:15	2457521.094	0.414	$10^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
DL Cas	2015-07-31 17:36	2457235.234	0.743	$300^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2015-08-07 14:49	2457242.118	0.604	$600^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2015-10-23 13:07	2457319.047	0.219	$300^s \times 4$	OSO	OK
S Sge	2015-10-26 10:29	2457321.937	0.940	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-21 19:01	2457469.293	0.520	$300^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
	2016-03-26 19:36	2457474.317	0.119	$300^s \times 2$	AB	OK
T Vul	2015-08-08 15:47	2457243.158	0.138	$200^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
	2016-05-14 18:48	2457523.284	0.293	$150^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
V367 Sct	2016-04-19 18:23	2457498.266	0.952	$600^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0930	2017-02-08 06:08	2457792.756	0.551	$300^s \times 2$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0917	2017-02-10 08:03	2457794.836	0.709	$450^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0848	2017-02-10 06:31	2457794.772	0.355	$600^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0788	2017-02-08 04:10	2457792.674	0.539	$150^s \times 2$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0689	2017-02-09 05:21	2457793.723	0.252	$600^s \times 2$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0460	2017-02-11 05:36	2457795.734	0.335	$450^s \times 2$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0336	2017-02-09 06:01	2457793.751	0.064	$1200^s \times 2$	ABBA	OK
OCEP 0267	2017-02-13 04:59	2457797.708	0.687	$600^s \times 2$	OSO	OK
OCEP 0272	2017-02-13 06:57	2457797.790	0.331	$1800^s \times 4$	ABBA	OK

2.3 Stellar Parameters from Literatures

2.3.1 Light curves

For every target Cepheids, there are various data available (Table 2.2) including time-series photometry, at least, that was used for classification and period determination. In contrast to Disk Targets for which only photometric data are available, we have time-series measurements of stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, ζ) for Calibrators and Validators.

Stellar parameters of Cepheids vary with the pulsation phase, and it is important to know the phase at which each spectrum was taken. Here, we determine the phases of the spectroscopic observations. The pulsation phase (ϕ) is given by :

$$\phi = \text{decimal portion of } \left[\frac{t_{\text{obs}} - T_0}{P} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

where t_{obs} , P , and T_0 indicate the time of observation, the period, and the time of phase zero, respectively. Following the standard definition, the phase is zero at maximum brightness (T_0).

If very accurate P and T_0 are available, we can estimate the phase at any given time of observation (t_{obs}). The periods of the Calibrator Cepheids and the Validator Cepheids are well established, but they are not accurate enough to give good phases for t_{obs} over 30 years. This is because of a tiny error in P accumulates and propagates over a large number of pulsation cycles. In the following analysis, we use the stellar parameters given by Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh (2005), Kovtyukh (2007) and Luck et al. (2008), who used spectra taken ~ 25 years ago. The phases given in the aforementioned papers are accurate because T_0 used for calculating their phases were determined based on photometric data which were collected sufficiently close to the epochs of spectroscopic observations. However, using the same set of P and T_0 does not give accurate phases at WINERED observations because of the accumulated errors.

In order to derive accurate pulsation phases at WINERED observations, we mainly used light curves publicly available at the American Association of Variable Star Observers (AAVSO) for visual and V -band light curves, but for some of the targets, the ASAS dataset was also available (such as for η Aql and V367 Sct). Moreover, to make these phases consistent with the phases given by Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh (2005), Kovtyukh (2007) and Luck et al. (2008), we determine T_0 with recent photometric data that show the phased light curves to be consistent in phase with the light curves for the data taken ~ 30 years ago. As such an old data set, we mainly use the V -band light curves available at the [McMaster Cepheid Photometry and Radial Velocity Data Archives](#). Table 2.2 indicates the data sets, both the old and recent photometric data, that we used for individual objects. Figure 2.5 presents an example of how WINERED observations were phased in case of X Cyg. The phases of WINERED observations are indicated by red markers.

FIGURE 2.5: Light Curve of X Cygni in the V band and visual light. The phases of WINERED observations are indicated by red markers.

2.3.2 Phase-by-phase Stellar Parameters from Literatures

Most of the Cepheids included in the Calibrators category have sufficient information in the literatures, i.e., well-sampled light curves and radial velocity curves, though the majority of them consisted of observations performed in the optical. In contrast, for the Cepheids in the Validators category, the amount and quality of the information in literatures was rather scarce and, in some cases, imprecise. For Disk Target Cepheids, we could determine the phase at the spectroscopic observations precisely with a large number of photometric points from the OGLE project, but there are no data useful for knowing the stellar parameters such as T_{eff} *a priori*.

The WINERED phases for the Calibrators were subsequently used to obtain literature values of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and ζ , together with their corresponding errors. We fitted the time-series values of the stellar parameters from the literatures by the discrete Fourier series and estimated the values at the WINERED phases. An example of how the interpolated curves are is shown in Figure 2.6. These stellar parameters for the Calibrators will be used as a reference in calibrating the LDR relations of T_{eff} and $\log g$ (Chapter 4). In the abundance analysis (Chapters 6 and 7), we rely on the stellar parameters of the Calibrators for calibrating the oscillator strengths ($\log gf$) of absorption lines.

FIGURE 2.6: Interpolated values of T_{eff} and $\log g$ for WINERED phases for X Cyg.

2.4 Chemical Abundances from Literatures

As presented in Table 2.2, we adopt chemical abundances from Luck (2018) except for Polaris, for which we use the work of Usenko et al. (2005). Detailed chemical abundances of Polaris have been scarcely reported. Figure 2.7 shows the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ – $[\text{X}/\text{Fe}]$ diagrams for all the targets cataloged in Luck (2018), of which the Calibrators and Validators are highlighted. Compared to $[\text{Si I}/\text{Fe}]$ and $[\text{Ca I}/\text{Fe}]$, $[\text{X}/\text{Fe}]$ of other species show larger scatters which are caused by larger errors. Polaris is indicated by a red circle, showing clear offsets from the measurements of Luck (2018).

As far as we know, no measurements of Phosphorus abundances in Cepheids have been reported before. Therefore, we have no reference to calibrate the $\log gf$ of P I lines. In this thesis, we assume $[\text{P}/\text{Fe}] = 0$ for all the calibrators.

FIGURE 2.7: The $[Fe/H]$ - $[X/Fe]$ diagrams for Si I, S I, Ca I, Ca II, Zn I, and Y II based on the abundances compiled by Luck (2018) except for Polaris whose abundances are adopted from Usenko et al. (2005).

Chapter 3

Data Reduction

3.1 Data Reduction

In this chapter, we describe the procedure employed for the analysis of the WINERED spectra (echelle type). During the observations, in order to subtract the background radiation from the sky and the telescope, we make the nodding of the telescope which is a standard procedure of infrared observations. We use two types of nodding patterns, "ABBA" (from one extreme to another) and "OSO" (object-sky-object). The OSO mode is used for extended objects or those in crowded areas and also for bright objects to avoid latent signal that could contaminate fainter objects to be observed with the ABBA nodding later. Calibration data was obtained right after finishing the observations. Starting with the flat fielding images by observing the dome flat, then, a ThAr lamp spectrum will be used in the further wavelength calibration.

As it was mentioned before WINERED spectra in WIDE mode is divided into 20 echelle orders of which 10 orders were suitable for performing our analysis, i.e., not heavily affected by Telluric contamination, constraining our working region to 9760–10890 Å (orders 57–52) and from 11800–13190 Å (orders 47–43).

RAW data was processed carefully to obtain the useful information contained in the final spectra. To achieve this purpose the pipeline software *WINERED Automatic Reduction Pipeline* (WARP; S. Hamano, 2021, private communication) was developed and written in Python using the PyRAF and astropy packages for astronomical data and numpy, scipy and matplotlib for calculations and plotting.

WARP has two modes, calibration, and science. Calibration mode deals with calibration raw data (flats and comparison images of ThAr lamps) and produces calibration images and parameters needed for the reduction process of raw science data that will be treated by WARP science mode. The input for the science mode is the raw science data, which in the following steps will be cross correlated so we can perform a wavelength calibration both for data in vacuum and in air wavelengths, having as a result, a normalized 1D spectra for λ_{air} (air wavelengths) and λ_{vac} (vacuum wavelengths). In this work, we will be using the normalized 1D spectra.

3.1.1 Sky subtraction

In order to remove the background emission, dark, bias and, stray light which produce a systematic noise in the object frame spectrum the background frame is subtracted. The easiest way of performing sky subtraction is by having separate sky and object frames taken almost consecutively, such as “OSO” dithering.

3.1.2 Wavelength calibration

Before proceeding with the analysis and telluric correction a simple check on the state of the applied wavelength calibration is a good idea for reassurance that the following steps will not exhibit systematic errors in the wavelength dimension which can induce errors in the forthcoming measurements and therefore increase the error budget on the final estimate of stellar parameters.

For this purpose, the observed spectra of every single target will be compared with synthetic telluric spectra created using MOLECFIT (Smette et al., 2015, Kausch et al., 2015): an astronomical software tool developed for ESO instruments to correct atmospheric absorption features that are present in astronomical Optical and Infrared observations, it also offers a way to determine the atmospheric water vapor content. For more details, see [ESO MOLECFIT](#).

The spectra collected for ζ (zeta) Geminorum without telluric correction applied will be compared with a set of synthetic spectra created using MOLECFIT, as an example. It is expected to observe no shifts between telluric features of both synthetic and observed spectra, this will reassure that the wavelength correction performed by the pipeline version 3.5 was correct as it is shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2.

If the above situation does not occur and shifts between telluric features of both the synthetic and observed spectra are indeed observed further wavelength corrections are needed which can be performed by estimating the linear shift in the wavelength axis and then applied to the observed spectra.

FIGURE 3.1: Synthetic telluric spectra compared with the observed spectra for the orders 43, 44, 45, 46

FIGURE 3.2: Synthetic telluric spectra compared with the observed spectra for the orders 47, 52, 56, 57

3.2 Signal-to-Noise Ratio

WARP also provides estimates of the signal-to-noise ratios for each spectrum, producing three different values for the spectrum corresponding to three different regions of each order for multiple exposures. The S/N values serve to evaluate the errors of line depths defined in Equation 4.4 in Chapter 4. In the case of the Calibrators and Validators, for the sake of obtaining reliable results, we have set the minimum S/N value for each target to 50 (confirm value), and some spectra having an average S/N below 50 were excluded from the analysis. In contrast, we included all the spectra of Disk Targets regardless of the S/N in order to examine the impact of low S/N. The distribution of the S/N values in individual orders are presented in Figures 3.3–3.5.

FIGURE 3.3: S/N values for the Calibrators sample.

FIGURE 3.4: S/N values for the Validator sample.

FIGURE 3.5: S/N values for the Disk Targets sample.

3.3 Telluric Correction

Infrared spectra carry a lot of contamination coming from the Earth's atmosphere, introducing what we know as telluric contamination, i.e., telluric lines in the spectra. These natural features are susceptible to a set of conditions such as the observatory location, the actual observation' weather, and airmass. For example, the telluric spectra observed in the summer with WINERED display obvious differences in the telluric line strength with those observed during winter, when the air is drier and the amount of water vapor is not as high as in summer.

These natural features must be removed from the observed spectra in order to resolve as many stellar features as possible. It has been proved that infrared spectra are much more affected by telluric contamination than the optical in which is almost negligible at certain passbands. Our observations need this step to be performed and in this work, this correction consisted in a combination of 2 steps: First, we used TelFit to create a synthetic model that adjusts best to the observed telluric spectra (Gullikson, Dodson-Robinson, and Kraus, 2014) and then identified stellar absorption features to be removed using the method described in Sameshima et al. (2018).

The common approach when dealing with this problem is to observe a telluric standard star on the same night of the observation and ideally close to the target star observation time. This means that when an observing run is being performed a non-negligible fraction of the time must be destined to the observation of telluric standard stars. Sameshima et al. (2018) work makes use of A0V stars as telluric standards because their spectra are almost featureless. However, in the case of high-resolution spectroscopic observations, such as those performed by WINERED, the weak intrinsic stellar lines that are seen in the A0V star cannot be ignored in the telluric correction. Therefore, Sameshima et al. (2018) identifies and removes the intrinsic stellar lines of AOV stars by using synthetic telluric spectra generated with MOLECFIT (Smette et al., 2015). The resulting spectra will only contain telluric features that will be used in the correction of the science targets (Cepheids). However, Sameshima et al. (2018) reported that at least for WINERED observations in Kyoto

where the humidity is relatively high, using the actual observed spectra with the intrinsic stellar lines removed in this way is significantly more accurate for telluric correction than directly using the theoretical telluric spectra produced by MOLECFIT.

As stated above, following the common approach requires the use of valuable time for the observation of telluric standard stars, especially when a high signal-to-noise ratio is required. TelFit provides a solution when time is scarce: generating a theoretical telluric absorption spectrum, under given observing conditions and a known line list. TelFit creates this theoretical (synthetic) spectrum by using the *Line-By-Line Radiative Transfer Model* (LBLRTM; Clough et al. 2005). In this work, we explored the two approaches: creating telluric synthetic spectra using both MOLECFIT and TelFit, the former completely supervised while the latter almost unsupervised reaching almost the same results. The final choice for this purpose was TelFit and for the next step, removal of intrinsic stellar lines, as it was prescribed in Sameshima et al. (2018). We attain to what was described in Sameshima et al. (2018) as it is better when dealing with spectra showing narrow and deeper lines, instead of trying a fast rotating star as we may face problems with stronger lines such as Hydrogen singlets.

Once the telluric spectrum is created it can be used for the telluric correction of the target star (Cepheid) using the IRAF task *telluric* where a couple of settings need to be considered such as the function to be fitted (spline, cubic spline, Chebyshev, Legendre) and the order of such function. We used a spline with an order usually above 11.

3.4 Continuum Normalization

Once the telluric correction is already performed on the targets, a normalization of the continuum level is often needed. This task is also run with IRAF with the *continuum* task which fits a one-dimensional function to the continuum of the spectra under analysis, such fitted function can be either a legendre polynomial, chebyshev polynomial, linear spline, cubic spline or an nth order spline. For our spectra, nth

order (usually higher than 15) spline seemed to work better than the other functions. A summary figure containing the tasks performed by IRAF on one of the Calibrators targets is shown below:

FIGURE 3.6: Before and after the telluric Correction and continuum normalization (FF Aql, order 44)

3.5 Correction of Wavelength Shift

Once the phases are defined and corroborated with the literature values (for Calibrators and Validators), it is possible to proceed with a step prior to the determination of stellar parameters. In order to apply the relations needed to obtain both T_{eff} and $\log g$, we need to make the correction of any wavelength shift to have each absorption line at the wavelength at rest. To “align” the spectra we computed the shifts between the observed spectra (in AIR wavelengths) and the synthetic one by cross-correlate them using the PyAstronomy package with its [crosscorrRV module](#). Those shifts were then applied to the observed spectra so all lines fall in the same wavelengths, as it can be seen in the following figure (3.7) for the Yttrium II line at 10329.7 \AA in δ Cep.

FIGURE 3.7: YII line aligned over the pulsation cycle of δ Cep

Chapter 4

Effective Temperature and Surface Gravity

4.1 Introduction

Our current knowledge of the intrinsic properties of classical Cepheid variables relies heavily on the atmospheric parameters derived for them. A key parameter, especially in the spectroscopic analysis, is the **Effective Temperature**, T_{eff} . Once this intrinsic parameter is defined, the subsequent (but not less important) parameters, i.e., **Surface Gravity** ($\log g$), **Microturbulent Velocity** (ξ), and **Metallicity** ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) may be estimated with spectra.

Stellar radiation from the photosphere is approximated by the blackbody radiation, and the effective temperature, T_{eff} , is defined by the *Stefan-Boltzmann Law*,

$$L = 4\pi R^2 \sigma T_{\text{eff}}^4 \quad (4.1)$$

where L is the luminosity of the star, R the stellar radius, and σ the Stefan–Boltzmann constant ($5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-4}$). On the other hand, the surface gravity ($\log g$) is given by Newton’s Law:

$$g = \frac{G \cdot M}{R^2}, \quad (4.2)$$

where G is the Newton constant and M is the stellar mass. Along with the radial pulsation of a classical Cepheids, while the mass remains almost constant over the long-term evolution of Cepheids crossing the instability strip ($\sim 10^6$ yr), the four

variables (L , R , T_{eff} , and $\log g$) change with the short time scale corresponding to the pulsation period following Equations (4.1) and (4.2). When a Cepheid shrinks (with decreasing R), T_{eff} and $\log g$ increase (see, e.g., Fig. 5 of Pejcha and Kochanek, 2012). Time-series measurements of T_{eff} and other stellar parameters are available for only exceptionally well-studied Cepheids like the Cepheids that we use as Calibrators. We need to establish a method of measuring the parameters with individual near-infrared spectra.

Throughout the pulsation cycle, the variation in temperature comes along with changes in radii resulting also in brightness changes. Such multi-parameter variation can lead to Effective Temperature estimates by substituting in Equation (4.1) for R^2 , allowing the understanding of how these two fundamental parameters (T_{eff} and $\log g$) change during the pulsation cycle of a Cepheid, i.e., when the Cepheid is contracting, its radius shrinks then according to equation 4.2 its surface gravity and effective temperature rise, similarly, when the Cepheid is expanding, as its radius increases, its surface gravity decreases and so does its Effective Temperature.

4.1.1 Approaches for estimating effective temperature

Obtaining highly precise temperatures is essential for the derivation of other stellar parameters as for further steps in the abundance analysis. Many methods have been employed to estimate the effective temperatures of astrophysical objects. The simplest, and often the most accurate method is using photometric colors, but it is subject to errors caused by interstellar extinction for reddened stars, e.g., in the Galactic disk.

Other approaches such as the *surface-brightness method*, involves the use of interferometric data (angular diameter) combined with photometry (fluxes), and the effectiveness of this method relies on the assumption that the extinction is negligible, which depicts a quite unrealistic scenario, especially for targets across the disk (Matsunaga, 2017) hence we need to use another method, that is precise and “reddening-free”.

The need of an empirical and “reddening-free” method becomes obvious. Such a method is found in the spectroscopic analysis itself, as having the spectrum of a

star with a decent signal-to-noise ratio is all what is needed for this procedure. We employ the **Line-Depth-Ratio** (LDR) method, in which we select pairs of absorption lines whose excitation potentials (χ) differ from each other and calculate the ratio of their depths $r = d_1/d_2$ (d : the depth of each line) because the lines of low and high excitation potential have different sensitivities to T_{eff} , and thus their ratio can provide good diagnostics on temperature reaching the utmost precision of 10 K (Gray and Johanson, 1991).

FIGURE 4.1: Illustration of the LDR method from Gray (2005).

There are still some limitations on the applicability of the LDR according to specific temperature ranges. Previous LDR works, performed mostly in optical spectra (Gray and Brown, 2001; Kovtyukh, 2000; Kovtyukh, 2007, and references therein), in addition to novel infrared works of Fukue et al. (2015), Taniguchi et al. (2018), and Jian, Matsunaga, and Fukue (2019) are limited to a certain temperature ranges which do not include warmer Cepheids (above 6000 K). Furthermore, LDRs used in the previous work tend to exhibit dependency not only on T_{eff} but also on $\log g$ and metallicity (Jian, Matsunaga, and Fukue, 2019; Jian et al., 2020) conditioning the derivation of T_{eff} and $\log g$ altogether. Matsunaga et al. (2021) proposed to pair lines of the same species but different ionization stages to overcome the previously described multi-parameter dependency of the LDR method. In this work, T_{eff} will be derived using LDR following the prescription stated in Matsunaga et al. (2021) applied on a wider temperature range, which will set the guidelines of this work.

4.1.2 Approaches for estimating surface gravity

Surface gravity ($\log g$) is also a key quantity for deriving stellar parameters, and analogously with T_{eff} there are multiple ways to estimate it. Its calculation is, however, not trivial. Some approaches rely on numerical models that are computationally expensive, and others depend on how stellar masses and radii can be estimated with photometry and/or interferometry.

There is a long-standing discrepancy between the $\log g$ values obtained with the spectroscopic and physical methods. Luck et al. (1998) investigated this discrepancy affecting the analysis of Cepheids' spectra and demonstrated potential approaches to tackle the problem. The observational evidence showed that for supergiants, the physical (or "theoretical") approach to obtain $\log g$ (from stellar masses and radii) was not consistent with the gravities with the spectroscopic method, i.e., demanding the Fe I/Fe II ionization balance in the Saha ionization equation, which tells us about the relative number of atoms in two ionization states as a function of electron density n_e and temperature T . The most used form of this equation:

$$\frac{n_{r+1}n_e}{n_r} = \frac{G_{r+1}g_e}{G_r} \frac{(2\pi m_e kT)^{(3/2)}}{h^3} \exp\left(-\frac{\chi_r}{kT}\right) \quad (4.3)$$

Where n_r and n_{r+1} are the number densities of atoms in the ionization state r and the ionization state $r + 1$ of a certain element (species). n_e corresponds to the electron number density, G_r , and G_{r+1} are the partition functions for the two states (r and $r + 1$), g_e the electron statistical weight, m_e the electron mass, k is the Boltzmann constant (a.k.a. k_b) and χ_r is the ionization potential (minimum energy needed to go from state r to state $r + 1$).

In this work, we opt for the spectroscopic approach to derive gravities, but not in the classical way mostly used in optical works, i.e., the Fe I - Fe II balance. We, instead, propose a complete empirical method to obtain the $\log g$ from the LDR method, altogether with the T_{eff} .

4.1.3 The LDR method

Matsunaga et al. (2021) proposed a method to estimate the surface gravity using neutral and ionized lines of Fe I, Fe II, Ca I, and Ca II in the *YJ* bands that are not affected by the uncertainties in the line list. By using the LDR technique, both T_{eff} and $\log g$ can be estimated based on empirical relations making use of spectra for 42 objects whose effective temperature ranged between 4800 and 6300 K (F–K spectral type) and surface gravity between 1.35 to 4.5 dex, the targets were selected from Jian et al. (2020) whose study involved the analysis of 63 stars (dwarfs, giants, and supergiants) observed with the WINERED spectrograph (Ikeda et al., 2016) in the *YJ* bands.

4.1.4 The goal of this chapter

In this chapter, we aim to provide guidelines on the spectroscopic analysis to get reliable stellar parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$) using the LDR method in an “adapted” version accomodating to the Cepheids temperature range. The necessary steps include identifying useful lines, measuring their depths, finding line pairs that optimize the results, creating relations for both T_{eff} and $\log g$, and the validation based on the comparison with stellar parameters from literatures.

4.2 Line Identification and Selection

As stated above, we will work under what was proposed in Taniguchi et al. (2021), i.e., using neutral and ionized lines of the same species. In this work, we follow what was prescribed in Matsunaga et al. (2021) by pairing Fe I–Fe II and Ca I–Ca II lines within 9760–10860 Å and 11600–13190 Å corresponding to WINERED echelle orders in the *Y* band (52nd–57th) and the *J* band (43rd–47th). The preliminary test of the line pairs proposed in Matsunaga et al. (2021) on our sample of Cepheids led to finding that they did not work well in hotter targets ($T_{\text{eff}} > 6000$ K), i.e., some lines at high temperatures were too shallow to give the LDRs.

It is worth mentioning that there were indeed other elements found in the spectra such as Si and Ti displaying both neutral and ionized lines yet they were rejected

from the analysis as their inclusion may hamper the construction of the line pairs that have valid LDR relations satisfying the requirements (target selection, T_{eff} range, $\log g$ range). From Matsunaga et al. (2021) we obtained a list of 97 candidates lines for the four species (76 Fe I, 5 Fe II, 11 Ca I and 5 Ca II) that must be confirmed in the observed spectra.

4.2.1 Hands on: measuring the line depth

We measured the depths of all of the 97 potential line candidates by doing a Gaussian fit to the section around five pixels around the line center λ_c (expected). Once the line minimum (λ_0) is determined and assuming that the continuum normalization is properly done, the depth is the "distance" from the continuum level (the unity) to the flux at λ_c . If the continuum level is not well normalized and the estimated distance gives a negative number, e.g., in presence of spiky features that could not be corrected, or when the position of λ_0 is too away from λ_c , we reject the measurement. This procedure was done using the `ir_ldr` python package developed by Jian, M. (private communication) (https://github.com/MingjieJian/ir_ldr).

The error of every depth measurement is linked to the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) for the target (obj) and the telluric standard (tell), and we add the two errors in quadrature:

$$e = \sqrt{e_{obj}^2 + e_{tell}^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{(S/N)_{obj}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{(S/N)_{tell}}\right)^2} \quad (4.4)$$

This formula is used for all the orders except the echelle orders 53 and 54, for which we perform no telluric correction and the error is simply $e = e_{obj}$.

4.3 LDR Relations Established With the Calibrators' Spectra

Among the 97 line candidates from Matsunaga et al. (2021) only a fraction satisfy the following requirements:

- Valid measurements for each neutral line should be ≥ 20 .
- Valid measurements for ionized lines should be ≥ 12 .
- The T_{eff} range of stars in which line is detected should exceed 1000 K.
- The $\log g$ range of stars in which each line is detected should exceed 2.5 dex.

The next step is pairing the lines and assessing how precise estimates of T_{eff} is possible. We note that both lines conforming the line pair should belong to the same band.

First, we use Fe I–Fe I pairs for estimating T_{eff} . As mentioned in Section 4.1.1, pairing lines of low and high excitation potential (having a $\Delta\text{EP} \geq 1$ eV) gives higher sensitivity to T_{eff} . Thus, the LDR of each pair is defined as $r = d_{\text{low}}/d_{\text{high}}$, i.e., the ratio of the depth of the line with a lower excitation potential (d_{low}) to the depth of the line with a higher excitation potential (d_{high}). We consider the following four forms of the relation between r and T_{eff} :

$$r = \alpha + \beta \cdot T_{\text{eff}} \quad (\text{T1})$$

$$r = \alpha + \beta \cdot \log T_{\text{eff}} \quad (\text{T2})$$

$$\log r = \alpha + \beta \cdot T_{\text{eff}} \quad (\text{T3})$$

$$\log r = \alpha + \beta \cdot \log T_{\text{eff}} \quad (\text{T4})$$

We rejected line pairs for which only 30 or fewer validated measurements of r were available and those for which the LDR relations have the dispersions larger than 200 K. In addition, the range of T_{eff} covered by the points used for the fitting must be larger than 1000 K. The last condition is considered in order to make each LDR relation useful for a wide range of targets. For each line pair, one of the forms

(T1)–(T4) was selected to give the smallest dispersion.

Second, we consider pairs of neutral and ionized lines, i.e., Fe I–Fe II and Ca I–Ca II pairs, for estimating the surface gravity, $\log g$. Their LDRs are defined as $r = d_{\text{Fe I}}/d_{\text{Fe II}}$ and $r = d_{\text{Ca I}}/d_{\text{Ca II}}$, and included in the LDR relations in the following forms:

$$r = \alpha + \beta \cdot T_{\text{eff}} + \gamma \cdot \log g \quad (\text{TG1})$$

$$r = \alpha + \beta \cdot \log T_{\text{eff}} + \gamma \cdot \log g \quad (\text{TG2})$$

$$\log r = \alpha + \beta \cdot T_{\text{eff}} + \gamma \cdot \log g \quad (\text{TG3})$$

$$\log r = \alpha + \beta \cdot \log T_{\text{eff}} + \gamma \cdot \log g \quad (\text{TG4})$$

Finally, we selected the set of the LDR relations, among those which were not rejected in the above steps, in order to include each line only in one line pair. This limit was also considered by many previous LDR works (e.g., Taniguchi et al., 2021; Matsunaga et al., 2021). The purpose of this limit is to make estimates from individual LDR relations that are independent and to make the error estimate simple. We then obtained 12 Fe I–Fe I, 5 Fe I–Fe II, and 5 Ca I–Ca II relations (Table 4.1). According to the form of each relation (T1–T4 for Fe I–Fe I pairs and TG1–TG4 for other pairs), the residual around the relation, σ_y where y is r or $\log r$, and the corresponding scatter (σ_p) in T_{eff} or $\log g$ are listed. The illustration of each relation is given in Appendix C

TABLE 4.1: LDR relations

ID	Line 1	Line 2	Form	α	β	γ	σ_y	σ_p	N
(1)	FeI 10155.162	FeI 10353.804	T3	2.7077	-4.857×10^{-4}	—	0.0524	108	39
(2)	FeI 10167.468	FeI 10347.965	T3	2.4553	-4.642×10^{-4}	—	0.0571	123	40
(3)	FeI 10195.105	FeI 10216.313	T3	2.4398	-5.560×10^{-4}	—	0.0691	124	45
(4)	FeI 10218.408	FeI 10227.994	T2	72.136	-18.751	—	0.2445	162	44
(5)	FeI 10340.885	FeI 10532.234	T2	19.291	-4.921	—	0.0398	100	50
(6)	FeI 10395.794	FeI 9861.7337	T2	18.188	-4.617	—	0.0452	122	44
(7)	FeI 10423.743	FeI 10863.518	T4	17.462	-4.725	—	0.0471	124	34
(8)	FeI 10577.139	FeI 10849.465	T2	26.307	-6.875	—	0.0756	137	37
(9)	FeI 10616.721	FeI 9868.1857	T2	19.550	-5.134	—	0.0627	152	38
(10)	FeI 10783.050	FeI 9889.0351	T2	17.490	-4.500	—	0.0520	143	42
(11)	FeI 10818.274	FeI 9811.5041	T4	16.377	-4.368	—	0.0412	117	43
(12)	FeI 12556.996	FeI 12648.741	T2	21.845	-5.667	—	0.0616	135	33
(13)	FeI 9868.1857	FeII 9997.5980	TG4	25.958	-7.089	0.2342	0.0492	0.21	73
(14)	FeI 10347.965	FeII 10173.515	TG3	1.9225	-4.140×10^{-4}	0.2462	0.0707	0.29	58
(15)	FeI 10353.804	FeII 10366.167	TG4	37.574	-10.112	0.2712	0.0742	0.27	60
(16)	FeI 10611.686	FeII 10501.500	TG3	2.0675	-4.763×10^{-4}	0.2260	0.0654	0.29	88
(17)	FeI 10818.274	FeII 10862.652	TG3	3.7109	-7.790×10^{-4}	0.2527	0.0656	0.26	58
(18)	CaI 10838.970	CaII 9854.7588	TG2	19.998	-5.344	0.2075	0.0670	0.32	67
(19)	CaI 10343.819	CaII 9890.6280	TG2	44.686	-11.830	0.3533	0.1174	0.33	73
(20)	CaI 10846.792	CaII 9931.3741	TG2	7.2836	-1.949	0.0799	0.0322	0.40	66
(21)	CaI 12105.841	CaII 11838.997	TG2	5.2136	-1.403	0.0644	0.0302	0.47	70
(22)	CaI 13033.554	CaII 11949.744	TG2	10.769	-2.875	0.1102	0.0340	0.31	72

Using these relations, we can determine T_{eff} and $\log g$ as follows:

(1) First, the LDR for each of the Fe I–Fe I pairs can be converted to an estimate of effective temperature, $T_{\text{LDR},i}$. We also estimate its error, e_i , considering the error in the LDR and the scatter of the LDR relation (σ_p in Table 4.1). Then, we calculate the weighted average and its standard error by

$$T_{\text{LDR}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pair}}} w_i T_{\text{LDR},i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pair}}} w_i} \quad (4.5)$$

$$e_T = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pair}}} w_i (T_{\text{LDR},i} - T_{\text{LDR}})^2}{(N_{\text{pair}} - 1) \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pair}}} w_i}} \quad (4.6)$$

where w_i is a weight given by $1/e_i^2$.

(2) We then estimate $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ by combining the Fe I–Fe II and Ca I–Ca II relations with the T_{LDR} obtained above. Based on each LDR relations of a Fe I–Fe II pair or a Ca I–Ca II pair, we obtain an estimate of surface gravity, $\log g_i$, and its error. Then, we calculate the weighted mean ($\log g_{\text{LDR}}$) and the error according to the formulae similar to Equations (4.5) and (4.6).

Figures 4.2 and 4.3 summarize the results for T_{LDR} and $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ we obtained for Calibrators together with the results for Validators and Disk Targets. The deviations of T_{LDR} and $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ from those expected from the literature time-series data show the standard deviations ~ 90 K and ~ 0.2 dex (top panels). Larger deviations and/or larger errors are found at higher temperatures for T_{LDR} or at both higher and lower temperatures for $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ (middle). Absorption lines of neutral atoms tend to get weak at higher temperatures, while lines of ions tend to get weak at lower temperatures within the range of our interest. This trend is observed in the number of the line pairs used in the bottom panels and explains the larger deviations and errors seen in the middle panels. The standard deviation of T_{LDR} , ~ 90 K, is larger than 42 K found by Matsunaga et al. (2021) for stars with $4800 \leq T_{\text{eff}} \leq 6200$ K and $1.35 \leq \log g \leq 4.5$, while the standard deviation of $\log g_{\text{LDR}} \sim 0.2$ dex, is similar to 0.17 dex in Matsunaga et al. (2021). The larger standard deviation of T_{LDR} can be ascribed to the fact that our sample include a significantly larger number of stars with higher temperature.

FIGURE 4.2: Performance of the T_{LDR} estimation.

FIGURE 4.3: Same as Figure 4.2 but for $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ instead of T_{LDR} .

4.4 Application of the LDR Relations

We then applied the LDR relations established with the Calibrator Cepheids (Table 4.1) to Validator and Disk Target Cepheids. Figure 4.4 summarizes the results of T_{LDR} and $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$. The derived T_{eff} and $\log g$ for each phase are listed in Appendix D.

FIGURE 4.4: Estimated T_{LDR} and $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$ and their errors

4.5 Trend of Temperature and Surface Gravity

Looking at the $(T_{\text{eff}}, \log g)$ obtained with the literature curves in section 2.3.2, we realized that the two parameters are tightly correlated (Figure 4.5). Such a correlation can be expected because of the fact that the mean stellar parameters of Cepheids fall within the Cepheid instability strip, i.e., their mean T_{eff} and luminosities (and also $\log g$) should be (anti-) correlated. However, T_{eff} at individual phases are not necessarily within the instability strip. Moreover, the variations of T_{eff} and L do not follow the trend of the instability strip. A Cepheid becomes fainter when it gets cooler, while the instability strip makes fainter Cepheids warmer on average. Nevertheless, Figure 4.5 shows a tight correlation between T_{eff} and $\log g$ at individual phases of the Calibrator Cepheids. Fitting the 51 points available for 8 Calibrators in total, we obtained the relation,

$$\log g = 11.110 \cdot \log(T_{\text{eff}}/5800) + 1.877 \quad (4.7)$$

with the standard deviation of 0.179 dex.

FIGURE 4.5: Distribution of the (T_{eff} , $\log g$) of the Calibrator Cepheids given in the literature (Luck and Andrievsky, 2004; Luck et al., 2008; Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh, 2005; Kovtyukh et al., 2005)

Furthermore, we found that including the $\log P$ term reduces the scatter. As illustrated in Figure 4.6 (in the bottom-left panel), the residual around the $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log g$ relation shows the dependency on the period. With the $\log P$ term included, we obtained the relation,

$$\log g = 6.483 \cdot \log(T_{\text{eff}}/5800) - 0.775 \cdot \log P + 2.475, \quad (4.8)$$

with the scatter of 0.108 dex. This is a very small scatter. It is hard to estimate $\log g$ with such high precision based solely on spectra (Mészáros et al., 2013). We presented a method of using the line-depth ratio to estimate $\log g$ below, but the precision is lower than the prediction given by the $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log g\text{-}\log P$ relation. As far as we have noticed, such a tight correlation **including the $\log P$ term** has not been discussed in the literature, but it turns out to be very useful when deciding the $\log g$ to be used in the spectroscopic analysis.

FIGURE 4.6: $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log P\text{-}\log g$ trend, displaying the dispersion when the pulsation period P is included (right) or not (left) in the relation. $T_{\text{mid}} = 5800$.

Once the temperature gets estimated, we can use the tight relation between T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $\log P$ to estimate the surface gravity of classical Cepheids. Let us denote

this estimated surface gravity as $\log g_{\text{trend}}$. The horizontal lines in the right-hand-side panels of Figure 4.4 indicate the scatters around the $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log g\text{-}\log P$ relation (0.108 dex, solid line) and the $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log g$ relation (0.179 dex, dotted line). For the precision of $\log g_{\text{trend}}$, we need to take into account the temperature error (for example, the error in T_{LDR}) when we use the LDR method for both T_{eff} and $\log g$. A moderately large error of 100 K in T_{LDR} would lead roughly to the error of 0.12 dex in $\log g_{\text{trend}}$ combined with the scatter of the $T_{\text{eff}}\text{-}\log g\text{-}\log P$ relation. Using $\log g_{\text{trend}}$ is, therefore, more accurate and robust than using $\log g_{\text{LDR}}$.

Chapter 5

Abundance Analysis: Methodology

5.1 Introduction

The vast majority of atoms in the Universe are Hydrogen (H) or Helium (He) whose origin dates back to some moments after the Big Bang. Other elements, inconveniently called “metals”, are believed to have been created through the nuclear fusion in stars or energetic events like supernovae explosions and neutron star mergers. The amount of the heavier elements (or metals) is denominated “metallicity”. Roughly speaking, it gives us a hint on when a star or nebula was formed. For instance, having a star whose metallicity is low indicates that the star might have been “born” a long time ago. In contrast, a star with higher metallicity could have formed “recently”.

Once we have estimated and tested our results for the effective temperature and surface gravity, it is time to tackle an interrogate beyond our solar neighborhood, related to how our galaxy has evolved, and reconstruct its chemical history through the study of chemical abundances. In this sense, Cepheids offer unique conditions to reach a better understanding in this matter. They are well-known chemical tracers as we can observe a sufficient number of absorption lines of many species with whose detailed abundances can be obtained. Moreover, they are good distance indicators, allowing us to draw the chemical structure of the Galaxy, such as the abundance gradient.

5.1.1 Oscillator strength: log gf values

The oscillator strength, a dimensionless quantity that measures the strength of a transition, can be estimated in the laboratory, theoretically, or from astronomical observations of the absorption spectral lines. Errors in log gf affect our abundance estimates in the NIR regime, in particular, we lack of accurate log gf values and it is needed to calibrate them as we will present in further sections.

In order to illustrate a detailed formulation (see Gray, 2005), let its derivation be recalled from the definition of the total energy (per second per atom per square radian) absorbed by the line taken from an I_λ beam, as it follows:

$$\int_0^\infty \alpha d\lambda = \int_{-\infty}^\infty \alpha d\Delta\lambda = \frac{\pi e^2}{mc} \frac{\lambda^2}{c} \quad (5.1)$$

Where α is the absorption coefficient per atom, λ , the wavelength in Angstrom, m , the electron mass, and c , the speed of light. It has been proved that actual values of the total absorption tend to be smaller than what is predicted by Equation 5.1, the amount of such deficit is different for different lines. The solution to such a problem came from a quantum mechanical analysis by introducing a factor f that compensates for the observed differences. The oscillator strength (f) can be then formulated as:

$$\int_0^\infty \alpha d\nu = \frac{\pi e^2}{mc} f \quad (5.2)$$

The f value is different for any atom at different transition levels which is determined by the atomic transition probability B_{lu} , the Einstein Coefficient that tells us the probability(ies) of an atom (or molecule) to undergo a transition from a state of lower energy (l) to another of upper energy (u), in a frequency range from ν to $\nu + d\nu$. Then, Equation (5.2) can be expressed in terms of a probability, as:

$$\int_0^\infty \alpha d\nu = B_{lu} h\nu \quad (5.3)$$

Re-arranging:

$$f = \frac{mc}{\pi e^2} B_{lu} h\nu \quad (5.4)$$

The Einstein coefficients can be expressed as:

$$B_{ul} = B_{lu} \frac{g_l}{g_u} \quad , \quad A_{ul} = \frac{2h\nu^3}{c^2} B_{ul}$$

So that:

$$f = \frac{mc^3}{2\pi e^2 \nu^2} \frac{g_u}{g_l} A_{ul} \quad (5.5)$$

This approach can also be understood as the number of valence electrons that might experience a transition. With g_u and g_l being the statistical weights of the upper and lower levels, the usage of these weights to indicate the value of the line strength ($\log gf$) is commonly accepted and will be used in this work.

As stated before, the uncertainties in the gf values are of significant importance when determining the abundances. Several studies aimed to improve the error budget carried by this quantity have been done mainly in optical regimes (see Meléndez et al., 2006, and references therein). In contrast to absorption lines in the optical range which have been established in the long history of astronomical spectroscopy, a large fraction of lines in the infrared range lacks accurate $\log gf$ values (see, e.g., Andreasen et al., 2016). One of the important goals in this chapter is the calibration of $\log gf$ for the lines present in Cepheids' spectra as it may help to reduce the internal errors given mainly by the choice of the atmosphere model.

5.1.2 Microturbulence

One of the reasons for the broadening observed in the line forming region of Cepheids and other stars is the presence of turbulent motions, altogether with instrumental factors. Such turbulent motions can be classified according the size of the components experiencing such turbulent velocities are measured in terms of the mean free path of the photons. If the portions are smaller than the mean free path of the photons, we talk about microturbulence, which *-usually-* follows the Maxwellian Distribution of Speeds. On the other hand, if the portion itself is larger than such mean free path of photons then we call it macro turbulence.

FIGURE 5.1: Microturbulence and Macro turbulence difference scheme in terms of their free path. Figure from Cantiello, M. (2008).

Mucciarelli (2011) pointed out the limitations of such distinction as it might lead to a misunderstanding on the way the velocity fields distribute in the two scenarios, indeed, the turbulence occurs on the continuous scale from the micro to the macro turbulent regimes. From what is empirically observed, ζ not only broadens the line profiles but also increases the equivalent widths (Mucciarelli, 2011), and thus it has a direct impact on the measurement of abundances that cannot be neglected as it serves as a “fudge parameter” (Takeda, 2021), having a noticeable effect on moderately strong lines on the shoulder or flat part of the curve of growth. The impact of ζ depends on the line strengths, it can be quantified by imposing consistent abundances derived for a substantial number of lines of the same species. This procedure will be explained later, in detail, in Section 5.3.1.

5.2 Tools for Measuring Abundances with Individual Lines

5.2.1 Stellar models

We employ the *ATLAS9-APOGEE* atmosphere model described in Mészáros et al. (2012) throughout this work. This grid of model photospheres originally aimed for the SDSS-III/APOGEE surveys makes use of both *ATLAS9* ($[M/H] \in [-5, 1.5]$) and *MARCS* ($[M/H] \in [-2.5, 0.5]$) models, one of the new features of this model is the inclusion of the solar reference abundances given in Asplund et al. (2009) (see Table 1.1). On the other hand, in the original *ATLAS9* the solar abundances were given by Anders and Grevesse (1989). The grid of stellar parameters for each model is summarized in Figure 5.2. When performing the abundance determination, we fixed Carbon and α to be solar, and the solar we use keeps being the one given in Asplund et al. (2009) (Table 1.1).

FIGURE 5.2: The grid of $(T_{\text{eff}}, \log g)$ *ATLAS9* and *MARCS* models from Mészáros et al., 2012

5.2.2 Line lists

We adopted the list of Fe I lines from Kondo et al. (2019), who selected and confirmed the lines from VALD3 (Ryabchikova et al., 2015) and MB99 (Meléndez and Barbuy, 1999). The confirmation and validation of the majority of the Fe I lines were possible in the observed spectra of most of our targets. In order to perform the calibration

of the oscillator strength and abundance analysis not only for Fe I we imposed a series of conditions concerning the depth of lines which will be discussed in Chapter 7.

We consider line information in VALD and MB99 separately in the following analysis. Even if the same line appears in the two lists, we calibrate its $\log gf$ twice and measure the abundance using the line. In the analyses with each line list, we use each list for all the atomic lines.

Line candidates for each of the elements were obtained from the synthetic spectra “synthesized” by MOOG (Sneden et al., 2012) considering the stellar parameters of an average Cepheid ($T_{\text{eff}} = 5900 \text{ K}$, $\log g = 2.0$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$), using the line list from the [Vienna Atomic Line Database](#) (VALD). Potential candidates were then filtered by the following criteria :

- They have to be deep enough ($d > 0.03$)
- Blending ratio (the fraction corresponding to the line of interest within the region of the absorption line) less than 0.3.
- Having a wide ($T_{\text{eff}}, \log g$) range.

5.2.3 Spectral synthesis codes: MOOG

During the passage of this work, we have referred to a “synthetic spectrum” several times. It is convenient now to explicit how a synthetic spectrum was created for the purposes of this thesis. MOOG developed by Sneden et al. (2012) was employed for synthesizing a spectrum with certain atmospheric parameters for a specific atmosphere model. MOOG performs a variety of LTE line analysis and spectrum synthesis tasks. The basic equations of LTE stellar line analysis are followed. The synthetic spectrum created with MOOG will be used in the next steps to estimate the abundances of different elements.

5.2.4 MPFIT

We estimate the abundance inferred from an individual line by searching iteratively for the set of free parameters (including the abundance) that gives the synthetic spectrum reproducing the observed spectrum with the least residual. The original “MPFIT” tool created and developed by Yoichi Takeda (Takeda, 1995) performs such an optimization to determine the abundance and has been used in many applications including some studies with WINERED spectra (Kondo et al., 2019; Fukue et al., 2021).

In this study, we use the MPFIT tool developed by Daisuke Taniguchi (private communication) who improved and optimized some parts of the original one by Takeda. In the original version, the theoretical fluxes ($F_{\lambda_i}; i = 1, 2, \dots$) will be computed for a given set of parameters ($x_k, k = 1, 2, \dots$) where k denotes each parameter and i , the wavelength point. In Taniguchi’s version the combination of parameters included: abundance of interest, line broadening, wavelength shift, and continuum normalization factor. The optimized solution minimizes the residual

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - C \cdot \eta_i)^2}{N} \quad (5.6)$$

between the model’ flux (η_i) and the observed flux (y_i). In the original version of MPFIT (Takeda, 1995), η_i and y_i are on the logarithmic scale, but in Taniguchi’s version we used, the fluxes (η_i and y_i) are on the linear scale. Through this optimization, we obtain the following four variables solved as free parameters:

1. The abundance(s) of the element(s) that we are trying to determine. In our analysis, we consider only one species in each MPFIT run.
2. The velocity offset (rv) that is required to adjust the wavelengths between the synthetic and observed spectra. This parameter should be small as our spectra are already corrected for radial velocity (Section 3.5), though each line’s wavelength is expected to differ from the theoretical one by $\sim 1\%$ because of imperfect wavelength calibration and/or inhomogeneous wavelength offsets.
3. The continuum normalization factor (cnorm, corresponding to C in Eq. 5.6) that

is required to correct the systematic offset in the flux level between the synthetic and observed spectra. Even though our spectra are already normalized (Section 3.4), there can be some bias at the level of $\sim 1\%$ ($\leq 1\text{km s}^{-1}$).

4. The line broadening with the Gaussian profile (FWHM). This can include the broadening caused by various factors including macro-turbulence, rotation, and instrumental broadening.

The optimization is done iteratively and the number of iteration (`niter`) is usually smaller than 10, and some problem is expected if the number is too large.

The abundance estimate with the MPFIT could be problematic in some cases. For example, if there are blended line(s) and they are not well reproduced in the synthetic spectra, the fitting would be disturbed and we cannot trust the resultant parameters (abundance, line wavelength, width, etc). Such disturbed measurements should be rejected, and we make the rejection of the measurements according to the resultant parameters as follows. First, we reject obviously erroneous outputs from the MPFIT run:

1. The number of iterations (`niter`) should be positive and less than 40.
2. The velocity offset (`rv`) should be within $\pm 10\text{km s}^{-1}$.
3. The full width at half maximum (`fwhmv`) should be positive and less than 100km s^{-1} .

Then, excluding the measurements rejected with the above criteria, we check the distribution of some parameters obtained with the MPFIT for the measurements for all the useful lines in a given spectrum. Figure 5.3 shows how the distributions of the three parameters (`fwhmv`, `rv`, `cnorm`) change with ζ . The dependency on ζ is not strong, and thus we combine all the measurements over the entire ζ to set the rejection thresholds. Moreover, we use the distributions for Fe I lines, which are the most fundamental sets of lines and are used for determining ζ . Thus, we calculate the quartiles (q_1, q_2, q_3) of the three parameters and reject the measurements outside the acceptable range $[q_1 - 1.5(q_3 - q_1) : q_3 + 1.5(q_3 - q_1)]$ using the same thresholds for the measurements with any ζ . We reject the measurements for which any of the three parameters are outside the acceptable range and use only the accepted measurements in the following steps described below.

FIGURE 5.3: The quartiles of FWHM (left), RV (middle), and the normalization factor (right) as functions of ξ are indicated by solid curves. The dashed curves indicate the upper and lower rejection thresholds. The results for FeI lines and other lines are given in red and blue, respectively. The plot here presents the result for δ Cep on 2013 Dec 2. In our analysis, we ignored the dependency on ξ and used the quartiles of all the available measurements for FeI lines to determine the rejection thresholds indicated by black horizontal lines.

5.3 Methods

5.3.1 Abundances as a function of microturbulence

For each absorption line, we measure the abundance as a function of microturbulence. We considered a grid with 24 different ξ values ranging from 1.4 to 6.0 km s⁻¹ with the step of 0.2 km s⁻¹. Each run of MPFIT was performed for a fixed $\xi \in [1.4 - 6.0]$ for each spectrum. In some cases, the MPFIT fails to give reasonable abundances for a part of the ξ grid points. We reject the measurements of a given line entirely if we get less than 20 measurements over the ξ grid.

Due to the effect of line saturation, the abundance obtained in each MPFIT run depends on ξ . As illustrated in the example in Figure 5.4, different lines show different trends of abundance against ξ . Deep lines show higher dependency on ξ because they are more saturated, while weaker lines show little dependency. When many lines are strong and show the dependency on ξ , the averaged abundance itself depends on ξ , i.e., the estimates of abundance and ξ show degeneracy. In contrast, if the majority of the lines are weak and depend little on ξ , the final estimate of abundance is more-or-less independent of the estimated ξ .

Such curves for Fe I lines are used when we determine ξ in Chapter 6. Also, for other species, examining such trends is useful to see how the microturbulence affects the measured abundance. Moreover, we use a plot like Figure 5.4 to identify the absorption lines whose measurements for a particular spectrum need to be rejected. We calculate the mean and standard deviation, σ , at each ξ grid point. The solid curve in Figure 5.4 indicates the curve of mean, while the dashed curves indicate the upper and lower limits (the mean $\pm 2\sigma$). Because of the different dependency on ξ , some curves of good measurements (especially the lines showing strong dependency on ξ) may well get outside the range between the upper and lower limits at some ξ . We reject the absorption lines whose curve in the ξ -[X/H] diagram is outside the limits at all the ξ grid points. We make this rejection of the outlying curves once and re-calculate the mean and standard deviation at each ξ .

FIGURE 5.4: Fe I abundances as a function of microturbulence. The case of η Aql observed on 2016 March 21.

5.3.2 Calibrating the oscillator strengths

We calibrate the $\log gf$ values of absorption lines present in Cepheids' spectra. We consider Fe I lines in Chapter 6 and lines of other species in Chapter 7. For this purpose, we use the Calibrators' spectra as follows.

We assume that the stellar parameters including the microturbulence (ζ) are known for each phase of spectroscopic observation. As described in Section 2.3, we obtained the stellar parameters ($T_{\text{eff}}, \log g, \zeta$) at each phase of our observations with the WINERED by interpolating the curves of each parameter given by Luck (2018). For each combination of absorption line and spectrum, we run the MPFIT to get the abundance. The deviation $\Delta \log gf$ of this abundance from the known abundance includes, together with other errors, the offset in $\log gf$.

We find that the $\Delta \log gf$ values obtained for deep lines tend to show large systematic offsets. This trend is clearer in the elements with both weak lines and very strong lines like Si I, more than Fe I, as we present in Chapter 7. We speculate that the microturbulence varies in the upper layers of pulsating Cepheids' atmospheres in which deeper lines are formed. We thus use the measurements for lines shallower than 0.2 in depth (the separation of the absorption core from the continuum level in each observed spectrum). In addition, among $\Delta \log gf$ of the not-too-strong lines, we reject outliers with the 2σ clipping according to the standard deviation (Section 5.3.1).

Then, we take the average and the standard deviation to calibrate the $\log gf$ and give its error of each line. We require that 20 or more $\Delta \log gf$ values must be used for the calibration. If the number of $\Delta \log gf$ is less than 20, we reject such a line considering that it is not very useful for determining the abundances of Cepheids over a reasonable range of conditions such as T_{eff} (hotter Cepheids tend to show limited absorption) and S/N of observations (low-S/N spectra tend to give poor measurements). We can use the same procedure for Fe I lines (Chapter 6) and lines of each of other species (Chapter 7).

5.3.3 Determining microturbulence

The basic idea for determining the microturbulence ζ is to find the condition that makes the abundances from lines of various strength (non- or less-saturated lines to saturated lines) consistent. Mucciarelli (2011) discusses some methods of determining ζ .

We here take a simple, classical approach. As described in Section 5.3.1, we measure the abundance from each line as a function of ζ . Combining the results for lines with different strengths, we search for ζ with which the abundances show no dependency on line strength. We use the X index,

$$X = \log gf - \text{EP} \cdot \frac{5040}{0.86 T_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (5.7)$$

as the indicator of line strength (Magain, 1984; Gratton et al., 2006). The equivalent width might be a good indicator, but measuring the equivalent width in the observed spectra is not a trivial task as other factors, such as blending, may disturb the results. We measure the line depth and use it for rejecting lines deeper than 0.2 in depth, but prefer to use the X indicator here because it is a theoretical value unaffected by observational errors. Then, at each ζ , we fit the linear relation,

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = aX + b, \quad (5.8)$$

to the abundances ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) from individual lines as a function of the X index. The slope a changes with ζ and we select the ζ , one of the ζ grid points with the 0.2 km s^{-1} step, that gives the slope closest to zero. Figure 5.5 illustrates a result of this analysis (for δ Cep). Fukue et al. (2021) performed a simulation to find that determining ζ requires at least 20 absorption lines. We use only Fe I lines to estimate ζ .

FIGURE 5.5: The slope a (Equation 5.8) as a function of ζ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ as a function of the X index for $\zeta_{\text{best}} = 2.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ that leads to the flat trend in the bottom panel. This case for δ Cep on 2013 Dec 02 (with the VALD lines used) is presented as an example of the analysis to determine ζ . The red horizontal line indicates the final estimate of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for the obtained ζ_{best} given by the weighted mean of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from individual lines, while the gray dashed line indicates $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from the literature (Luck, 2018).

5.3.4 Determining the abundance with the microturbulence given

Once the microturbulence is obtained, it is relatively simple to derive the abundances making use of an established list of lines (with calibrated $\log gf$). For each species, we calculate the weighted mean of $[X/H]_i$ from N individual lines that were not rejected,

$$[X/H] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (w_i [X/H]_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i} \quad (5.9)$$

where the weights are given by $w_i = 1/e_i^2$ and e_i is the error in the calibrated $\log gf$. We consider the weighted standard deviation,

$$e_{X,1} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i ([X/H]_i - [X/H])^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i}} \quad (5.10)$$

as the error of $[X/H]$. Using the standard deviation rather than the standard error (i.e., the standard deviation divided by $\sqrt{N-1}$) is commonly done and recommended by Jofré, Heiter, and Soubiran (2019). However, Equation 5.10 would underestimate the uncertainty of the averaged abundance when $[X/H]_i$ with a small number of lines get closer, than expected from the statistical errors to each other by coincidence. We consider another indicator of the uncertainty,

$$e_{X,2} = \sqrt{1 / \sum_{i=1}^N w_i} \quad (5.11)$$

which is given by the error propagation. Then, we take the larger of $e_{X,1}$ and $e_{X,2}$ as the error e_X of the derived $[X/H]$.

In the case of Fe I, the derivation of $[\text{Fe I}/H]$ and its error is done immediately after the determination of ξ . As in Figure 5.5, the selected ξ gives (almost) a flat trend of $[\text{Fe I}/H]$ against the line strength (X) and we calculate the weighted mean and standard deviation using the measurements of individual lines like those presented in the figure. Then, we can use the same ξ to estimate the abundances and errors of other species once we select and calibrate the lines for them.

When we have $[X/H]$ estimated with multiple spectra of each Cepheid, we would like to take the mean of phase-by-phase measurements. We calculate the weighted mean using the formula like Equations 5.9 but with the weights that are determined with the e_X of individual phases. The errors are also determined in the same way by taking the larger of the weighted standard deviation (Equation 5.10) and the propagated error (Equation 5.11).

Chapter 6

Abundance Analysis: Iron

6.1 Calibration of the Oscillator Strengths

We consider Fe I lines compiled by Kondo et al. (2019). These authors and later Fukue et al. (2021) used the lines to confirm the abundances of the prototype red giants, Arcturus ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.52$) and μ Leo ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.25$). However, the standard deviation of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from individual lines (for all the Calibrators sample and their pulsation cycle), 0.1–0.3 dex, is larger than the typically achievable 0.05–0.1 dex with optical high-quality spectra (see the discussion in Fukue et al., 2021). Adopted from their list are 75 lines from VALD and 64 lines from MB99 within the wavelength ranges we consider.

We use the 51 reference spectra, in total, of the 8 Calibrator Cepheids. We measured the depths of these lines following the algorithm described in Section 4.2.1. We avoid using the measurements of lines deeper than 0.2 (see Chapter 7). Since we require that we get more than 20 good measurements of each line obtained with the reference spectra in order to calculate a new $\log gf$ value, we reject at this stage the lines for which we have less than 20 accepted measurements with depth smaller than 0.2. 64 lines from VALD and 53 lines from MB99 passed this stage.

Then, we used the MPFIT tool to obtain the Fe I abundance (simply denoted $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) as a function of ζ for each line (Section 5.3.1). We applied the rejection criteria according to the parameters, `niter`, `fwhmv`, and `rv` (Section 5.2.4). We require

that the MPFIT measurements are successful at 19 or more grid points of ζ . In addition, we reject the ζ -[Fe/H] curves that show unexpected upturn by more than 0.05 dex; i.e., we reject a curve if [Fe/H] at the largest ζ is higher than [Fe/H] at the smallest ζ by 0.05 dex or more. Thus, the accepted curves have sufficient numbers of good MPFIT measurements and show flat or decreasing trends against ζ (see, e.g., Figure 5.4).

With each of the accepted ζ -[Fe/H] curves, we calculate [Fe/H] at the ζ expected with the time-series data of Luck (2018) (Section 2.3.2). Thus, based on the 51 reference spectra, we get the offsets from the literature [Fe/H] ($\Delta \log gf_i$), although measurements from some spectra are rejected. We require 20 or more $\Delta \log gf_i$ values to calculate the mean, which we consider is the offset to add for the calibration. In addition, we consider the standard deviation of $\Delta \log gf_i$ values to be the error of the final $\log gf$ after the calibration. Figure 6.1 shows an example. We successfully made the calibration of 42 VALD lines and 37 MB99 lines, and Table E.1 lists the $\log gf$ values before and after the calibration.

FIGURE 6.1: The offset in $\log gf$ inferred from individual spectra. Horizontal lines indicate the mean (solid) and the standard deviation (dotted), for which we neglected the measurements for the absorption deeper than 0.2 (vertical dotted line). This is for FeI 9800.3075 with the original $\log gf$ taken from VALD.

Figure 6.2 shows $\Delta \log gf$ values against the number of measurements used for the calibration. We see some differences between the $\Delta \log gf$ for VALD lines and

those for MB99 lines. There are 34 Fe I lines common between VALD and MB99 and we calibrated their $\log gf$, the comparison of which is presented in Figure 6.3. The systematic offset in $\Delta \log gf$ between VALD and MB99 corresponds to the offset in the $\log gf$ values in the two line lists. This offset was also found by Kondo et al. (2019).

FIGURE 6.2: The offsets between the original and new $\log gf$ values in our calibration.

FIGURE 6.3: Comparison of $\log g f$ before and after the calibration for the lines in both VALD and MB99.

6.2 Derivation of Microturbulence and $[Fe/H]$

Using the 42 VALD and 37 MB99 Fe I lines with $\log gf$ calibrated, we determined ζ and $[Fe/H]$ of all the spectra of all the Cepheids in the three categories (Calibrators, Validators, and Disk Targets). The method is given in Section 5.3.3. We successfully obtained $(\zeta, [Fe/H])$ for 51 spectra of the 8 Calibrator Cepheids, 17 spectra of the 5 Validator Cepheids, and 7 spectra of the 7 Disk Target Cepheids. The results are presented in the Appendix E (Section E.1).

FIGURE 6.4: (Upper) The number of Fe I lines used for deriving ζ and $[Fe/H]$. (Lower) The standard deviations of $[Fe/H]$ from individual lines.

The upper panels of Figure 6.4 show how the number of Fe I lines that could be used depends on T_{eff} (upper left) and S/N (upper right), while the lower panels show how the standard deviation of $[Fe/H]$ from individual lines depends on T_{eff} (lower left) and S/N (lower right).

Figures 6.5 and 6.6 compare our estimates of $(\zeta, [Fe/H])$ with the literature values for Calibrators and Validators, respectively. The standard deviation of $\Delta[Fe/H]$

is 0.067 dex for Calibrators and 0.117 dex for Validators, while the standard deviation of $\Delta\zeta$ is 0.530 km s^{-1} for Calibrators and 0.439 km s^{-1} for Validators.

FIGURE 6.5: Deviations of our estimates of ζ and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from the literature values. For Calibrators.

FIGURE 6.6: Same as Figure 6.5, but for Validators.

Figure 6.7 shows how ζ depends on the period and the effective temperature. The derived ζ tends to be larger in Cepheids with longer periods and those with lower T_{eff} . The orange lines indicate the trends,

$$\zeta_{f(\log P)} = 1.5(\log P - 0.8) + 3.25, \quad (6.1)$$

$$\zeta_{f(T_{\text{eff}})} = -0.00065(T_{\text{eff}} - 5500) + 3.45, \quad (6.2)$$

around which the scatters are $\sim 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ for Calibrators and Validators while $\sim 1.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ for Disk Targets. The residuals of $\sim 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ are not significantly larger than the deviations between our ζ and the literature values ($\sim 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, in Figures 6.5 and 6.6). Therefore, maybe it is useful to have ζ estimated with these trends when it is impossible to estimate ζ with our method or others based on spectra or when large errors are expected. The residuals around the $\log P$ - ζ trend show no dependency on the effective temperature, and those around the T_{eff} - ζ trend show no dependency on ζ . Therefore, considering the $\log P$ - T_{eff} - ζ relation does not reduce the residuals significantly.

FIGURE 6.7: ξ plotted against $\log P$ (upper) and T_{LDR} (lower). The orange lines indicate the approximate trends given in Equation 6.2 and 6.2

Chapter 7

Abundance Analysis: Other Species

7.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to identify and characterize absorption lines available in Cepheids' spectra for determining the abundances of various species other than neutral Iron (Fe I). In this thesis, we consider the following species: neutral Silicon (Si I), neutral Phosphorus (P I), neutral Sulphur (S I), neutral and ionized Calcium (Ca I, Ca II), ionized Iron (Fe II), neutral Zinc (Zn I), ionized Yttrium (Y II), and ionized Dysprosium (Dy II).

Some of the elements mentioned above are identified as heavy metals (or simply heavy elements), i.e., those with atomic numbers $Z \geq 29$ (some of them belonging to the α elements such as Ca and Si). Even though their absorption lines are rather limited, they offer unique perspectives on the chemical evolution of galaxies. Within this group of heavy elements we can distinguish a representative sample, namely, the neutron-capture (*n-capture*) elements starting with a $Z \geq 31$ whose isotopes are created as a result of neutron incorporation reactions. Given the conditions on the density of neutrons and the time taken for such nucleosynthesis process to happen (compared to β decay rates), n-capture nucleosynthesis can be either slow (*s-process*) occurring mainly in asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars or rapid (*r-process*) happening in different sites in the death of a massive star as a supernova and its remnants. It is worth noting that both s and r process contribute to the synthesis of most, if not

all, of the n-capture element (Snedden, Cowan, and Gallino, 2008).

In addition, increasing interests in biogenic elements emerge from rapid progress in the exoplanet field. Almost every single element known and registered in the periodic table plays, to some extent, a role in living systems on Earth, yet only about 20 of them make up the material of all the biological systems here and also outside our planet. These elements are sometimes referred to as *Essential Elements* for life, of which the most important are H, C, O, N, P, and S.

One of the problems addressed in this section is related to the $\log gf$ values of the absorption lines. For some of the elements treated here, there is a lack of information about the transition probabilities of the lines under study. This problem is particularly severe in the infrared regime. We propose here a way to calibrate the $\log gf$ values following the procedure established in Section 6.1.

7.2 Line Identification

First, we created a list of absorption lines for each element that we are going to use to measure the abundances. Excluding Fe I we discussed in the previous chapter, we consider Si I, P I S I, Ca I, Ca II, Fe II, Zn I, Y II, and Dy II in the following analysis. We also considered Sr II but gave it up because the available Sr II lines are too strong.

For the purpose of line identification, we created a synthetic spectrum by MOOG using stellar parameters for an average Cepheid ($T_{\text{eff}} = 5900$ [K], $\log g = 2.0$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$), for a given species and searched for lines whose depth is deeper than 0.02. Then, the lines complying with the given conditions have to be confirmed in the majority of the spectra of the Calibrator sample.

7.3 Calibration of the Oscillator Strengths

For the species mentioned in the above section, we created a "species" line list containing 105 lines from VALD and 90 lines from MB99 within our work wavelength

range. Analogously to what was done in Section 6.1, we started this procedure using only the calibrating sample, for 8 Calibrators Cepheids having a total of 51 spectra. For each of the lines in our species line list, the depth was measured using the algorithm detailed in Section 4.2.1. We first included strong lines but we found that the analysis with a fixed ξ did not work as we discuss in Section 7.3.1. Thus, we decided to exclude measurements if the line depths are larger than 0.2, and we present these obtained results in Section 7.3.2.

7.3.1 Failed calibration including strong lines

For the analysis in this subsection, we included the MPFIT measurements for lines deeper than 0.2 but made the rejection with the parameters *niter*, *fwhmv*, *rv*, and *cnorm* (Section 5.2.4). Also, we required that each ξ -[X/H] curve has 19 or more accepted measurements and shows a flat or decreasing trend (Section 6.1). Then, comparing the [X/H] at the ξ given (expected) from Luck (2018) with the abundance given by Luck (2018), we get the offset $\Delta \log gf_i$ of the oscillator strength inferred from individual measurements. Figures 7.1–7.8 show all the available $\Delta \log gf_i$ values for a few species. The $\Delta \log gf_i$ values tend to be systematically high at depth larger than 0.2 - 0.25. This may be partly attributed to a systematic trend buried in the original $\log gf$ values in VALD and MB99. However, such a systematic trend of $\Delta \log gf$ exceeding 0.5 dex for all strong lines is unexpected. It is instead understood as the limitation of using a fixed microturbulence. As we discuss in more detail in Section 8.1.3, the microturbulence is expected to be significantly larger in the upper layers of the stellar atmosphere. Trying to calibrate $\log gf$ with underestimated ξ would lead to overestimates as we see here. Considering the depth-dependent ξ could make it possible to include such strong lines, but we have no set of atmosphere models with depth-dependent ξ for Cepheids in which the turbulent velocity field may well be different from static stars. Therefore, in this thesis, we reject lines stronger than 0.2 and focus on lines that appear with weak to moderate depths.

FIGURE 7.1: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for Si I lines from
VALD.

FIGURE 7.2: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for Si I lines from
MB99.

FIGURE 7.3: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for P I lines from
VALD.

FIGURE 7.4: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for P I lines from
MB99.

FIGURE 7.5: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for S I lines from
VALD.

FIGURE 7.6: $\Delta \log g f_i$
for S I lines from
MB99.

FIGURE 7.7: $\Delta \log gf_i$
for Ca I lines from
VALD.

FIGURE 7.8: $\Delta \log gf_i$
for Ca I lines from
MB99.

7.3.2 Calibration without including strong lines

Without including the measurements of lines whose depths were more than 0.2, we demand having more than 20 good measurements for each line in order to proceed with the calculations of new $\log gf$. The accepted measurements made a toll of 97 lines for VALD and 86 lines for MB99.

Subsequently, MPFIT was run for each of the accepted lines in order to obtain the abundance of each of the elements, let us denote it as $[X/H]$, as a function of ζ (as it is described in 5.3.1). The rejection criteria for the MPFIT outputs followed the prescription made in Section 5.2.4 for the parameters `niter`, `fwhmv`, `rv`, and `cnorm`. The MPFIT measurements that complied with the mentioned criteria are considered good when we have 19 or more grid points of ζ for each line. Also, as stated in Section 6.1, when we encounter $\zeta - [X/H]$ curves displaying a significant upturn by more than 0.05 dex, that means, if we find that the value of $[X/H]$ at the largest grid point of ζ is higher than the $[X/H]$ at the smallest ζ by 0.05 dex or more, that curve will be rejected. Thus, we accept curves having a sufficient number of good measurements showing a flat or decreasing trend over ζ .

Then, for the accepted $\zeta - [X/H]$ curves, we estimate the $[X/H]$ at the ζ given (expected) from the Luck (2018) dataset (Section 2.3), and thus, we can obtain the necessary shift to match the literature $[X/H]_{lit}$ values. We denominate such an offset given by each spectrum ($\Delta \log gf_i$), and calculate the mean of it from all the spectra

that give accepted measurements for the particular line. In order to calculate the mean we need 20 or more $\Delta \log gf_i$ values. The final error of the calibrated $\log gf$ of this offset is obtained by calculating the standard deviation of the $\Delta \log gf_i$. This calibration was effective enough for 48 VALD lines and 37 MB99 lines. The results of this procedure are given in Appendix E (Section E.2).

FIGURE 7.9: The offsets between the original and new $\log gf$ values in our calibration for the lines taken from VALD (upper) and MB99 (middle).

7.4 Derivation of abundances of various species

Using the 46 VALD and 35 MB99 lines with $\log gf$ calibrated, we determined the abundances, $[X/H]$, of 9 species. The results are given in Appendix F.2. Figures 7.10–7.18 plot $[X/H]$ and the deviations from the literature, Luck (2018) and Usenko et al. (2005), for Calibrators and Validators. For a few species, like Si I (Figure 7.10) and Fe II (Figure 7.15), we find very good agreements between our measurements and the literature values ($\sigma \sim 0.07$ dex). Some species, however, show large scatters ($\sigma > 0.15$ dex).

Table 7.1 summarizes how well the abundances we derived agree with the literature values. The mean offsets from the abundance scale of Luck (2018) are not significant for both Calibrators and Validators although the standard deviation is large for some species, in particular, Ca II and Zn I. The large offsets may be partly attributed to errors in Luck (2018). Looking at Figure 7.13 for Ca I and Figure 7.16 for Zn I, the abundances of some objects from Luck (2018) seem to show unexpected offsets from other objects; see, e.g., SU Cas and SZ Tau for Ca II and X Cyg for Zn I. Furthermore, Polaris shows significant and systematic offsets for a few species. These offsets are attributed to the systematic offsets of the abundance by Usenko et al. (2005) from the abundance scale of Luck (2018) illustrated in 2.7.

Finally, Figure 7.19 plots $[X/H]$ of 6 species as a function of $[Fe/H]$. Our measurements follow the trends found by Luck (2018) although the Disk Targets show large scatters. The error bars on these panels are given by the error estimated as described in Section 5.3.4.

TABLE 7.1: Deviations of abundances from the literature values, Luck (2018) and Usenko et al. (2005)

Species	Calibrators			Validators		
	Mean (dex)	SD (dex)	<i>N</i>	Mean (dex)	SD (dex)	<i>N</i>
[Si I/H]	-0.007	0.067	51	-0.007	0.072	17
[P I/H]	-0.008	0.066	51	-0.008	0.057	17
[S I/H]	-0.007	0.098	51	-0.007	0.094	17
[Ca I/H]	-0.000	0.075	50	-0.000	0.121	17
[Ca II/H]	0.109	0.301	32	0.109	0.178	13
[Fe II/H]	-0.003	0.083	51	-0.003	0.063	17
[Zn I/H]	-0.060	0.215	37	-0.060	0.126	11
[Y II/H]	-0.026	0.112	51	-0.026	0.090	17
[Dy II/H]	-0.005	0.176	20	-0.005	0.176	8

FIGURE 7.10: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Si I.

FIGURE 7.11: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for P I.

FIGURE 7.12: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for S I.

FIGURE 7.13: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Ca I.

FIGURE 7.14: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Ca II.

FIGURE 7.15: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Fe II.

FIGURE 7.16: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Zn I.

FIGURE 7.17: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Y II.

FIGURE 7.18: The derived abundances (upper) and the deviations from the literature values (lower) for Dy II.

FIGURE 7.19: $[Fe/H]$ - $[X/H]$ for six species (Si I, P I, S I, Ca I, Zn I, and Y II). Light blue circles represent the Calibrators. Green triangles, the Validators, and pink downward triangles represent the Disk Cepheids.

Chapter 8

Discussion

In this chapter, we would like to open a discussion on what we have found throughout this thesis and also what should be addressed in the future for coming projects. This chapter is divided into two sections, focused on two main aspects: the quality of our unique spectra and its implication on the derivation of stellar parameters and abundance analysis (Section 8.1) and, then, discussions on individual elements (Section 8.2). We also provide an atlas of the identified lines in our work regime which can be found in the Appendix A.

8.1 Discussions on Stellar Parameters

8.1.1 Limitations due to S/N and effective temperature

The method described in this work for obtaining effective temperatures using the LDR relations exposed in Chapter 4 has certain limitations caused mainly by the target's temperature and the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of the available spectrum. For instance, among the sample of Disk Cepheids, we have identified Cepheids whose spectra cannot be well treated with our method as their temperatures seem to be above of what our relations can cover. This reasoning is supported by their pulsational periods, as short as (1–3) days, meaning that they reach higher temperatures. In addition, the S/N of the spectra of Disk Targets are limited (Section 3.2).

Certainly, finding such limitations turns out to be helpful for further observation planning. It is then useful to determine what S/N is needed for specific targets (as a function of T_{eff} inferred from period and pulsations phase, if possible). It is also

important to mention that having an uncertain derivation of stellar parameters hampers the abundance analysis in a non-negligible way. Figures 4.2 and 4.3 illustrate the S/N dependency when deriving T_{eff} and $\log g$, as it is shown for the samples of Disk Targets and Validators. Having a low S/N means, in practical terms, that fewer lines can be resolved, therefore, fewer line pairs can be used for the targets. For some of the Disk Targets, the number of the lines we could measure go down to a minimum of 2. This can also happen when we deal with a warmer phase and lines get too shallow leading to a small number of useful line pairs. We were able to obtain acceptable T_{eff} estimates having a minimum S/N of ~ 70 yet, their error budget seems a bit bulky, and we thus recommend that for further observations a limit of S/N of above 100 is necessary to have a good performance of our method.

The consequences of having a low S/N for both T_{eff} and $\log g$ also get "propagated" into the abundances estimates. Figure 6.4 illustrates the number of lines that are available at given temperatures as well as at given S/N and consequently the errors in the metallicity at the given conditions.

8.1.2 The choice of literature (reference) data

In this work, we took T_{eff} and $\log g$ from Kovtyukh et al. (2005), Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh (2005), Luck and Andrievsky (2004), and Kovtyukh (2007) for calibration and validation (Chapter 4). Our results are well consistent with those obtained with optical spectra; for instance, their result in Figure 8.1 (Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh, 2005) agrees well with what we found for our targets in Figure 4.4.

FIGURE 8.1: Temperature and surface gravity variation for 30 Cepheids in Andrievsky, Luck, and Kovtyukh (2005).

It should be noted, however, that there might be systematic offsets between Luck (2018) and other authors. We adopted the abundances of Luck (2018) as reference, because they provide the largest set of Cepheids' abundances. For instance, the work of Takeda et al. (2013) includes a complete analysis on stellar parameters and abundances for different elements. The sample included in their analysis is not as complete as the one of Luck (2018) which matched all of our Calibrators and Validators (except for Polaris).

Polaris deserves special mention. Neither Luck (2018) nor Takeda et al. (2013) give the abundance of Polaris, and we took the measurements provided by Usenko et al. (2005) for comparison. However, their measurements show significant offsets from the trend for other Cepheids given by Luck (2018). Polaris itself has posed

much of debate in the last decades, as it was believed for a certain time that "it stopped pulsating" (Fernie, Kamper, and Seager, 1993) given the nature of its light curves exhibiting almost no variation, and later was confirmed that experiences non-negligible period changes (Usenko et al., 2005). Even when it is our nearest (and brightest) Cepheid, its distance is also a matter of controversy, with values varying significantly from one method to another and, as a consequence, stellar parameters are affected for such estimates. As of now, there is no agreement on how far from us Polaris is, nor for its evolutionary stage. We have to keep in mind that its brightness makes it impossible for being resolved by GAIA so the problem can not be solved "geometrically". We believe that a spectroscopic/interferometric approach could help solving this issue.

According to Usenko et al. (2005), they used the solar abundance given by Kurucz et al. (1984) with an $\log \epsilon_{Fe} = 7.50$, yet it is not totally clear what values were used for other elements. The abundances of Luck (2018) and Usenko et al. (2005) might be somehow, on different abundance scales (2.7 and therefore cannot be directly compared with each other.

8.1.3 The derivation of the Microturbulence

As we have discussed in Chapters 5 and 6, the microturbulence is affected by the line strength. When determining the $\log gf$ of the species, one interrogate that popped up was whether it was suitable to use the microturbulence obtained using only Fe I lines. We observed that having stronger lines such as those of Silicon or Strontium, will also affect the resulting ζ , providing evidence that ζ does change along the Cepheid's atmosphere, i.e., at different τ . This phenomena was first reported by Takeda and Sadakane (1997) in a HB star, later reported on RR Lyrae by Takeda et al. (2006), Kolenberg et al. (2010), and Fossati et al. (2014), suggesting that the microturbulence increases with height in the atmosphere of RR Lyrae stars and that a specific ζ should be applied to lines with specific strength in order to avoid wrong estimates of the abundances.

FIGURE 8.2: Comparison of the dependency of ζ on the atmosphere layer represented by the Rosseland optical depth τ_{Ross} from the studies of Kolenberg et al. (2010) and Fossati et al. (2014)

In this work, we found evidence of depth-dependent ζ for Cepheids for the first time (Figures 7.1 - 7.8). Thus, using only a fixed ζ for both weak and strong lines does not allow self consistent measurements, being the main reason why we decided to use only lines with depths smaller than 0.2. We note that this complication severely affects all the detected Sr II lines (those reported in Matsunaga et al. (2020)) are too strong and rejected due to the limit of line depth.

Figure 8.3 indicates the contribution function for the absorption lines confirmed for our Cepheids, in terms of the atmosphere height of the line forming region represented by the Rosseland optical depth τ_{Ross} and the depth of the line. We see that most of the lines tend to "cluster" at depths smaller than 0.2, where we can find almost all the lines under study except by Sr II, which is found at larger depths as well as for Si I which distributes uniformly throughout the depth range.

FIGURE 8.3: The different atmosphere heights (τ) for each line line under study.

8.2 Discussions on Individual Elements

In this section, we aim to discuss the astronomical background and impacts of individual species other than Fe I. A general perspective on what has been discussed in the literature for them as well as their prospects in the NIR YJ bands analyzed in this study.

8.2.1 Ionized Iron — Fe II

According to studies from various authors including Kovtyukh and Andrievsky (1999), Meléndez and Barbuy (2009), and references therein, the ionized Iron (Fe II) abundances are nearly insensitive to the model atmosphere' parameter degeneracy (T_{eff}). Some authors have reported that Fe II may exhibit small departures from LTE (Meléndez et al., 2006; Shchukina and Trujillo Bueno, 2001) in contrast to considerable mild effects for Fe II than for Fe I. Certainly, using Fe II as an abundance indicator, and sometimes even preferred over Fe I is not a rare thing in optical studies at least. A complete different scenario occurs for Infrared regimes where the amount

of these lines tends to be small. Another factor hampering the suitability of using Fe II as the primary abundance indicator is the uncertainty in their gf (oscillator strength) values, situation that during the last decade has not experienced major improvements. It is important to keep in mind that having an accurate and precise abundance determination of Fe II provides not only the information *de facto* but also allows us to validate our previous fundamental parameter estimates (such as surface gravity) by following the Saha Ionization Equilibrium (equation 4.3).

In the YJ bands, with WINERED spectra we identified a set of 13 Fe II lines, of which 12 had their $\log gf$ calibrated. An important thing to keep in mind is that, according to what was discussed above, indeed, Fe II serves as an abundance indicator as well as a proxy to the surface gravity, though, in our working regions, the number of lines available limited our attempts to take full advantage of the benefits of having a robust set of lines of this specie. An important aspect to keep in mind is that the studies including Fe II in the infrared are rather scarce, for instance, Marfil et al. (2020) studied FGK-type stars in the optical and NIR with CARMENES spectra only made use of only 2 lines at 99997.598 and 10501.503 in the Y band. We detected Fe I 99997.598 but its $\log gf$ was not calibrated as the line did not meet the requirements we impose for that procedure (see Section 6.1). Fe I 10501.503 was also included in Andreasen et al. (2016) work on the compilation of a new NIR line list for the Sun and HD 20010, and we confirmed this line in our spectra and made the calibration of its oscillator strength.

From what is currently available in the literature, we can infer that our study is the one that has provided the most extensive list of Fe II for the $Y - J$ bands applied to hotter stars, such as Cepheids. Though, the number is still relatively small compared to what is found in optical, our measurements allowed us to give a better calibration on their $\log gf$ as well as also using them as a key for deriving the surface gravity, as described in Chapter 4.

8.2.2 Neutral Phosphorus — P I

Phosphorus, an odd-Z ($Z = 15$) element, whose isotope (^{31}P) belongs to the same group as Nitrogen is believed to have been produced during the C and Ne burning. It is one of the most fundamental life-bearing elements dominated by macromolecules composed mainly by Carbon that are present in every single organism formed by cells. Each contains membranes and inner organelles whose primary component is a molecule denominated **Phospholipid** (a.k.a. phosphatides) which is a class of lipid whose molecule is formed by a hydrophilic head where the phosphate group is located as well as two hydrophobic tails. Moreover, from Biology, we know that when DNA is synthesized, a molecule called adenosine triphosphate (ATP) brings energy to the whole DNA structure, by keeping it together, as a superglue.

Phosphorus has surprisingly been "skipped" for years, an example of this is that prior 2011 with the study of Caffau et al. (2007), **P was barely analyzed in stars**. A possible cause for this sort of dodging was raised back in the early 1930's by Struve (1930) who found that no neutral P was available in spectra of stars whose spectral type ranged from F-K. Though, it was acknowledged that Phosphorus ions might be visible in other kinds of stars or other regimes (Maas et al., 2020; Naghma, Nahar, and Pradhan, 2018), such as P II, P III, P IV observable in UV spectra.

A handful of studies have been done on stars after the study of Caffau et al. (2007) which first suggested using the high-excitation P I lines in multiplet at 1051-1068 nm. Different authors have focused their attention on various other targets of interest: such as Hubrig et al. (2009) obtained P I abundance of HB stars in globular clusters. Meléndez et al. (2009) investigated the P I abundances of a handful of solar twins. Sbordone et al. (2009) suggested that Sulphur could have been produced by *proton capture* on P, leading to a debate on how possible it is to create the amount of S found there as a product of P when P was never measured on stars in that globular cluster. The work on stars in our galaxy was particularly led by Elisabetta Caffau, reporting in the P abundance on 22 MS (main sequence) stars Caffau et al. (2005),

stars in the galactic disk Caffau et al. (2011), and dwarf stars (Caffau et al., 2016). Discussions on biological and geological implications can be found, e.g., in Hinkel, Hartnett, and Young (2020).

We detected more lines of P I present in our NIR spectra observed with WINERED whose abundances were also measured. None of the aforementioned studies have included Cepheids. Our study on the P abundance is **probably the first** to be performed on stars as hot and variable as Cepheids. We confirmed ten P I lines in our spectra of which 9 had their $\log gf$ values calibrated.

8.2.3 Neutral Sulphur — S I

Sulphur ($Z = 16$), amongst the top ten most abundant elements (Mifsud et al., 2021), plays an important role, as an essential elements for life. Its most common isotope, ^{32}S , constitutes around 95% of all the sulphur in the universe. Even though it is thought to be almost an “omnipresent” element, its distribution in the universe remains unclear. Several authors, such as Chieffi and Limongi (2004) and Woosley and Weaver (1995), have agreed that the origin of the so-called α -elements (C, O, Ne, Mg, Si, S, Ar, Ca, and Ti) is a product of the final evolutionary stages that massive stars ($M_* > 20M_\odot$) undergo up to end their lives in a type II supernova (SN) explosion. The literature describing the usage of Oxygen, Magnesium, Silicon, Calcium, and Titanium for the study of stellar abundances is quite vast as these elements are easily identifiable and measured in the spectra of different type of stars (including Cepheids).

Conversely, Sulphur, has roughly been neglected for years in the study of chemical evolution of our Galaxy, probably because measuring its abundance in stars is not a trivial task as its elusive nature makes it hard to identify suitable lines for abundance analysis. On the other hand, Sulphur has played an important role in the chemical analysis of extragalactic systems, planetary nebulae, and the Interstellar Medium itself as it does not form dust (Caffau et al., 2005), making it interesting

for estimating the abundances of our Galaxy and comparing the results on external sources clinging to the fact that Sulphur is created by Oxygen burning in upper layers, the same process that Si and Ca undergo, suggesting that these elements are expected to vary in consonance with chemical evolution.

The study of Sulphur abundances in the Galaxy has posed a clear discrepancy among authors claiming that S mimics the behavior of Silicon and other α elements displaying a flat trend (often referred to as plateau) in their ratios to Fe (Chen et al., 2003, Nissen et al., 2004 and Ryde and Lambert, 2004), which is opposed to the linear increase toward lower metallicity regions (Takada-Hidai et al., 2002).

Here, we provide new insights into the use of Sulphur, from confirming its presence in our working waverange available for analyzing the abundances of Cepheids. We confirmed the already known 1045 nm multiplet (Caffau et al., 2011) plus three additional S lines (10633.08, 10635.97, and 10821.8 Å) as they meet our requirements for confirmation, i.e., not blended and strong enough to remain observable even in hotter Cepheids. Even though we improved the list of confirmed S I lines, we failed to obtain abundance measurements using all of the confirmed lines, nor calibrate their $\log gf$, in fact, only two of them passed our requirements (Section 6.1), leaving a final toll of S I 10635.97 and 10821.80 Å. Both of those two lines have not been commonly studied, nor fully understood. For instance, in a recent study by Ryde et al. (2019), a spectral feature at $\lambda_{air} \sim 10636$ Å was revealed and confirmed to be the S I line at $\lambda_{air} = 10635.9$ Å, the reason for having it absent from the main line lists was an incorrect conversion from its vacuum to air wavelengths, thus, years of investigation on its main parameters were missed (Ryde et al., 2019). Now, with the advent of IR spectroscopy, we could confirm what was found by Ryde et al. (2019), and moreover, we could calibrate its oscillator strength.

Additionally, we made use of the forbidden S I line at $\lambda_{air} = 10821.8$ Å, with a predicted transition between the ground-state and the excited state (see Ryde, 2006, for details), which is virtually unaffected by non-LTE effects making it a good indicator to trace S I abundances. We could also extend our analysis for this line to

obtain its $\log gf$ value, making our study unique on targets such as Cepheids.

8.2.4 Alpha-elements - Si I and Ca I

Among our sample of species, we can distinguish those belonging to the α -elements, being Ca ($Z = 20$) and Si ($Z = 14$) (as well as Sulphur, previously described). As it was first pointed out by Sasselov and Lester (1990) for infrared regions, specifically in the $1.1 \mu\text{m}$, Cepheids and cooler stars are “rich” in Si I lines. Recently, Genovali et al. (2015) studied the gradients of α -elements (Si and Ca included) in the thick disk using Cepheids, finding that Si displays a different abundance trend by showing a slope of $\sim 0.01\text{--}0.02 \text{ dex kpc}^{-1}$. In addition, Fukue et al. (2021) could use a large number of these lines in the YJ bands. As they also observed, these lines show a broad depth range from rather weak lines to strong lines which we rejected as they are too deep. On the other hand, Genovali et al. (2015) observed that the $[\text{Ca}/\text{Fe}]$ radial distribution showed some evidence of a positive slope. We confirmed 15 Ca I lines in VALD and 22 in MB99, as well as 4 Ca II lines in VALD. Most of the Ca I lines are found to be shallower than Ca II lines. As reported in Fukue et al. (2021), some Ca I lines have highly inaccurate $\log gf$, thus, as described in Section 7.3.1, some of the strong lines had to be excluded in order to obtain abundance estimates. We obtained in total 15 lines in VALD and 13 in MB99 for Si I, 5 lines in VALD and 8 in MB99 for Ca I, and only one line in VALD for Ca II with their $\log gf$ values calibrated.

8.2.5 Heavier elements - Zn I, Y II and Dy II

Following the work of Matsunaga et al. (2020), we confirmed a considerable fraction of the metallic lines they reported in Cepheids. We detected three species: Dy II, Y II, and Zn I. We confirmed only one line of Dy ($Z = 66$) listed in VALD at 10523.9 \AA , which was clearly detected in our spectra of Cepheids, making this study the first performed in hotter variable stars in the infrared regimes. Yttrium ($Z = 39$) is an element produced by neutron-capture process, we detected and confirmed all the Y II lines described in Matsunaga et al. (2020), most of them tended to be prominent and well isolated. Additionally, we detected Zinc ($Z = 30$) which is considered

an iron-peak element, though its origin is thought to be a consequence of a *special* s-process path since its production site is different than the one for other heavier s-process elements (Delgado Mena et al., 2017). We could detect and confirm only one line (13053.60 Å) of the two listed in Matsunaga et al. (2020), which is available in the Kurucz, VALD, and in the MB99 line lists (we only used the one in VALD and MB99), though the wavelengths for this line at each of the line lists slightly differ. We successfully used these lines for abundance measurements and including the calibration of its $\log gf$ values which can be found in Appendix E (Section E.2).

8.3 Abundance Gradients

By employing the method established in this work, we constrained the stellar parameters and measured the chemical abundances based on the YJ spectra. Now, we demonstrate that the measurements with the YJ -band spectra are useful and consistent with previous results with optical spectra by illustrating the abundance gradients, one of the main features of the Galactic disk's chemistry traced by Cepheids.

FIGURE 8.4: Fe I abundances for our sample of Cepheids compared to those from Luck (2018)

From the works of Luck (2018) on hundreds of Cepheids, which itself included our sample of Calibrators and Validators, with the exception of Polaris (Usenko et

al., 2005), the abundances of a handful of elements was provided. Our estimates of chemical abundances are in agreement with the abundance gradient found by Luck (2018) (Figures 8.4, 8.5) and prove that we can use spectra in the YJ bands to take the study of the Galactic Chemistry to the next level by including the interstellar-hidden Cepheids that can be observed in the infrared only.

FIGURE 8.5: Our abundance estimates of elements other than Fe I for our sample of Cepheids compared to the results in Luck (2018).

8.4 Summary

We have proved that our method can provide reliable stellar parameters as well as chemical abundances for different kinds of species for which we could also calibrate their oscillator strengths. The number of the calibrated lines are given in Table 8.1. In addition, in Appendix A we present a new atlas of these and some other lines in the YJ bands. Our derived abundances can be compared and seem in agreement with those in the literature. We have given the guidelines for the study of pulsating stars in the NIR falling within our parameter space, regardless of their loci. Our results can be efficiently used for planning future observations with infrared spectrographs, for example, WINERED which will be soon installed at 6.5m Magellan Telescope in Las Campanas observatory (LCO), Chile. We can look towards the future with new targets in the southern hemisphere.

TABLE 8.1: Numbers of lines with calibrated $\log gf$

Species		Number of lines		
		Combined	VALD	MB99
Si I	14.1	16	15	13
P I	15.1	9	8	7
S I	16.1	2	1	2
Ca I	20.1	9	5	9
Ca II	20.2	1	1	0
Fe I	26.1	46	42	37
Fe II	26.2	12	12	0
Zn I	30.1	1	1	1
Y II	39.2	5	4	5
Dy II	66.2	1	1	0
<i>Total</i>		102	90	74

Appendix A

Spectral Atlas

In this Appendix chapter, the following three spectra are presented to illustrate the absorption lines used in our analysis together with some prominent lines for the Y band, 9760–10890 Å (43th to 47th orders) and the J band, 11800–13190 Å (43th to 47th orders). Absorption lines labeled in red have $\log gf$ calibrated by us, while those in gray do not.

- SU Cas on 2016 Mar 17 with $T_{\text{eff}} = 6495$ K (indicated by blue curve)
- δ Cep on 2013 Dec 25 with $T_{\text{eff}} = 5668$ K (indicated by green curve)
- X Cyg on 2014 Sep 15 with $T_{\text{eff}} = 4792$ K (indicated by orange curve)

FIGURE A.1: Order 57 ($9760 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 9920\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.2: **Order 56** ($9920 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 10100\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.3: **Order 55** ($10100 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 10280 \text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.4: **Order 54** ($10280 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 10480\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.5: **Order 53** ($10480 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 10680\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.6: Order 52 ($10680 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 10890\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.7: **Order 47** ($11800 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 12050 \text{ \AA}$)

FIGURE A.8: **Order 46** ($12050 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 12320\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.9: **Order 45** ($12320 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 12600\text{\AA}$)

FIGURE A.10: **Order 44** ($12600 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 12900\text{Å}$)

FIGURE A.11: **Order 43** ($12900 < \lambda_{\text{air}} < 13190\text{Å}$)

Appendix B

Light Curves

B.1 Calibrators

B.1.1 δ Cephei

FIGURE B.1: Light Curve of δ Cephei in V band and Visual band.

B.1.2 η Aquilae

FIGURE B.2: Light Curve of η Aquilae in V band and Visual band.

B.1.3 FF Aquilae

FIGURE B.3: Light Curve of FF Aquilae in V band and Visual band.

B.1.4 RT Aurigae

FIGURE B.4: Light Curve of RT Aurigae in V band and Visual band.

B.1.5 SU Cassiopeiae

FIGURE B.5: Light Curve of SU Cassiopeia in V band and Visual band.

B.1.6 SZ Tauri

FIGURE B.6: Light Curve of SZ Tauri in V band and Visual band.

B.1.7 X Cygni

FIGURE B.7: Light Curve of X Cygni in V band and Visual band.

B.1.8 ζ GeminorumFIGURE B.8: Light Curve of ζ Geminorum in V band and Visual band.

B.2 Validators

B.2.1 DL Cassiopeia

FIGURE B.9: Light Curve of DL Cassiopeia in V band and Visual band.

B.2.2 Polaris

FIGURE B.10: Light Curve of Polaris in V band and Visual band.

B.2.3 S Sagittae

FIGURE B.11: Light Curve of S Sagittae in V band and Visual band.

B.2.4 T Vultur

FIGURE B.12: Light Curve of T Vultur in V band and Visual band.

B.2.5 V367 Scuti

Galactic double mode Cepheids (also called beat Cepheids)

FIGURE B.13: Light Curve of V367 Scuti in V band and Visual band.

Appendix C

LDR relations

We present the LDR- T_{eff} relations for the Fe I–Fe I pairs and the LDR- T_{eff} - $\log g$ relations for the Fe I–Fe II and Ca I–Ca II pairs (Table 4.1). In addition to our targets (Calibrator Cepheids) used for deriving the relations, the plots show the sample analyzed in Matsunaga et al. (2021) though the latter is not included in the analysis.

FIGURE C.1: **Line Pair 1:** Fe I 10155.162 Å/Fe I 10353.804 Å

FIGURE C.2: Line Pair 2: Fe I 10167.468 Å/Fe I 10347.965 Å

FIGURE C.3: **Line Pair 3:** Fe I 10195.105 Å / Fe I 10216.313 Å

FIGURE C.4: **Line Pair 4:** Fe I 10218.408 Å/Fe I 10227.994 Å

FIGURE C.5: **Line Pair 5:** Fe I 10340.885 Å / Fe I 10532.234 Å

FIGURE C.6: **Line Pair 6:** Fe I 10395.794 Å/Fe I 9861.7337 Å

FIGURE C.7: **Line Pair 7:** Fe I 10423.743 Å / Fe I 10863.518 Å

FIGURE C.8: **Line Pair 8:** Fe I 10577.139 Å/Fe I 10849.465 Å

FIGURE C.9: **Line Pair 9:** Fe I 10616.721 Å / Fe I 9868.1857 Å

FIGURE C.10: **Line Pair 10:** Fe I 10783.050 Å/Fe I 9889.0351 Å

FIGURE C.11: Line Pair 11: Fe I 10818.274 Å/Fe I 9811.5041 Å

FIGURE C.12: Line Pair 12: Fe I 12556.996 Å/Fe I 12648.741 Å

FIGURE C.13: Line Pair 13: Fe I 9868.1857 Å/Fe II 9997.5980 Å

FIGURE C.14: Line Pair 14: Fe I 10347.965 Å/Fe II 10173.515 Å

FIGURE C.15: Line Pair 15: Fe I 10353.804 Å/Fe II 10366.167 Å

FIGURE C.16: **Line Pair 16:** Fe I 10611.686 Å/Fe II 10501.500 Å

FIGURE C.17: Line Pair 17: Fe I 10818.274 Å/Fe II 10862.652 Å

FIGURE C.18: **Line Pair 18:** Ca I 10838.970 Å/Ca II 9854.7588 Å

FIGURE C.19: **Line Pair 19:** Ca I 10343.819 Å / Ca II 9890.6280 Å

FIGURE C.20: Line Pair 20: Ca I 10846.792 Å/Ca II 9931.3741 Å

FIGURE C.21: **Line Pair 21:** Ca I 12105.841 Å / Ca II 11838.997 Å

FIGURE C.22: Line Pair 22: Ca I 13033.554 Å / Ca II 11949.744 Å

Appendix D

Derived Effective Temperature and Surface Gravity

In this chapter, we provide the derived stellar parameters (T_{eff} and $\log g$) for each of the targets at each of their phases.

ID	Phase	T_{LDR}	$e_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{LDR}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{trend}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{trend}}}$
δ Cep	0.119	6158.858	109.492	9	1.995	0.129	10	2.079	0.119
	0.178	5974.720	95.670	10	2.177	0.163	8	1.993	0.117
	0.556	5564.740	52.993	12	1.974	0.118	9	1.793	0.111
	0.672	5460.668	78.134	11	1.611	0.140	10	1.740	0.115
	0.711	5530.576	41.254	11	1.812	0.104	9	1.776	0.110
	0.897	6305.770	292.722	3	2.310	0.194	6	2.145	0.170
η Aql	0.174	5851.384	86.724	11	1.755	0.145	8	1.836	0.116
	0.216	5846.917	75.231	10	1.757	0.106	9	1.834	0.114
	0.395	5674.762	90.609	11	2.070	0.161	9	1.750	0.117
	0.700	5304.119	41.614	11	1.475	0.107	9	1.560	0.110
	0.743	5357.368	145.628	8	1.439	0.235	6	1.588	0.132
	0.887	5886.794	134.170	9	1.774	0.147	8	1.853	0.126
FF Aql	0.105	6257.612	66.101	9	2.225	0.102	10	2.185	0.112
	0.594	5918.142	148.542	6	2.067	0.172	7	2.028	0.129
	0.627	6156.364	62.646	12	2.143	0.105	10	2.139	0.112
	0.737	6299.516	54.178	10	2.294	0.097	10	2.204	0.111
	0.823	6155.288	154.563	9	1.774	0.112	10	2.138	0.129
RT Aur	0.149	6303.853	168.488	6	2.207	0.151	8	2.267	0.132
	0.155	6382.660	81.993	9	2.385	0.109	10	2.302	0.114
	0.252	6069.138	47.748	12	2.136	0.098	10	2.160	0.110

ID	Phase	T_{LDR}	$e_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{LDR}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{trend}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{trend}}}$
RT Aur	0.341	5851.989	44.895	12	1.940	0.097	10	2.057	0.110
	0.422	5711.910	50.499	11	1.917	0.102	10	1.989	0.111
	0.492	5680.734	45.042	12	1.760	0.100	10	1.974	0.110
	0.620	5667.429	50.531	8	1.927	0.123	7	1.967	0.111
	0.776	5737.308	81.643	12	1.913	0.159	7	2.001	0.115
	0.920	6206.251	67.663	9	2.166	0.103	10	2.223	0.112
SU Cas	0.108	6341.471	98.568	8	2.193	0.114	10	2.502	0.117
	0.150	6420.494	123.257	7	2.305	0.121	10	2.537	0.121
	0.546	6103.989	75.763	11	2.261	0.112	10	2.394	0.114
SZ Tau	0.502	5813.069	82.707	12	1.953	0.143	9	2.095	0.115
	0.639	5799.423	56.040	12	1.860	0.112	9	2.089	0.111
	0.772	6114.620	128.669	7	2.334	0.142	9	2.238	0.123
	0.870	6099.724	87.401	6	2.034	0.111	9	2.231	0.115
X Cyg	0.030	6006.767	61.034	11	1.794	0.114	8	1.632	0.112
	0.103	5628.700	48.255	10	1.404	0.098	10	1.449	0.111
	0.353	5058.509	39.302	11	1.385	0.117	10	1.149	0.110
	0.408	4912.173	61.398	9	0.992	0.268	8	1.066	0.114
	0.582	4716.821	51.199	10	0.739	0.466	5	0.952	0.112
	0.606	4726.672	42.517	11	0.759	0.208	4	0.958	0.111
	0.685	4852.158	51.921	10	1.191	0.159	5	1.031	0.112
	0.760	5101.901	70.059	9	1.080	0.233	2	1.173	0.115
ζ Gem	0.880	5383.506	39.783	12	1.467	0.106	9	1.324	0.110
	0.028	5803.001	41.689	10	1.696	0.094	10	1.696	0.110
	0.133	5636.552	41.616	12	1.579	0.102	9	1.614	0.110
	0.200	5488.495	42.429	12	1.483	0.099	10	1.540	0.110
	0.534	5246.328	36.864	12	1.365	0.100	9	1.412	0.110
	0.626	5509.257	44.747	10	1.740	0.113	8	1.550	0.110
	0.645	5442.997	38.323	11	1.433	0.101	9	1.516	0.110
	0.791	5706.932	54.991	12	1.671	0.110	9	1.649	0.111
	0.923	5711.450	43.379	10	1.508	0.095	10	1.652	0.110

ID	Phase	T_{LDR}	$e_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{LDR}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{trend}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{trend}}}$
Polaris	0.061	6005.218	54.796	12	2.014	0.102	10	2.110	0.111
	0.268	5968.652	43.802	12	1.928	0.096	10	2.092	0.110
	0.444	5976.108	44.277	11	1.967	0.095	10	2.096	0.110
	0.520	5959.075	43.502	11	1.992	0.095	10	2.088	0.110
	0.569	6012.864	52.981	12	2.038	0.097	10	2.113	0.111
	0.757	6057.928	41.621	12	2.086	0.094	10	2.134	0.110
	0.776	6070.738	55.766	12	2.032	0.102	10	2.140	0.111
	0.988	6062.193	78.468	10	2.021	0.115	10	2.136	0.114
DL Cas	0.219	5855.625	94.278	8	1.924	0.124	9	1.802	0.117
	0.604	5310.473	83.805	8	1.550	0.158	7	1.527	0.117
	0.743	5422.091	107.744	8	1.662	0.229	3	1.585	0.122
S Sge	0.119	5996.566	71.749	12	1.968	0.115	10	1.853	0.113
	0.520	5342.743	39.696	12	1.426	0.098	10	1.528	0.110
	0.940	6097.361	107.231	10	1.823	0.134	9	1.900	0.119
T Vul	0.138	6131.199	102.707	9	2.104	0.135	8	2.130	0.118
	0.293	5798.716	52.616	12	1.798	0.104	10	1.973	0.111
V367 Sct	0.952	5580.974	227.380	5	1.129	0.185	8	1.747	0.158

ID	Phase	T_{LDR}	$e_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{T_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{LDR}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$N_{\log g_{\text{LDR}}}$	$\log g_{\text{trend}}$	$e_{\log g_{\text{trend}}}$
OCEP 0930	0.551	4910.530	100.831	9	1.301	0.322	7	0.942	0.123
OCEP 0917	0.709	5348.158	130.240	11	1.752	0.224	7	1.608	0.128
OCEP 0848	0.355	5461.809	969.438	2	0.895	0.355	3	1.821	0.517
OCEP 0788	0.539	4649.101	110.088	9	0.782	0.199	7	0.728	0.127
OCEP 0689	0.252	5528.404	101.370	12	1.521	0.205	8	1.556	0.120
OCEP 0460	0.335	5244.893	166.269	10	1.430	0.223	5	1.311	0.140
OCEP 0336	0.064	NaN	NaN	0	NaN	NaN	0	NaN	NaN
OCEP 0267	0.687	6000.802	364.164	3	2.971	0.809	3	2.123	0.202
OCEP 0272	0.331	NaN	NaN	0	NaN	NaN	0	NaN	NaN

Appendix E

Calibrated $\log gf$ for Fe I and species lines.

Here, we include the results of our method for calculating the oscillator strengths ($\log gf$ values) by following the procedure stated in Section 6.1.

E.1 For Fe I

TABLE E.1: Calibration of $\log gf$ of Fe I lines

λ_{air} (Å)	EP (eV)	$\log gf_{\text{VALD}}$ (dex)		$\log gf_{\text{MB99}}$ (dex)	
		old	new (SD, N)	old	new (SD, N)
9800.3075	5.0856	-0.453	-0.722 (0.142, 21)	—	—
9811.5041	5.0117	-1.362	-1.374 (0.100, 36)	—	—
9861.7337	5.0638	-0.142	-0.559 (0.102, 42)	—	—
9868.1857	5.0856	-0.979	-0.843 (0.077, 41)	—	—
9889.0351	5.0331	-0.446	-0.576 (0.141, 30)	—	—
9944.2065	5.0117	-1.338	-1.421 (0.166, 20)	—	—
9980.4629	5.0331	-1.379	-1.518 (0.101, 40)	—	—
10065.045	4.8349	-0.289	-0.578 (0.103, 26)	-0.570	-0.585 (0.103, 25)
10145.561	4.7955	-0.177	-0.289 (0.150, 45)	-0.410	-0.291 (0.139, 46)
10155.162	2.1759	-4.226	-4.430 (0.132, 38)	-4.360	-4.507 (0.079, 35)
10167.468	2.1979	-4.117	-4.320 (0.121, 42)	-4.260	-4.324 (0.130, 40)
10195.105	2.7275	-3.580	-3.679 (0.114, 46)	-3.630	-3.673 (0.104, 46)
10216.313	4.7331	-0.063	-0.154 (0.103, 48)	-0.290	-0.178 (0.100, 51)
10218.408	3.0713	-2.760	-2.971 (0.094, 46)	-2.930	-2.987 (0.090, 46)
10227.994	6.1189	-0.354	-0.243 (0.094, 39)	—	—

TABLE E.1: Calibration of $\log gf$ of Fe I lines—continued.

λ_{air} (Å)	EP (eV)	$\log gf_{\text{VALD}}$ (dex)		$\log gf_{\text{MB99}}$ (dex)	
		old	new (SD, N)	old	new (SD, N)
10265.217	2.2227	-4.537	-4.745 (0.156, 21)	-4.670	-4.751 (0.150, 22)
10340.885	2.1979	-3.577	-3.767 (0.099, 44)	-3.650	-3.764 (0.096, 50)
10347.965	5.3933	-0.551	-0.825 (0.087, 43)	-0.820	-0.845 (0.075, 50)
10353.804	5.3933	-0.819	-1.063 (0.069, 41)	-1.090	-1.094 (0.088, 50)
10395.794	2.1759	-3.393	-3.462 (0.071, 28)	-3.420	-3.579 (0.087, 38)
10469.652	3.8835	-1.184	-1.641 (0.109, 43)	-1.370	-1.671 (0.116, 45)
10532.234	3.9286	-1.480	-1.893 (0.104, 45)	-1.760	-1.900 (0.094, 51)
10535.709	6.2057	-0.108	-0.202 (0.098, 43)	—	—
10577.139	3.3014	-3.136	-3.378 (0.115, 39)	-3.280	-3.408 (0.118, 44)
10611.686	6.1692	0.021	-0.080 (0.067, 45)	-0.090	-0.075 (0.067, 51)
10616.721	3.2671	-3.127	-3.397 (0.097, 25)	-3.340	-3.417 (0.116, 41)
10725.185	3.6398	-2.763	-2.997 (0.127, 25)	-2.980	-3.052 (0.133, 28)
10753.010	3.9600	—	—	-2.140	-2.150 (0.082, 23)
10783.050	3.1110	-2.567	-2.758 (0.101, 28)	-2.800	-2.920 (0.102, 47)
10818.274	3.9597	-1.948	-2.274 (0.095, 45)	-2.230	-2.298 (0.089, 44)
10849.460	5.5400	—	—	-0.730	-0.768 (0.111, 48)
10863.518	4.7331	-0.895	-1.035 (0.078, 30)	-1.060	-1.113 (0.085, 49)
12053.082	4.5585	-1.543	-1.723 (0.136, 43)	-1.750	-1.722 (0.136, 43)
12119.494	4.5931	-1.635	-1.928 (0.168, 23)	-1.880	-1.894 (0.181, 24)
12190.098	3.6352	-2.330	-2.776 (0.136, 25)	-2.750	-2.849 (0.135, 26)
12283.280	6.1700	—	—	-0.610	-0.572 (0.177, 25)
12342.916	4.6382	-1.463	-1.661 (0.103, 40)	-1.680	-1.645 (0.107, 40)
12556.996	2.2786	-3.626	-4.116 (0.118, 36)	-4.070	-4.129 (0.113, 36)
12615.928	4.6382	-1.517	-1.708 (0.172, 28)	-1.770	-1.712 (0.191, 29)
12638.703	4.5585	-0.783	-1.065 (0.181, 31)	-1.000	-1.054 (0.193, 30)
12648.741	4.6070	-1.140	-1.300 (0.148, 32)	-1.320	-1.297 (0.149, 32)
12807.152	3.6398	-2.452	-2.716 (0.156, 21)	-2.760	-2.701 (0.158, 25)
12879.766	2.2786	-3.458	-3.671 (0.134, 36)	-3.610	-3.663 (0.128, 35)
12896.120	4.9100	—	—	-1.800	-1.735 (0.195, 21)
13006.684	2.9904	-3.744	-3.460 (0.171, 22)	-3.490	-3.483 (0.161, 22)
13147.920	5.3933	-0.814	-0.788 (0.172, 23)	-0.930	-0.784 (0.171, 24)

E.2 For species

TABLE E.2: Calibration of $\log gf$ of lines other than Fe I

	λ_{air} (Å)	EP (eV)	$\log gf_{\text{VALD}}$ (dex)		$\log gf_{\text{MB99}}$ (dex)	
			old	new (SD, N)	old	new (SD, N)
Si I	10068.329	6.099	-1.318	-1.566 (0.071, 37)	-1.400	-1.564 (0.070, 39)
Si I	10288.944	4.920	-1.511	-1.851 (0.078, 51)	-1.710	-1.885 (0.074, 50)
Si I	10301.410	6.100	—	—	-1.830	-1.946 (0.121, 31)
Si I	10313.197	6.399	-0.886	-1.460 (0.125, 31)	—	—
Si I	10407.037	6.616	-0.597	-0.937 (0.072, 48)	-0.770	-0.891 (0.074, 48)
Si I	10414.913	6.619	-1.137	-1.579 (0.113, 45)	-1.380	-1.563 (0.095, 46)
Si I	10582.160	6.223	-1.169	-1.218 (0.088, 21)	—	—
Si I	10784.562	5.964	-0.839	-0.838 (0.088, 45)	-0.720	-0.886 (0.076, 45)
Si I	10796.106	6.181	-1.266	-1.628 (0.104, 40)	-1.490	-1.561 (0.123, 39)
Si I	10882.809	5.984	-0.815	-0.812 (0.085, 39)	-0.620	-0.789 (0.077, 41)
Si I	12110.659	6.616	-0.136	-0.411 (0.147, 23)	—	—
Si I	12175.733	6.619	-0.855	-1.061 (0.106, 33)	-0.970	-1.052 (0.116, 39)
Si I	12178.339	6.269	-1.100	-1.161 (0.122, 45)	-1.140	-1.179 (0.124, 45)
Si I	12390.154	5.082	-1.767	-1.977 (0.098, 47)	-1.930	-2.006 (0.096, 48)
Si I	12395.832	4.954	-1.644	-1.871 (0.084, 47)	-1.820	-1.874 (0.085, 48)
Si I	12583.924	6.616	-0.462	-0.736 (0.145, 37)	-0.620	-0.751 (0.124, 36)
P I	9796.8280	6.985	0.270	0.338 (0.104, 38)	—	—
P I	9903.6710	7.176	-0.300	-0.322 (0.142, 24)	—	—
P I	10084.277	7.213	0.140	0.202 (0.129, 30)	-0.070	0.141 (0.140, 36)
P I	10204.700	7.210	—	—	-0.590	-0.543 (0.115, 24)
P I	10511.588	6.936	-0.130	-0.192 (0.116, 42)	-0.220	-0.195 (0.110, 42)
P I	10529.524	6.954	0.240	0.432 (0.055, 46)	0.140	0.360 (0.067, 46)
P I	10581.577	6.985	0.450	0.660 (0.132, 44)	0.360	0.678 (0.121, 45)
P I	10596.903	6.936	-0.210	-0.005 (0.075, 49)	-0.280	-0.074 (0.096, 49)
P I	10813.141	6.985	-0.410	-0.395 (0.128, 33)	-0.440	-0.409 (0.153, 36)
Si I	10635.970	8.580	—	—	0.380	0.478 (0.116, 49)
Si I	10821.180	0.000	-8.607	-8.762 (0.074, 32)	-8.550	-8.743 (0.101, 39)
Ca I	10343.819	2.932	-0.300	-0.446 (0.106, 50)	-0.400	-0.439 (0.105, 49)
Ca I	10516.140	4.740	—	—	-0.520	-0.765 (0.160, 33)
Ca I	10791.450	4.740	—	—	-0.680	-0.740 (0.132, 21)

TABLE E.2: Calibration of $\log gf$ of lines other than Fe I—continued.

	λ_{air} (Å)	EP (eV)	$\log gf_{\text{VALD}}$ (dex)		$\log gf_{\text{MB99}}$ (dex)	
			old	new (SD, N)	old	new (SD, N)
Ca I	10838.970	4.878	0.238	-0.141 (0.113, 44)	0.030	-0.140 (0.106, 43)
Ca I	10846.790	4.740	—	—	-0.640	-0.565 (0.086, 39)
Ca I	11955.955	4.131	-0.849	-1.065 (0.180, 22)	-0.910	-1.060 (0.183, 21)
Ca I	12105.840	4.550	—	—	-0.540	-0.726 (0.168, 24)
Ca I	13033.554	4.441	-0.064	-0.415 (0.159, 32)	-0.310	-0.379 (0.164, 34)
Ca I	13134.942	4.451	0.085	-0.181 (0.198, 22)	-0.140	-0.185 (0.198, 22)
Ca II	9854.7590	7.505	-0.205	-0.277 (0.134, 32)	—	—
Fe II	9956.3220	5.484	-2.985	-3.017 (0.130, 35)	—	—
Fe II	9997.5980	5.484	-1.867	-1.721 (0.164, 40)	—	—
Fe II	10173.515	5.511	-2.736	-2.805 (0.103, 43)	—	—
Fe II	10189.060	6.729	-2.141	-2.225 (0.127, 32)	—	—
Fe II	10245.556	6.730	-2.057	-1.865 (0.198, 28)	—	—
Fe II	10332.928	6.729	-1.968	-1.965 (0.100, 37)	—	—
Fe II	10366.167	6.724	-1.825	-1.860 (0.114, 47)	—	—
Fe II	10490.945	5.549	-2.985	-2.915 (0.101, 42)	—	—
Fe II	10501.503	5.548	-2.086	-1.975 (0.086, 50)	—	—
Fe II	10525.149	5.553	-2.958	-2.938 (0.092, 46)	—	—
Fe II	10862.652	5.589	-2.199	-2.327 (0.107, 26)	—	—
Fe II	10871.626	5.589	-3.098	-2.974 (0.111, 24)	—	—
Zn I	13053.600	6.655	0.340	0.329 (0.176, 35)	0.130	0.320 (0.163, 32)
Y II	10105.520	1.721	-1.890	-1.672 (0.126, 34)	-1.890	-1.627 (0.130, 35)
Y II	10186.460	1.839	—	—	-1.970	-2.215 (0.148, 25)
Y II	10245.220	1.738	-1.820	-2.167 (0.191, 36)	-1.910	-2.246 (0.230, 25)
Y II	10329.700	1.748	-1.760	-1.877 (0.121, 24)	-1.710	-1.885 (0.125, 34)
Y II	10605.150	1.738	-1.960	-1.844 (0.118, 43)	-1.890	-1.844 (0.119, 41)
Dy II	10523.390	1.946	-0.450	-0.357 (0.176, 21)	—	—

Appendix F

Abundances

F.1 Abundances for Fe I

TABLE F.1: Derived microturbulence and Fe I abundance

Cepheid	Date (Phase)	T_{LDR} (K)	$\log g_{\text{rel}}$ (dex)	ζ (km s^{-1})	[Fe/H] (SD, N) (dex)
<i>Calibrators</i>					
δ Cep	20131202 (0.119)	6159	2.08	2.40	0.10 (0.14, 52)
	20131205 (0.672)	5461	1.74	3.40	0.04 (0.14, 53)
	20150806 (0.178)	5975	1.99	3.00	0.14 (0.17, 35)
	20150808 (0.556)	5565	1.79	3.40	0.04 (0.13, 59)
	20150815 (0.897)	6306	2.14	3.60	0.01 (0.17, 35)
	20151023 (0.711)	5531	1.78	3.60	0.02 (0.13, 61)
η Aql	20140916 (0.743)	5357	1.59	4.20	0.03 (0.15, 47)
	20150806 (0.887)	5887	1.85	3.00	0.14 (0.17, 35)
	20150808 (0.174)	5851	1.84	2.80	0.15 (0.15, 51)
	20160321 (0.700)	5304	1.56	4.20	-0.04 (0.15, 42)
	20160326 (0.395)	5675	1.75	3.00	0.06 (0.16, 52)
	20160514 (0.216)	5847	1.83	2.40	0.17 (0.15, 44)
FF Aql	20150806 (0.594)	5918	2.03	3.00	0.02 (0.16, 37)
	20150807 (0.823)	6155	2.14	3.40	-0.08 (0.15, 43)
	20160317 (0.737)	6300	2.20	3.40	-0.02 (0.14, 52)
	20160321 (0.627)	6156	2.14	5.20	-0.13 (0.15, 46)
	20160419 (0.105)	6258	2.18	3.20	0.08 (0.13, 57)
RT Aur	20140123 (0.920)	6206	2.22	3.20	-0.05 (0.13, 57)
	20151028 (0.422)	5712	1.99	2.20	0.07 (0.13, 62)

TABLE F.1: Derived microturbulence and FeI abundance—continued.

Cepheid	Date (Phase)	T_{LDR} (K)	$\log g_{\text{rel}}$ (dex)	ξ (km s^{-1})	[Fe/H] (SD, N) (dex)
	20160216 (0.149)	6304	2.27	2.20	0.13 (0.16, 38)
	20160228 (0.341)	5852	2.06	1.80	0.10 (0.12, 66)
	20160307 (0.492)	5681	1.97	2.40	0.10 (0.13, 61)
	20160315 (0.620)	5667	1.97	3.00	0.02 (0.12, 65)
	20160317 (0.155)	6383	2.30	2.80	0.12 (0.14, 54)
	20160321 (0.252)	6069	2.16	2.40	0.07 (0.13, 61)
	20160323 (0.776)	5737	2.00	3.60	-0.01 (0.12, 65)
SU Cas	20150815 (0.014)	nan	nan	1.80	0.04 (0.17, 34)
	20160312 (0.546)	6104	2.39	2.20	-0.07 (0.13, 57)
	20160315 (0.108)	6341	2.50	1.80	0.01 (0.15, 44)
	20160317 (0.150)	6420	2.54	2.20	-0.04 (0.14, 49)
SZ Tau	20140124 (0.870)	6100	2.23	3.40	-0.07 (0.15, 46)
	20160218 (0.639)	5799	2.09	3.00	-0.06 (0.13, 57)
	20160317 (0.502)	5813	2.10	2.40	-0.02 (0.13, 62)
	20160321 (0.772)	6115	2.24	2.40	-0.05 (0.16, 48)
X Cyg	20140830 (0.606)	4727	0.96	4.00	0.07 (0.14, 49)
	20140915 (0.582)	4717	0.95	3.60	0.11 (0.14, 54)
	20140918 (0.760)	5102	1.17	5.80	0.02 (0.18, 58)
	20141015 (0.408)	4912	1.07	3.80	0.08 (0.13, 60)
	20150725 (0.685)	4852	1.03	4.60	0.12 (0.15, 46)
	20151026 (0.353)	5059	1.15	2.40	0.07 (0.14, 49)
	20160317 (0.103)	5629	1.45	3.20	0.04 (0.13, 62)
	20160504 (0.030)	6007	1.63	3.40	0.10 (0.13, 57)
	20160518 (0.880)	5384	1.32	3.60	0.26 (0.13, 59)
ζ Gem	20130222 (0.534)	5246	1.41	2.80	0.01 (0.12, 65)
	20130223 (0.645)	5443	1.52	4.60	-0.06 (0.13, 56)
	20130227 (0.028)	5803	1.70	3.20	-0.13 (0.14, 55)
	20131129 (0.133)	5637	1.61	3.60	-0.04 (0.12, 69)
	20160217 (0.923)	5711	1.65	2.60	0.00 (0.15, 47)
	20160307 (0.791)	5707	1.65	3.40	0.03 (0.14, 53)
	20160501 (0.200)	5488	1.54	3.60	0.04 (0.13, 58)

TABLE F.1: Derived microturbulence and FeI abundance—continued.

Cepheid	Date (Phase)	T_{LDR} (K)	$\log g_{\text{rel}}$ (dex)	ζ (km s^{-1})	[Fe/H] (SD, N) (dex)
	20171204 (0.626)	5509	1.55	4.60	-0.02 (0.15, 44)
<i>Validators</i>					
Polaris	20160316 (0.268)	5969	2.09	3.00	-0.03 (0.13, 58)
	20160317 (0.444)	5976	2.10	2.80	0.01 (0.13, 61)
	20160321 (0.520)	5959	2.09	3.80	-0.08 (0.14, 52)
	20160326 (0.757)	6058	2.13	3.60	-0.03 (0.14, 53)
	20160419 (0.776)	6071	2.14	3.80	-0.05 (0.13, 62)
	20160420 (0.988)	6062	2.14	3.20	0.03 (0.16, 38)
	20160424 (0.061)	6005	2.11	3.20	-0.02 (0.14, 48)
	20160512 (0.569)	6013	2.11	3.80	-0.01 (0.13, 57)
DL Cas	20150731 (0.743)	5422	1.59	3.20	-0.10 (0.15, 43)
	20150807 (0.604)	5310	1.53	3.80	-0.12 (0.14, 58)
	20151023 (0.219)	5856	1.80	3.20	-0.00 (0.12, 65)
S Sge	20151026 (0.940)	6097	1.90	3.00	0.03 (0.16, 40)
	20160321 (0.520)	5343	1.53	3.40	-0.03 (0.13, 59)
	20160326 (0.119)	5997	1.85	3.60	0.03 (0.14, 52)
T Vul	20150808 (0.138)	6131	2.13	2.80	-0.01 (0.15, 47)
	20160514 (0.293)	5799	1.97	2.20	-0.04 (0.14, 52)
V367 Sct	20160419 (0.952)	5581	1.75	3.60	-0.22 (0.13, 56)
<i>Disk Targets</i>					
OCEP 0930	20170207 (0.551)	4911	0.94	5.80	-0.03 (0.20, 26)
OCEP 0917	20170209 (0.709)	5348	1.61	3.00	0.28 (0.18, 39)
OCEP 0848	20170209 (0.355)	5462	1.82	1.60	-0.49 (0.23, 33)
OCEP 0788	20170207 (0.539)	4649	0.73	3.00	0.12 (0.21, 23)
OCEP 0689	20170208 (0.252)	5528	1.56	2.00	0.01 (0.17, 53)
OCEP 0460	20170210 (0.335)	5245	1.31	3.20	-0.24 (0.18, 51)
OCEP 0267	20170212 (0.687)	6001	2.12	3.20	-0.09 (0.36, 33)

F.2 Abundances for Species

TABLE F.2: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 1)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Si I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{P I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{S I}/\text{H}]$
δ Cep	20131202	0.33 (0.08, 19)	0.11 (0.05, 10)	0.32 (0.05, 3)
	20131205	0.21 (0.04, 22)	-0.01 (0.05, 9)	0.20 (0.06, 3)
	20150806	0.29 (0.12, 12)	0.10 (0.04, 9)	0.25 (0.12, 1)
	20150808	0.24 (0.05, 16)	0.00 (0.05, 11)	0.27 (0.08, 3)
	20150815	0.25 (0.10, 21)	-0.01 (0.04, 12)	-0.00 (0.27, 3)
	20151023	0.19 (0.04, 24)	-0.03 (0.03, 12)	0.15 (0.05, 3)
η Aql	20140916	0.18 (0.18, 13)	0.08 (0.20, 9)	0.52 (0.18, 2)
	20150806	0.33 (0.13, 19)	0.19 (0.16, 11)	0.14 (0.11, 2)
	20150808	0.30 (0.11, 26)	0.12 (0.11, 14)	0.35 (0.10, 3)
	20160321	0.12 (0.08, 22)	0.02 (0.12, 11)	0.27 (0.17, 3)
	20160326	0.28 (0.08, 26)	0.07 (0.07, 12)	0.34 (0.12, 3)
	20160514	0.32 (0.06, 22)	0.15 (0.08, 10)	0.39 (0.05, 3)
FF Aql	20150806	0.13 (0.11, 15)	0.05 (0.10, 9)	0.29 (0.12, 1)
	20150807	0.19 (0.12, 22)	0.06 (0.07, 8)	0.36 (0.12, 1)
	20160317	0.21 (0.07, 25)	0.06 (0.03, 11)	0.16 (0.23, 2)
	20160321	0.10 (0.09, 23)	-0.01 (0.08, 13)	0.17 (0.08, 3)
	20160419	0.24 (0.07, 25)	0.05 (0.06, 13)	0.29 (0.05, 3)
RT Aur	20140123	0.19 (0.07, 21)	0.03 (0.04, 12)	0.36 (0.12, 1)
	20151028	0.27 (0.06, 26)	0.08 (0.04, 12)	0.31 (0.06, 3)
	20160216	0.30 (0.11, 27)	0.09 (0.05, 14)	0.44 (0.12, 1)
	20160228	0.31 (0.06, 25)	0.07 (0.07, 15)	0.29 (0.05, 3)
	20160307	0.21 (0.07, 25)	0.05 (0.06, 12)	0.22 (0.05, 3)
	20160315	0.20 (0.07, 22)	0.03 (0.05, 11)	0.25 (0.09, 3)
	20160317	0.27 (0.07, 21)	0.07 (0.06, 12)	0.36 (0.11, 2)
	20160321	0.27 (0.06, 27)	0.03 (0.08, 15)	0.22 (0.12, 1)
	20160323	0.20 (0.07, 18)	0.02 (0.06, 9)	0.26 (0.05, 3)
SU Cas	20150815	0.27 (0.10, 16)	0.09 (0.13, 12)	0.45 (0.12, 1)
	20160312	0.20 (0.09, 26)	0.04 (0.05, 14)	0.21 (0.08, 2)
	20160315	0.21 (0.05, 21)	0.04 (0.09, 11)	0.36 (0.12, 1)
	20160317	0.18 (0.06, 21)	0.04 (0.04, 14)	0.26 (0.12, 1)
SZ Tau	20140124	0.10 (0.09, 20)	-0.04 (0.06, 12)	0.20 (0.06, 2)
	20160218	0.16 (0.06, 23)	0.00 (0.05, 14)	0.17 (0.08, 2)
	20160317	0.21 (0.04, 24)	0.03 (0.05, 15)	0.17 (0.08, 2)
	20160321	0.18 (0.13, 21)	0.02 (0.08, 12)	0.34 (0.12, 1)

TABLE F.2: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 1 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Si I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{P I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{S I}/\text{H}]$
X Cyg	20140830	0.17 (0.16, 13)	−0.09 (0.11, 3)	0.29 (0.35, 3)
	20140915	0.21 (0.17, 14)	−0.18 (0.29, 4)	0.35 (0.24, 3)
	20140918	0.21 (0.20, 17)	−0.13 (0.38, 4)	0.15 (0.08, 3)
	20141015	0.10 (0.11, 15)	0.05 (0.13, 6)	0.39 (0.16, 3)
	20150725	0.25 (0.18, 8)	−0.10 (0.31, 5)	0.25 (0.27, 3)
	20151026	0.26 (0.07, 14)	0.17 (0.09, 12)	0.34 (0.07, 2)
	20160317	0.28 (0.10, 20)	0.06 (0.05, 11)	0.19 (0.09, 3)
	20160504	0.29 (0.13, 26)	0.03 (0.12, 14)	0.37 (0.10, 3)
	20160518	0.32 (0.12, 22)	−0.06 (0.12, 8)	−0.05 (0.12, 1)
ζ Gem	20130222	0.21 (0.09, 21)	−0.06 (0.10, 11)	0.12 (0.12, 1)
	20130223	0.10 (0.09, 21)	−0.19 (0.10, 10)	0.18 (0.20, 3)
	20130227	0.12 (0.05, 25)	−0.03 (0.06, 11)	0.15 (0.09, 2)
	20131129	0.13 (0.04, 26)	−0.08 (0.04, 15)	0.15 (0.06, 3)
	20160217	0.24 (0.06, 23)	0.02 (0.04, 13)	0.28 (0.06, 3)
	20160307	0.21 (0.03, 22)	−0.05 (0.03, 11)	0.14 (0.12, 1)
	20160501	0.17 (0.05, 28)	−0.01 (0.06, 15)	0.18 (0.11, 3)
	20171204	0.14 (0.06, 21)	−0.09 (0.03, 6)	0.16 (0.11, 3)
Polaris	20160316	0.19 (0.06, 23)	0.01 (0.05, 12)	0.32 (0.09, 3)
	20160317	0.25 (0.07, 23)	0.02 (0.06, 13)	0.27 (0.08, 2)
	20160321	0.15 (0.07, 21)	−0.02 (0.05, 12)	0.15 (0.07, 3)
	20160326	0.18 (0.06, 23)	−0.03 (0.04, 14)	0.27 (0.11, 3)
	20160419	0.16 (0.06, 23)	−0.02 (0.06, 14)	0.17 (0.08, 2)
	20160420	0.22 (0.06, 20)	0.04 (0.09, 15)	0.17 (0.12, 1)
	20160424	0.21 (0.08, 22)	0.01 (0.07, 11)	0.20 (0.05, 3)
	20160512	0.15 (0.05, 23)	−0.06 (0.04, 14)	0.19 (0.13, 2)
DL Cas	20150731	0.23 (0.11, 16)	−0.09 (0.18, 6)	0.41 (0.20, 2)
	20150807	0.21 (0.24, 19)	0.09 (0.16, 7)	0.16 (0.06, 3)
	20151023	0.19 (0.08, 24)	−0.08 (0.11, 9)	0.39 (0.05, 3)
S Sge	20151026	0.25 (0.08, 21)	0.07 (0.04, 10)	0.42 (0.12, 1)
	20160321	0.24 (0.06, 18)	0.03 (0.04, 11)	0.21 (0.05, 3)
	20160326	0.24 (0.07, 23)	0.00 (0.04, 14)	0.23 (0.05, 3)
T Vul	20150808	0.23 (0.07, 19)	−0.03 (0.07, 13)	0.17 (0.12, 1)
	20160514	0.18 (0.09, 25)	0.02 (0.07, 13)	0.24 (0.05, 3)
V367 Sct	20160419	0.10 (0.13, 21)	0.03 (0.09, 10)	0.34 (0.05, 3)
OCEP 0930	20170207	0.02 (0.16, 11)	−0.28 (0.19, 3)	0.45 (0.05, 3)
OCEP 0917	20170209	0.41 (0.23, 14)	0.08 (0.21, 6)	0.60 (0.14, 3)

TABLE F.2: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 1 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Si I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{P I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{S I}/\text{H}]$
OCEP 0848	20170209	0.02 (0.18, 13)	0.29 (0.12, 4)	-0.04 (0.08, 2)
OCEP 0788	20170207	0.27 (0.09, 10)	0.92 (0.29, 2)	0.30 (0.12, 1)
OCEP 0689	20170208	0.29 (0.30, 19)	0.07 (0.10, 7)	0.13 (0.10, 3)
OCEP 0460	20170210	-0.14 (0.10, 9)	-0.10 (0.05, 5)	-0.10 (0.10, 1)
OCEP 0267	20170212	-0.03 (0.18, 18)	-0.32 (0.42, 3)	0.06 (0.74, 2)

TABLE F.3: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 2)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Ca I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Ca II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Fe II}/\text{H}]$
δ Cep	20131202	0.15 (0.10, 8)	0.60 (0.13, 1)	0.12 (0.10, 9)
	20131205	0.21 (0.05, 7)	0.32 (0.13, 1)	0.03 (0.08, 6)
	20150806	—	0.70 (0.13, 1)	0.12 (0.18, 8)
	20150808	0.22 (0.08, 5)	—	0.01 (0.06, 3)
	20150815	0.09 (0.08, 4)	0.61 (0.13, 1)	0.08 (0.11, 8)
	20151023	0.20 (0.07, 12)	0.25 (0.13, 1)	0.02 (0.06, 9)
η Aql	20140916	0.26 (0.24, 7)	0.45 (0.13, 1)	0.15 (0.29, 7)
	20150806	0.33 (0.11, 4)	—	0.10 (0.14, 10)
	20150808	0.27 (0.16, 7)	0.49 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.09, 10)
	20160321	0.18 (0.14, 7)	—	-0.05 (0.09, 7)
	20160326	0.25 (0.10, 6)	0.38 (0.13, 1)	-0.01 (0.25, 8)
	20160514	0.18 (0.11, 2)	0.77 (0.13, 1)	0.11 (0.16, 9)
FF Aql	20150806	0.21 (0.38, 3)	0.69 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.19, 6)
	20150807	0.31 (0.20, 6)	0.38 (0.13, 1)	0.06 (0.10, 11)
	20160317	0.12 (0.04, 6)	—	0.06 (0.10, 12)
	20160321	0.05 (0.17, 8)	—	-0.04 (0.11, 11)
	20160419	0.18 (0.06, 9)	—	0.03 (0.09, 11)
RT Aur	20140123	0.08 (0.12, 11)	0.52 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.08, 11)
	20151028	0.26 (0.09, 7)	0.52 (0.13, 1)	0.10 (0.06, 10)
	20160216	0.42 (0.13, 8)	0.66 (0.13, 1)	0.16 (0.09, 10)
	20160228	0.22 (0.04, 11)	0.47 (0.13, 1)	0.05 (0.07, 11)
	20160307	0.15 (0.13, 7)	—	0.07 (0.09, 11)
	20160315	0.19 (0.08, 8)	—	0.01 (0.06, 9)
	20160317	0.29 (0.12, 12)	0.37 (0.13, 1)	0.05 (0.05, 11)
	20160321	0.21 (0.07, 11)	—	-0.03 (0.09, 11)
	20160323	0.28 (0.12, 7)	0.41 (0.13, 1)	0.08 (0.06, 10)
SU Cas	20150815	0.30 (0.05, 5)	0.68 (0.13, 1)	0.18 (0.23, 8)
	20160312	0.12 (0.07, 13)	0.47 (0.13, 1)	0.00 (0.09, 10)

TABLE F.3: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 2 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Ca I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Ca II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Fe II}/\text{H}]$
	20160315	0.15 (0.06, 7)	0.81 (0.13, 1)	0.15 (0.11, 10)
	20160317	0.08 (0.12, 10)	0.54 (0.13, 1)	0.03 (0.04, 11)
SZ Tau	20140124	-0.11 (0.09, 7)	0.33 (0.13, 1)	-0.00 (0.08, 10)
	20160218	0.08 (0.07, 10)	0.34 (0.13, 1)	-0.01 (0.08, 10)
	20160317	0.12 (0.04, 10)	0.46 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.07, 7)
	20160321	0.14 (0.17, 9)	0.49 (0.13, 1)	0.05 (0.09, 9)
X Cyg	20140830	0.21 (0.06, 8)	—	0.15 (0.45, 3)
	20140915	0.32 (0.19, 9)	0.50 (0.13, 1)	0.01 (0.28, 5)
	20140918	0.20 (0.26, 4)	—	-0.07 (0.18, 5)
	20141015	0.35 (0.10, 8)	—	0.02 (0.18, 5)
	20150725	0.13 (0.22, 7)	—	-0.13 (0.23, 3)
	20151026	0.29 (0.07, 7)	0.78 (0.13, 1)	0.22 (0.15, 9)
	20160317	0.24 (0.08, 3)	0.45 (0.13, 1)	0.09 (0.10, 8)
	20160504	0.25 (0.07, 6)	0.35 (0.13, 1)	0.12 (0.07, 11)
	20160518	0.29 (0.10, 6)	0.08 (0.13, 1)	-0.05 (0.13, 8)
ζ Gem	20130222	0.14 (0.09, 9)	—	-0.08 (0.07, 5)
	20130223	0.10 (0.12, 9)	—	-0.21 (0.07, 7)
	20130227	0.12 (0.09, 8)	0.44 (0.13, 1)	-0.07 (0.05, 7)
	20131129	0.10 (0.04, 9)	0.16 (0.13, 1)	-0.08 (0.07, 11)
	20160217	0.13 (0.04, 8)	0.61 (0.13, 1)	0.03 (0.06, 10)
	20160307	0.15 (0.05, 6)	0.36 (0.13, 1)	-0.06 (0.06, 9)
	20160501	0.15 (0.06, 10)	0.17 (0.13, 1)	-0.07 (0.07, 10)
	20171204	0.17 (0.05, 5)	0.09 (0.13, 1)	-0.19 (0.16, 7)
Polaris	20160316	0.13 (0.06, 9)	0.42 (0.13, 1)	0.01 (0.06, 10)
	20160317	0.14 (0.05, 8)	0.47 (0.13, 1)	0.06 (0.07, 10)
	20160321	0.11 (0.10, 6)	0.23 (0.13, 1)	-0.02 (0.04, 10)
	20160326	0.20 (0.05, 5)	0.31 (0.13, 1)	0.00 (0.04, 11)
	20160419	0.14 (0.15, 10)	0.15 (0.13, 1)	-0.01 (0.07, 9)
	20160420	0.18 (0.09, 5)	0.40 (0.13, 1)	0.01 (0.05, 8)
	20160424	0.27 (0.10, 4)	0.43 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.07, 10)
	20160512	0.18 (0.05, 7)	0.22 (0.13, 1)	-0.03 (0.06, 11)
DL Cas	20150731	0.14 (0.12, 4)	—	0.02 (0.09, 6)
	20150807	0.19 (0.14, 4)	—	0.03 (0.22, 6)
	20151023	0.22 (0.07, 5)	0.20 (0.13, 1)	-0.01 (0.10, 6)
S Sge	20151026	0.21 (0.05, 4)	0.65 (0.13, 1)	0.11 (0.08, 9)
	20160321	0.20 (0.07, 7)	0.25 (0.13, 1)	0.07 (0.09, 6)

TABLE F.3: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 2 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Ca I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Ca II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Fe II}/\text{H}]$
	20160326	0.14 (0.05, 4)	0.26 (0.13, 1)	0.06 (0.04, 9)
T Vul	20150808	0.12 (0.07, 5)	—	−0.03 (0.08, 8)
	20160514	0.08 (0.12, 8)	0.28 (0.13, 1)	−0.02 (0.13, 9)
V367 Sct	20160419	0.03 (0.12, 9)	0.34 (0.13, 1)	0.09 (0.12, 8)
OCEP 0930	20170207	0.25 (0.13, 4)	—	−0.34 (0.08, 3)
OCEP 0917	20170209	0.21 (0.07, 8)	—	0.32 (0.19, 5)
OCEP 0848	20170209	0.20 (0.19, 3)	0.50 (0.13, 1)	0.47 (0.09, 2)
OCEP 0788	20170207	0.25 (0.25, 5)	—	0.17 (0.56, 4)
OCEP 0689	20170208	0.25 (0.09, 4)	0.92 (0.13, 1)	−0.01 (0.20, 6)
OCEP 0460	20170210	−0.12 (0.11, 7)	−0.26 (0.13, 1)	−0.06 (0.14, 4)
OCEP 0267	20170212	−0.01 (0.60, 4)	—	−0.43 (0.08, 2)

TABLE F.4: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 3)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Zn I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Y II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Dy II}/\text{H}]$
δ Cep	20131202	—	0.34 (0.12, 4)	—
	20131205	0.20 (0.12, 2)	0.20 (0.10, 7)	—
	20150806	—	0.42 (0.07, 8)	—
	20150808	—	0.33 (0.07, 7)	—
	20150815	—	0.36 (0.07, 3)	0.02 (0.18, 1)
	20151023	0.01 (0.12, 2)	0.27 (0.07, 5)	0.02 (0.18, 1)
η Aql	20140916	−0.30 (0.12, 2)	0.37 (0.10, 4)	—
	20150806	—	0.23 (0.09, 2)	—
	20150808	—	0.34 (0.08, 6)	−0.13 (0.18, 1)
	20160321	0.40 (0.12, 2)	0.33 (0.20, 7)	−0.35 (0.18, 1)
	20160326	0.42 (0.12, 2)	0.35 (0.07, 4)	—
	20160514	−0.04 (0.12, 2)	0.40 (0.09, 5)	—
FF Aql	20150806	—	0.16 (0.20, 7)	—
	20150807	—	0.09 (0.09, 4)	0.10 (0.18, 1)
	20160317	—	0.20 (0.15, 6)	—
	20160321	—	0.15 (0.05, 9)	—
	20160419	—	0.35 (0.12, 7)	0.01 (0.18, 1)
RT Aur	20140123	0.10 (0.12, 2)	0.32 (0.07, 6)	—
	20151028	0.14 (0.12, 2)	0.33 (0.08, 6)	0.23 (0.18, 1)
	20160216	0.25 (0.12, 2)	0.41 (0.12, 4)	—
	20160228	0.07 (0.12, 2)	0.29 (0.08, 6)	—
	20160307	0.11 (0.12, 2)	0.31 (0.06, 7)	—

TABLE F.4: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 3 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Zn I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Y II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Dy II}/\text{H}]$
	20160315	0.08 (0.12, 2)	0.22 (0.05, 6)	-0.06 (0.18, 1)
	20160317	0.32 (0.12, 2)	0.33 (0.07, 5)	0.12 (0.18, 1)
	20160321	0.18 (0.12, 2)	0.31 (0.05, 7)	0.13 (0.18, 1)
	20160323	-0.08 (0.12, 2)	0.21 (0.17, 6)	—
SU Cas	20150815	—	0.47 (0.07, 4)	—
	20160312	-0.05 (0.12, 2)	0.23 (0.10, 5)	—
	20160315	-0.14 (0.20, 2)	0.28 (0.08, 2)	—
	20160317	-0.10 (0.18, 1)	0.25 (0.08, 2)	—
SZ Tau	20140124	-0.19 (0.12, 2)	0.21 (0.11, 3)	—
	20160218	-0.01 (0.12, 2)	0.13 (0.08, 6)	—
	20160317	0.05 (0.12, 2)	0.28 (0.07, 5)	—
	20160321	0.07 (0.18, 1)	0.30 (0.11, 5)	0.42 (0.18, 1)
X Cyg	20140830	0.08 (0.12, 2)	0.31 (0.16, 8)	—
	20140915	-0.10 (0.16, 1)	0.37 (0.12, 6)	—
	20140918	-0.51 (0.18, 1)	0.56 (0.14, 4)	—
	20141015	0.13 (0.12, 2)	0.55 (0.13, 8)	—
	20150725	0.04 (0.12, 2)	0.19 (0.06, 4)	-0.21 (0.18, 1)
	20151026	0.07 (0.12, 2)	0.49 (0.10, 7)	0.24 (0.18, 1)
	20160317	0.09 (0.12, 2)	0.36 (0.06, 4)	-0.01 (0.18, 1)
	20160504	0.20 (0.16, 1)	0.32 (0.06, 6)	—
	20160518	—	0.50 (0.08, 3)	—
ζ Gem	20130222	-0.11 (0.18, 1)	0.25 (0.10, 5)	—
	20130223	-0.02 (0.12, 2)	0.08 (0.06, 4)	-0.14 (0.18, 1)
	20130227	-0.02 (0.12, 2)	0.13 (0.08, 6)	—
	20131129	0.10 (0.12, 2)	0.20 (0.06, 5)	-0.01 (0.18, 1)
	20160217	0.06 (0.12, 2)	0.31 (0.06, 5)	0.13 (0.18, 1)
	20160307	0.03 (0.12, 2)	0.28 (0.10, 2)	-0.05 (0.18, 1)
	20160501	0.21 (0.12, 2)	0.26 (0.07, 6)	0.08 (0.18, 1)
	20171204	—	0.21 (0.14, 7)	0.09 (0.18, 1)
Polaris	20160316	0.40 (0.12, 2)	0.23 (0.08, 4)	—
	20160317	0.23 (0.12, 2)	0.27 (0.06, 5)	—
	20160321	0.22 (0.12, 2)	0.30 (0.09, 6)	0.07 (0.18, 1)
	20160326	0.19 (0.12, 2)	0.25 (0.19, 1)	-0.00 (0.18, 1)
	20160419	0.22 (0.12, 2)	0.23 (0.12, 4)	-0.02 (0.18, 1)
	20160420	—	0.31 (0.10, 3)	—
	20160424	—	0.28 (0.11, 4)	0.03 (0.18, 1)

TABLE F.4: Abundances other than $[\text{Fe I}/\text{H}]$ (Part 3 —continued)

Cepheid	Date	$[\text{Zn I}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Y II}/\text{H}]$	$[\text{Dy II}/\text{H}]$
	20160512	0.33 (0.16, 1)	0.20 (0.06, 6)	—
DL Cas	20150731	—	0.07 (0.40, 4)	—
	20150807	—	0.28 (0.17, 3)	—
	20151023	0.10 (0.12, 2)	0.35 (0.15, 2)	—
S Sge	20151026	—	0.29 (0.09, 2)	-0.03 (0.18, 1)
	20160321	-0.01 (0.12, 2)	0.34 (0.09, 6)	-0.04 (0.18, 1)
	20160326	0.18 (0.12, 2)	0.31 (0.08, 4)	—
T Vul	20150808	—	0.27 (0.07, 5)	-0.14 (0.18, 1)
	20160514	-0.08 (0.18, 1)	0.11 (0.07, 5)	0.04 (0.18, 1)
V367 Sct	20160419	-0.10 (0.12, 2)	0.16 (0.30, 3)	—
OCEP 0930	20170207	—	—	—
OCEP 0917	20170209	0.39 (0.12, 2)	—	—
OCEP 0848	20170209	—	—	—
OCEP 0788	20170207	—	0.71 (0.15, 2)	-0.28 (0.18, 1)
OCEP 0689	20170208	0.07 (0.12, 2)	0.72 (0.12, 1)	—
OCEP 0460	20170210	-0.23 (0.12, 2)	0.41 (0.13, 1)	—
OCEP 0267	20170212	—	—	—

Bibliography

- Allen, C. W. (Aug. 1951). "Dex". In: *The Observatory* 71, pp. 157–157.
- Anders, E. and N. Grevesse (Jan. 1989). "Abundances of the elements: Meteoritic and solar". In: *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 53.1, pp. 197–214. DOI: [10.1016/0016-7037\(89\)90286-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037(89)90286-X).
- Andreasen, D. T. et al. (Jan. 2016). "Near-infrared spectroscopy of the Sun and HD 20010. Compiling a new line list in the near-infrared". In: *A&A* 585, A143, A143. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201527308](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201527308). arXiv: [1510.08273](https://arxiv.org/abs/1510.08273) [astro-ph.SR].
- Andrievsky, S. M., R. E. Luck, and V. V. Kovtyukh (Oct. 2005). "Phase-dependent Variation of the Fundamental Parameters of Cepheids. III. Periods between 3 and 6 Days". In: *AJ* 130.4, pp. 1880–1889. DOI: [10.1086/444541](https://doi.org/10.1086/444541).
- Andrievsky, S. M. et al. (Jan. 2002a). "Using Cepheids to determine the galactic abundance gradient. I. The solar neighbourhood". In: *A&A* 381, pp. 32–50. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20011488](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20011488). arXiv: [astro-ph/0112525](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0112525) [astro-ph].
- Andrievsky, S. M. et al. (Mar. 2002b). "Using Cepheids to determine the galactic abundance gradient. II. Towards the galactic center". In: *A&A* 384, pp. 140–144. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20020016](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20020016). arXiv: [astro-ph/0112513](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0112513) [astro-ph].
- Andrievsky, S. M. et al. (Sept. 2002c). "Using Cepheids to determine the galactic abundance gradient. III. First results for the outer disc". In: *A&A* 392, pp. 491–499. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20021035](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20021035). arXiv: [astro-ph/0208056](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0208056) [astro-ph].
- Asplund, Martin et al. (Sept. 2009). "The Chemical Composition of the Sun". In: *ARA&A* 47.1, pp. 481–522. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145222](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145222). arXiv: [0909.0948](https://arxiv.org/abs/0909.0948) [astro-ph.SR].
- Baker, N. and R. Kippenhahn (Jan. 1962). "The Pulsations of Models of δ Cephei Stars. With 17 Figures in the Text". In: *ZAp* 54, p. 114.

- Barbuy, Beatriz, Cristina Chiappini, and Ortwin Gerhard (Sept. 2018). “Chemodynamical History of the Galactic Bulge”. In: *ARA&A* 56, pp. 223–276. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-081817-051826](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-081817-051826). arXiv: [1805.01142](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.01142) [astro-ph.GA].
- Belopolsky, A. (Feb. 1895). “The spectrum of delta Cephei.” In: *ApJ* 1, pp. 160–161. DOI: [10.1086/140027](https://doi.org/10.1086/140027).
- Berdnikov, L. N. and O. V. Vozyakova (May 1995). “Photoelectric observations of Cepheids in 1994”. In: *Astronomy Letters* 21.3, pp. 308–338.
- Bland-Hawthorn, Joss and Ortwin Gerhard (Sept. 2016). “The Galaxy in Context: Structural, Kinematic, and Integrated Properties”. In: *ARA&A* 54, pp. 529–596. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-081915-023441](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-081915-023441). arXiv: [1602.07702](https://arxiv.org/abs/1602.07702) [astro-ph.GA].
- Boeche, C. et al. (Nov. 2013). “Chemical gradients in the Milky Way from the RAVE data. I. Dwarf stars”. In: *A&A* 559, A59, A59. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201322085](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322085). arXiv: [1309.4279](https://arxiv.org/abs/1309.4279) [astro-ph.GA].
- Caffau, E. et al. (Oct. 2005). “Sulphur abundance in Galactic stars”. In: *A&A* 441.2, pp. 533–548. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20052905](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20052905). arXiv: [astro-ph/0507030](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0507030) [astro-ph].
- Caffau, E. et al. (Oct. 2007). “The solar photospheric abundance of phosphorus: results from CO⁵BOLD 3D model atmospheres”. In: *A&A* 473.2, pp. L9–L12. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20078370](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20078370). arXiv: [0708.1607](https://arxiv.org/abs/0708.1607) [astro-ph].
- Caffau, E. et al. (Aug. 2011). “The Galactic evolution of phosphorus”. In: *A&A* 532, A98, A98. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201117313](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201117313). arXiv: [1107.2657](https://arxiv.org/abs/1107.2657) [astro-ph.GA].
- Caffau, E. et al. (Jan. 2016). “GIANO Y-band spectroscopy of dwarf stars: Phosphorus, sulphur, and strontium abundances”. In: *A&A* 585, A16, A16. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201527272](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201527272). arXiv: [1510.06396](https://arxiv.org/abs/1510.06396) [astro-ph.SR].
- Cardelli, Jason A., Geoffrey C. Clayton, and John S. Mathis (Oct. 1989). “The Relationship between Infrared, Optical, and Ultraviolet Extinction”. In: *ApJ* 345, p. 245. DOI: [10.1086/167900](https://doi.org/10.1086/167900).
- Chen, Xiaodian et al. (Feb. 2019). “An intuitive 3D map of the Galactic warp’s precession traced by classical Cepheids”. In: *Nature Astronomy* 3, pp. 320–325. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-018-0686-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-018-0686-7). arXiv: [1902.00998](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.00998) [astro-ph.GA].
- Chen, Y. Q. et al. (July 2003). “Chemical Abundances of Old Metal-rich Stars in the Solar Neighborhood”. In: *ApJ* 591.2, pp. 925–935. DOI: [10.1086/375292](https://doi.org/10.1086/375292).

- Chieffi, Alessandro and Marco Limongi (June 2004). “Explosive Yields of Massive Stars from $Z = 0$ to $Z = Z_{\text{solar}}$ ”. In: *ApJ* 608.1, pp. 405–410. DOI: [10.1086/392523](https://doi.org/10.1086/392523). arXiv: [astro-ph/0402625](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0402625) [astro-ph].
- Clough, S.A. et al. (2005). “Atmospheric radiative transfer modeling: a summary of the AER codes”. In: *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 91.2, pp. 233–244. ISSN: 0022-4073. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2004.05.058>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022407304002158>.
- Cox, J. P. (June 1985). “Theory of Cepheid pulsation - Excitation mechanisms”. In: *IAU Colloq. 82: Cepheids: Theory and Observation*. Ed. by B. F. Madore, pp. 126–146.
- Cox, John P. and Charles A. Whitney (Jan. 1963). “Comments on Zhevakin’s Paper, “One Common Error in the Theory of Stellar Variability””. In: *AZh* 40, p. 184.
- da Silva, R. et al. (Feb. 2016). “Neutron-capture elements across the Galactic thin disk using Cepheids”. In: *A&A* 586, A125, A125. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201527300](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201527300). arXiv: [1510.06314](https://arxiv.org/abs/1510.06314) [astro-ph.SR].
- Dékány, I. et al. (Jan. 2015a). “Discovery of a Pair of Classical Cepheids in an Invisible Cluster Beyond the Galactic Bulge”. In: *ApJ* 799.1, L11, p. L11. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/799/1/L11](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/799/1/L11). arXiv: [1412.8658](https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.8658) [astro-ph.GA].
- Dékány, I. et al. (Oct. 2015b). “The VVV Survey Reveals Classical Cepheids Tracing a Young and Thin Stellar Disk across the Galaxy’s Bulge”. In: *ApJ* 812.2, L29, p. L29. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/812/2/L29](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/812/2/L29). arXiv: [1509.08402](https://arxiv.org/abs/1509.08402) [astro-ph.GA].
- Dékány, István et al. (Sept. 2019). “Into the Darkness: Classical and Type II Cepheids in the Zona Galactica Incognita”. In: *ApJ* 883.1, 58, p. 58. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab3b60](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab3b60). arXiv: [1908.08290](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.08290) [astro-ph.SR].
- Delgado Mena, E. et al. (Oct. 2017). “Chemical abundances of 1111 FGK stars from the HARPS GTO planet search program. II. Cu, Zn, Sr, Y, Zr, Ba, Ce, Nd, and Eu”. In: *A&A* 606, A94, A94. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201730535](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201730535). arXiv: [1705.04349](https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.04349) [astro-ph.SR].
- Eggen, O. J., D. Lynden-Bell, and A. R. Sandage (Nov. 1962). “Evidence from the motions of old stars that the Galaxy collapsed.” In: *ApJ* 136, p. 748. DOI: [10.1086/147433](https://doi.org/10.1086/147433).

- Ekström, S. et al. (Jan. 2012). “Grids of stellar models with rotation. I. Models from 0.8 to 120 M_{\odot} at solar metallicity ($Z = 0.014$)”. In: *A&A* 537, A146, A146. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201117751](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201117751). arXiv: [1110.5049](https://arxiv.org/abs/1110.5049) [astro-ph.SR].
- Fernie, J. D., Karl W. Kamper, and S. Seager (Oct. 1993). “Goodbye to Polaris the Cepheid”. In: *ApJ* 416, p. 820. DOI: [10.1086/173279](https://doi.org/10.1086/173279).
- Fossati, L. et al. (Dec. 2014). “An in-depth spectroscopic analysis of RR Lyr Variations over the pulsation cycle”. In: *MNRAS* 445.4, pp. 4094–4104. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu2044](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2044). arXiv: [1410.4380](https://arxiv.org/abs/1410.4380) [astro-ph.SR].
- Fukue, Kei et al. (Oct. 2015). “Line-depth Ratios in H-band Spectra to Determine Effective Temperatures of G- and K-type Giants and Supergiants”. In: *ApJ* 812.1, 64, p. 64. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/812/1/64](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/812/1/64).
- Fukue, Kei et al. (May 2021). “Absorption Lines in the 0.91-1.33 μm Spectra of Red Giants for Measuring Abundances of Mg, Si, Ca, Ti, Cr, and Ni”. In: *ApJ* 913.1, 62, p. 62. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abf0b1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abf0b1). arXiv: [2103.12478](https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.12478) [astro-ph.SR].
- Genovali, K. et al. (June 2014). “On the fine structure of the Cepheid metallicity gradient in the Galactic thin disk”. In: *A&A* 566, A37, A37. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201323198](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201323198). arXiv: [1403.6128](https://arxiv.org/abs/1403.6128) [astro-ph.GA].
- Genovali, K. et al. (Aug. 2015). “On the α -element gradients of the Galactic thin disk using Cepheids”. In: *A&A* 580, A17, A17. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201525894](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201525894). arXiv: [1503.03758](https://arxiv.org/abs/1503.03758) [astro-ph.SR].
- Gilmore, G. and N. Reid (Mar. 1983). “New light on faint stars - III. Galactic structure towards the South Pole and the Galactic thick disc.” In: *MNRAS* 202, pp. 1025–1047. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/202.4.1025](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/202.4.1025).
- Goodricke, John (Jan. 1786). “A Series of Observations on, and a Discovery of, the Period of the Variation of the Light of the Star Marked δ by Bayer, Near the Head of Cepheus. In a Letter from John Goodricke, Esq. to Nevil Maskelyne, D. D. F. R. S. and Astronomer Royal”. In: *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London Series I* 76, pp. 48–61.
- Gratton, Raffaele et al. (May 2006). “The Metallicity of the Old Open Cluster NGC 6791”. In: *ApJ* 642.1, pp. 462–469. DOI: [10.1086/500729](https://doi.org/10.1086/500729). arXiv: [astro-ph/0601027](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0601027) [astro-ph].

- Gray, D. F. and K. Brown (June 2001). "Line-Depth Ratios: Temperature Indices for Giant Stars". In: *PASP* 113.784, pp. 723–735. DOI: [10.1086/320811](https://doi.org/10.1086/320811).
- Gray, David F. (2005). *The Observation and Analysis of Stellar Photospheres*.
- Gray, D.F. and H.L. Johanson (Aug. 1991). "A technique for precisely measuring stellar temperatures." In: *JRASC* 85.4, p. 183.
- Grijs, Richard de R. de (2013). *An introduction to distance measurement in astronomy*. Wiley.
- Gullikson, Kevin, Sarah Dodson-Robinson, and Adam Kraus (Sept. 2014). "Correcting for Telluric Absorption: Methods, Case Studies, and Release of the TelFit Code". In: *AJ* 148.3, 53, p. 53. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/148/3/53](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/148/3/53). arXiv: [1406.6059](https://arxiv.org/abs/1406.6059) [[astro-ph.IM](#)].
- Hinkel, Natalie R., Hilairy E. Hartnett, and Patrick A. Young (Sept. 2020). "The Influence of Stellar Phosphorus on Our Understanding of Exoplanets and Astrobiology". In: *ApJ* 900.2, L38, p. L38. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/abb3cb](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/abb3cb). arXiv: [2009.00009](https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.00009) [[astro-ph.EP](#)].
- Hubrig, S. et al. (June 2009). "A high-resolution study of isotopic composition and chemical abundances of blue horizontal branch stars in the globular clusters NGC 6397 and NGC 6752". In: *A&A* 499.3, pp. 865–878. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/200911721](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/200911721). arXiv: [0903.5182](https://arxiv.org/abs/0903.5182) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Ikeda, Yuji et al. (Aug. 2016). "High sensitivity, wide coverage, and high-resolution NIR non-cryogenic spectrograph, WINERED". In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VI*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans, Luc Simard, and Hideki Takami. Vol. 9908. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 99085Z. DOI: [10.1117/12.2230886](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2230886).
- Ikeda, Yuji et al. (July 2018). "Very high-sensitive NIR high-resolution spectrograph WINERED: on-going observations at NTT". In: *Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy VII*. Ed. by Christopher J. Evans, Luc Simard, and Hideki Takami. Vol. 10702. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, 107025U. DOI: [10.1117/12.2309605](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2309605).
- Inno, L. et al. (Jan. 2019). "First metallicity determination from near-infrared spectra for five obscured Cepheids discovered in the inner disc". In: *MNRAS* 482.1, pp. 83–97. DOI: [10.1093/mnr/sty2661](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnr/sty2661). arXiv: [1805.03212](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.03212) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].

- Ivezić, Željko et al. (Sept. 2008). “The Milky Way Tomography with SDSS. II. Stellar Metallicity”. In: *ApJ* 684.1, pp. 287–325. DOI: [10.1086/589678](https://doi.org/10.1086/589678). arXiv: [0804.3850](https://arxiv.org/abs/0804.3850) [astro-ph].
- Jian, Mingjie, Noriyuki Matsunaga, and Kei Fukue (May 2019). “The metallicity effect on line-depth ratios in APOGEE H-band spectra”. In: *MNRAS* 485.1, pp. 1310–1319. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz237](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz237). arXiv: [1901.07141](https://arxiv.org/abs/1901.07141) [astro-ph.SR].
- Jian, Mingjie et al. (May 2020). “The effect of surface gravity on line-depth ratios in the wavelength range 0.97-1.32 μm ”. In: *MNRAS* 494.2, pp. 1724–1734. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa834](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa834). arXiv: [2003.10641](https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.10641) [astro-ph.SR].
- Jofré, Paula, Ulrike Heiter, and Caroline Soubiran (Aug. 2019). “Accuracy and Precision of Industrial Stellar Abundances”. In: *ARA&A* 57, pp. 571–616. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-091918-104509](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-091918-104509). arXiv: [1811.08041](https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.08041) [astro-ph.SR].
- Kausch, W. et al. (2015). “Molecfit: A general tool for telluric absorption correction”. In: *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 576. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201423909](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201423909).
- Kiss, Laszlo L. (July 1998). “A photometric and spectroscopic study of the brightest northern Cepheids - I. Observations”. In: *MNRAS* 297.3, pp. 825–838. DOI: [10.1046/j.1365-8711.1998.01559.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-8711.1998.01559.x).
- Kolenberg, K. et al. (Sept. 2010). “An in-depth spectroscopic analysis of the Blazhko star RR Lyrae . I. Characterisation of the star: abundance analysis and fundamental parameters”. In: *A&A* 519, A64, A64. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201014471](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201014471). arXiv: [1004.5156](https://arxiv.org/abs/1004.5156) [astro-ph.SR].
- Kondo, Sohei et al. (Apr. 2019). “Fe I Lines in 0.91-1.33 μm Spectra of Red Giants for Measuring the Microturbulence and Metallicities”. In: *ApJ* 875.2, 129, p. 129. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab0ec4](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab0ec4). arXiv: [1903.02241](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.02241) [astro-ph.SR].
- Kovtyukh, V. V. (June 2000). “Precise temperatures of classical Cepheids and yellow supergiants from line-depth ratios”. In: *A&A* 358, pp. 587–592.
- (June 2007). “High-precision effective temperatures of 161 FGK supergiants from line-depth ratios”. In: *MNRAS* 378.2, pp. 617–624. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11804.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11804.x).
- Kovtyukh, V. V. and S. M. Andrievsky (Nov. 1999). “Do we really obtain reliable elemental abundances for supergiant stars?” In: *A&A* 351, pp. 597–606.

- Kovtyukh, V. V. et al. (Jan. 2005). "Phase-dependent Variation of the Fundamental Parameters of Cepheids. II. Periods Longer than 10 Days". In: *AJ* 129.1, pp. 433–453. DOI: [10.1086/426339](https://doi.org/10.1086/426339).
- Kukarkin, B. V. (1975). *Pulsating stars*.
- Kurucz, Robert L. et al. (1984). *Solar flux atlas from 296 to 1300 nm*.
- Leavitt, Henrietta S. and Edward C. Pickering (Mar. 1912). "Periods of 25 Variable Stars in the Small Magellanic Cloud." In: *Harvard College Observatory Circular* 173, pp. 1–3.
- López-Corredoira, M., A. Cabrera-Lavers, and O. E. Gerhard (Aug. 2005). "A boxy bulge in the Milky Way. Inversion of the stellar statistics equation with 2MASS data". In: *A&A* 439.1, pp. 107–110. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20053075](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20053075). arXiv: [astro-ph/0504608](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0504608) [[astro-ph](#)].
- Luck, R. E. and S. M. Andrievsky (July 2004). "Phase-dependent Variation of the Fundamental Parameters of Cepheids. I. Periods from 6 to 10 Days". In: *AJ* 128.1, pp. 343–356. DOI: [10.1086/420991](https://doi.org/10.1086/420991).
- Luck, R. E., V. V. Kovtyukh, and S. M. Andrievsky (Aug. 2006). "The Distribution of the Elements in the Galactic Disk". In: *AJ* 132.2, pp. 902–918. DOI: [10.1086/505687](https://doi.org/10.1086/505687).
- Luck, R. E. et al. (July 2008). "Phase-Dependent Variation of the Fundamental Parameters of Cepheids. Iv. s-CEPHEIDS". In: *AJ* 136.1, pp. 98–110. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/136/1/98](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/136/1/98).
- Luck, R. Earle (Oct. 2018). "Cepheid Abundances: Multiphase Results and Spatial Gradients". In: *AJ* 156.4, 171, p. 171. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/aadcac](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aadcac). arXiv: [1808.05863](https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.05863) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Luck, R. Earle and David L. Lambert (Oct. 2011). "The Distribution of the Elements in the Galactic Disk. III. A Reconsideration of Cepheids from $l = 30^\circ$ to 250° ". In: *AJ* 142.4, 136, p. 136. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/142/4/136](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/142/4/136). arXiv: [1108.1947](https://arxiv.org/abs/1108.1947) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Luck, R. Earle et al. (Feb. 1998). "Magellanic Cloud Cepheids: Abundances". In: *AJ* 115.2, pp. 605–634. DOI: [10.1086/300227](https://doi.org/10.1086/300227).

- Maas, Z. et al. (Jan. 2020). "Exploring Phosphorus Nucleosynthesis with Chemical Abundances in Disk Stars and Chemically Peculiar Giants". In: *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts #235*. Vol. 235. American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts, p. 110.17.
- Madore, Barry F., Wendy L. Freedman, and Sandy Moak (June 2017). "A Method for Improving Galactic Cepheid Reddenings and Distances". In: *ApJ* 842.1, 42, p. 42. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa6e4d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa6e4d).
- Magain, P. (May 1984). "A comment on systematic errors in determinations of microturbulent velocities". In: *A&A* 134.1, pp. 189–192.
- Majewski, Steven R. et al. (Sept. 2017). "The Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment (APOGEE)". In: *AJ* 154.3, 94, p. 94. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/aa784d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aa784d). arXiv: [1509.05420](https://arxiv.org/abs/1509.05420) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).IM].
- Marfil, E. et al. (Mar. 2020). "Stellar atmospheric parameters of FGK-type stars from high-resolution optical and near-infrared CARMENES spectra". In: *MNRAS* 492.4, pp. 5470–5507. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa058](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa058). arXiv: [2001.01495](https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.01495) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).SR].
- Matsunaga, Noriyuki (Sept. 2017). "Time-series surveys and pulsating stars: The near-infrared perspective". In: *European Physical Journal Web of Conferences*. Vol. 152. European Physical Journal Web of Conferences, p. 01007. DOI: [10.1051/epjconf/201715201007](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201715201007). arXiv: [1705.02547](https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.02547) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).SR].
- Matsunaga, Noriyuki et al. (Sept. 2011). "Three classical Cepheid variable stars in the nuclear bulge of the Milky Way". In: *Nature* 477.7363, pp. 188–190. DOI: [10.1038/nature10359](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10359). arXiv: [1111.6359](https://arxiv.org/abs/1111.6359) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).SR].
- Matsunaga, Noriyuki et al. (Oct. 2016). "A lack of classical Cepheids in the inner part of the Galactic disc". In: *MNRAS* 462.1, pp. 414–420. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw1548](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw1548). arXiv: [1606.07943](https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.07943) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).GA].
- Matsunaga, Noriyuki et al. (Jan. 2020). "Identification of Absorption Lines of Heavy Metals in the Wavelength Range 0.97-1.32 μm ". In: *ApJS* 246.1, 10, p. 10. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/ab5c25](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ab5c25). arXiv: [1911.11277](https://arxiv.org/abs/1911.11277) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).SR].
- Matsunaga, Noriyuki et al. (June 2021). "Line-depth ratios as indicators of effective temperature and surface gravity". In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2106.09995, arXiv:2106.09995. arXiv: [2106.09995](https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.09995) [[astro-ph](https://arxiv.org/archive/astro).SR].

- Matteucci, Francesca (Dec. 2021). “Modelling the chemical evolution of the Milky Way”. In: *A&A Rev.* 29.1, 5, p. 5. DOI: [10.1007/s00159-021-00133-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00159-021-00133-8). arXiv: [2106.13145](https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.13145) [astro-ph.GA].
- Meléndez, J. and B. Barbuy (Apr. 2009). “Both accurate and precise gf-values for Fe II lines”. In: *A&A* 497.2, pp. 611–617. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/200811508](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/200811508). arXiv: [0901.4451](https://arxiv.org/abs/0901.4451) [astro-ph.SR].
- Meléndez, J. et al. (June 2008). “Chemical similarities between Galactic bulge and local thick disk red giant stars”. In: *A&A* 484.3, pp. L21–L25. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:200809398](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:200809398). arXiv: [0804.4124](https://arxiv.org/abs/0804.4124) [astro-ph].
- Meléndez, J. et al. (Oct. 2009). “The Peculiar Solar Composition and Its Possible Relation to Planet Formation”. In: *ApJ* 704.1, pp. L66–L70. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/704/1/L66](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/704/1/L66). arXiv: [0909.2299](https://arxiv.org/abs/0909.2299) [astro-ph.SR].
- Meléndez, Jorge and Beatriz Barbuy (Oct. 1999). “Oscillator Strengths and Damping Constants for Atomic Lines in the J and H Bands”. In: *ApJS* 124.2, pp. 527–546. DOI: [10.1086/313261](https://doi.org/10.1086/313261). arXiv: [astro-ph/9908296](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/9908296) [astro-ph].
- Meléndez, Jorge et al. (May 2006). “Permitted Oxygen Abundances and the Temperature Scale of Metal-poor Turnoff Stars”. In: *ApJ* 642.2, pp. 1082–1097. DOI: [10.1086/501158](https://doi.org/10.1086/501158). arXiv: [astro-ph/0601256](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0601256) [astro-ph].
- Mészáros, Sz. et al. (Oct. 2012). “New ATLAS9 and MARCS Model Atmosphere Grids for the Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment (APOGEE)”. In: *AJ* 144.4, 120, p. 120. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/144/4/120](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/144/4/120). arXiv: [1208.1916](https://arxiv.org/abs/1208.1916) [astro-ph.SR].
- Mészáros, Sz. et al. (Nov. 2013). “Calibrations of Atmospheric Parameters Obtained from the First Year of SDSS-III APOGEE Observations”. In: *AJ* 146.5, 133, p. 133. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/146/5/133](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/146/5/133). arXiv: [1308.6617](https://arxiv.org/abs/1308.6617) [astro-ph.SR].
- Mifsud, Duncan V. et al. (Feb. 2021). “Sulfur Ice Astrochemistry: A Review of Laboratory Studies”. In: *Space Sci. Rev.* 217.1, 14, p. 14. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-021-00792-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-021-00792-0). arXiv: [2101.05001](https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.05001) [astro-ph.EP].
- Minniti, J. H. et al. (Aug. 2020). “Using classical Cepheids to study the far side of the Milky Way disk. I. Spectroscopic classification and the metallicity gradient”. In: *A&A* 640, A92, A92. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202037575](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202037575). arXiv: [2007.03122](https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.03122) [astro-ph.GA].

- Mucciarelli, A. (Apr. 2011). “Microturbulent velocity from stellar spectra: a comparison between different approaches”. In: *A&A* 528, A44, A44. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201015814](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201015814). arXiv: [1101.3426](https://arxiv.org/abs/1101.3426) [astro-ph.SR].
- Naghma, Rahla, Sultana N. Nahar, and Anil K. Pradhan (Sept. 2018). “Collision strengths for FIR and UV transitions in P III and the phosphorus abundance”. In: *MNRAS* 479.1, pp. L60–L64. DOI: [10.1093/mnras1/sly095](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras1/sly095). arXiv: [1806.01358](https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.01358) [astro-ph.SR].
- Nissen, P. E. et al. (Mar. 2004). “Sulphur and zinc abundances in Galactic stars and damped Ly α systems”. In: *A&A* 415, pp. 993–1007. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20034063](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20034063). arXiv: [astro-ph/0311529](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0311529) [astro-ph].
- Pejcha, Ondřej and Christopher S. Kochanek (Apr. 2012). “A Global Physical Model for Cepheids”. In: *ApJ* 748.2, 107, p. 107. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/748/2/107](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/748/2/107). arXiv: [1112.3038](https://arxiv.org/abs/1112.3038) [astro-ph.SR].
- Rattenbury, Nicholas J. et al. (July 2007). “Modelling the Galactic bar using OGLE-II red clump giant stars”. In: *MNRAS* 378.3, pp. 1064–1078. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11843.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11843.x). arXiv: [0704.1614](https://arxiv.org/abs/0704.1614) [astro-ph].
- Ryabchikova, T. et al. (May 2015). “A major upgrade of the VALD database”. In: *Phys. Scr* 90.5, 054005, p. 054005. DOI: [10.1088/0031-8949/90/5/054005](https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-8949/90/5/054005).
- Ryde, N. (Aug. 2006). “Sulphur abundances in disk stars as determined from the forbidden $\lambda 10821$ [S I] line”. In: *A&A* 455.2, pp. L13–L16. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20065745](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20065745). arXiv: [astro-ph/0607017](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0607017) [astro-ph].
- Ryde, N. and D. L. Lambert (Feb. 2004). “On the Galactic chemical evolution of sulfur”. In: *A&A* 415, pp. 559–569. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20034616](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20034616). arXiv: [astro-ph/0312070](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0312070) [astro-ph].
- Ryde, N. et al. (Nov. 2019). “Stellar population astrophysics (SPA) with the TNG. Identification of a sulphur line at $\lambda_{air} = 1063.6$ nm in GIANO-B stellar spectra”. In: *A&A* 631, L3, p. L3. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201936594](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201936594). arXiv: [1910.03587](https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.03587) [astro-ph.SR].
- Saito, R. K. et al. (Jan. 2012). “VVV DR1: The first data release of the Milky Way bulge and southern plane from the near-infrared ESO public survey VISTA variables in the Vía Láctea”. In: *A&A* 537, A107, A107. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201118407](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201118407). arXiv: [1111.5511](https://arxiv.org/abs/1111.5511) [astro-ph.GA].

- Sameshima, Hiroaki et al. (July 2018). “Correction of Near-infrared High-resolution Spectra for Telluric Absorption at 0.90-1.35 μm ”. In: *PASP* 130.989, p. 074502. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aac1b4](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aac1b4). arXiv: [1805.00495](https://arxiv.org/abs/1805.00495) [astro-ph.IM].
- Sasselov, Dimitar D. and John B. Lester (Sept. 1990). “Accurate Relative Temperatures and Reddenings for Cool Stars from C i Lines at 1 Micron”. In: *ApJ* 360, p. 227. DOI: [10.1086/169111](https://doi.org/10.1086/169111).
- Sbordone, L. et al. (Aug. 2009). “Sulfur in the globular clusters 47 Tucanae and NGC 6752”. In: *A&A* 503.1, pp. 121–127. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/200811513](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/200811513). arXiv: [0904.1417](https://arxiv.org/abs/0904.1417) [astro-ph.GA].
- Searle, L. and R. Zinn (Oct. 1978). “Composition of halo clusters and the formation of the galactic halo.” In: *ApJ* 225, pp. 357–379. DOI: [10.1086/156499](https://doi.org/10.1086/156499).
- Shapley, Harlow (Dec. 1914). “On the Nature and Cause of Cepheid Variation”. In: *ApJ* 40, p. 448. DOI: [10.1086/142137](https://doi.org/10.1086/142137).
- Shchukina, Nataliya and Javier Trujillo Bueno (Apr. 2001). “The Iron Line Formation Problem in Three-dimensional Hydrodynamic Models of Solar-like Photospheres”. In: *ApJ* 550.2, pp. 970–990. DOI: [10.1086/319789](https://doi.org/10.1086/319789).
- Skowron, Dorota M. et al. (Aug. 2019). “A three-dimensional map of the Milky Way using classical Cepheid variable stars”. In: *Science* 365.6452, pp. 478–482. DOI: [10.1126/science.aau3181](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau3181). arXiv: [1806.10653](https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.10653) [astro-ph.GA].
- Smette, A. et al. (2015). “Molecfit: A general tool for telluric absorption correction”. In: *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 576. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201423932](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201423932).
- Snedden, C., J. J. Cowan, and R. Gallino (Sept. 2008). “Neutron-capture elements in the early galaxy.” In: *ARA&A* 46, pp. 241–288. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145207](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145207).
- Snedden, Chris et al. (Feb. 2012). *MOOG: LTE line analysis and spectrum synthesis*. ascl: [1202.009](https://ascl.net/1202.009).
- Struve, O. (Mar. 1930). “Phosphorus in stellar spectra.” In: *ApJ* 71, pp. 150–152. DOI: [10.1086/143238](https://doi.org/10.1086/143238).
- Takada-Hidai, Masahide et al. (July 2002). “Behavior of Sulfur Abundances in Metal-poor Giants and Dwarfs”. In: *ApJ* 573.2, pp. 614–630. DOI: [10.1086/340748](https://doi.org/10.1086/340748). arXiv: [astro-ph/0103481](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0103481) [astro-ph].

- Takeda, Y. et al. (June 2013). “C, N, O and Na abundances of Cepheid variables: implications on the mixing process in the envelope”. In: *MNRAS* 432.1, pp. 769–792. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stt528](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt528). arXiv: [1303.6593](https://arxiv.org/abs/1303.6593) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Takeda, Yoichi (June 1995). “Self-Consistent Multi-Parameter Fitting of Stellar Flux Spectra”. In: *PASJ* 47, pp. 287–298.
- (Dec. 2021). “Center–limb variation of solar photospheric microturbulence”. In: *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2112.01142, arXiv:2112.01142. arXiv: [2112.01142](https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.01142) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Takeda, Yoichi and Kozo Sadakane (Oct. 1997). “Spectroscopic Study of C, N, O, and S Abundances in a Field Horizontal-Branch Star HD 161817”. In: *PASJ* 49, pp. 571–581. DOI: [10.1093/pasj/49.5.571](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/49.5.571).
- Takeda, Yoichi et al. (Apr. 2006). “On the Spectroscopic Determination of Atmospheric Parameters and O/Fe Abundances of RR Lyrae Stars”. In: *PASJ* 58, pp. 389–406. DOI: [10.1093/pasj/58.2.389](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/58.2.389).
- Taniguchi, Daisuke et al. (Feb. 2018). “Method to estimate the effective temperatures of late-type giants using line-depth ratios in the wavelength range 0.97–1.32 μm ”. In: *MNRAS* 473.4, pp. 4993–5001. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx2691](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2691). arXiv: [1710.04674](https://arxiv.org/abs/1710.04674) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Taniguchi, Daisuke et al. (Apr. 2021). “Effective temperatures of red supergiants estimated from line-depth ratios of iron lines in the YJ bands, 0.97–1.32 μm ”. In: *MNRAS* 502.3, pp. 4210–4226. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa3855](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3855). arXiv: [2012.07856](https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.07856) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Tanioka, Satoshi et al. (June 2017). “New Classical Cepheids in the Inner Part of the Northern Galactic Disk, and Their Kinematics”. In: *ApJ* 842.2, 104, p. 104. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa7260](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa7260). arXiv: [1705.02571](https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.02571) [[astro-ph.GA](#)].
- Tautvaišienė, G. et al. (May 2021). “Abundances of neutron-capture elements in thin- and thick-disc stars in the solar neighbourhood”. In: *A&A* 649, A126, A126. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202039979](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039979). arXiv: [2103.09778](https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.09778) [[astro-ph.SR](#)].
- Usenko, I. A. (Sept. 2015). “Spectroscopic studies of yellow supergiants in the open cluster NGC 129”. In: *Astronomy Letters* 41.9, pp. 501–516. DOI: [10.1134/S1063773715090054](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1063773715090054).
- Usenko, I. A. et al. (Oct. 2005). “Polaris, the nearest Cepheid in the Galaxy: atmosphere parameters, reddening and chemical composition”. In: *MNRAS* 362.4, pp. 1219–1224. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2005.09353.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2005.09353.x).

- Usenko, I. A. et al. (Jan. 2017). "Pulsational Activity of the Small-Amplitude Cepheid Polaris (α UMi) in 2016-2017". In: *Odessa Astronomical Publications* 30, p. 146. DOI: [10.18524/1810-4215.2017.30.114382](https://doi.org/10.18524/1810-4215.2017.30.114382).
- Vasilyev, V. et al. (Mar. 2018). "Spectroscopic properties of a two-dimensional time-dependent Cepheid model. II. Determination of stellar parameters and abundances". In: *A&A* 611, A19, A19. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201732201](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201732201). arXiv: [1711.00236](https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.00236) [astro-ph.SR].
- Woosley, S. E. and Thomas A. Weaver (Nov. 1995). "The Evolution and Explosion of Massive Stars. II. Explosive Hydrodynamics and Nucleosynthesis". In: *ApJS* 101, p. 181. DOI: [10.1086/192237](https://doi.org/10.1086/192237).
- Yoshii, Y. (Jan. 1982). "Density distribution of faint stars in the direction of the north galactic pole." In: *PASJ* 34, pp. 365–379.
- Zhevakin, S. A. (Jan. 1963). "The Incorrectness of Cox and Whitney's Simplified Criterion for the Pulsational Instability of a Star". In: *AZh* 40, p. 189.